
ENVIRONMENTAL DEPENDENCE OF GALAXY
PROPERTIES USING MARKED STATISTICS

A DOCTORAL THESIS

by

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Dedicated to the Universe

Abstract

Environmental dependence of galaxy properties using marked statistics

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Galaxies live in dark matter haloes and hence the galaxy properties are majorly defined by the properties of the haloes. Thus the environmental dependence of dark matter halo properties prompts a correlation between galaxy properties and the environment. More insights into these environmental correlations are crucial for the better understanding of the galaxy formation. The objective of this thesis is to explore the environmental dependence of galaxy properties using robust statistical tools on galaxies from redshift surveys and simulations.

We study the environmental dependence of luminosities in optical, near-infrared, and mid-infrared bands, as well as stellar mass and star formation rate. For that, we use a set of galaxy samples from the GAMA and SDSS galaxy surveys and the cosmoDC2 mock galaxy catalogue. We measure two-point correlation function and marked correlation function using the above-mentioned properties as marks.

Using these measurements, we show which among the properties is the strongest tracer of the environment in which the galaxies live. We also demonstrate which photometric passband best serves as a proxy for stellar mass and star formation rate in the absence thereof. In this thesis, we also test whether the survey flux limit influences the clustering results. Furthermore, we verify how well the cosmoDC2 mock catalogue - the state-of-the-art mock catalogue prepared to mimic the galaxy and large-scale structure properties in the future Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) - reproduces the environmental dependence of galaxy properties observed in GAMA and we find significant discrepancies.

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Contents

Abstract	v
Acknowledgements	vii
Contents	ix
List of Figures	xiii
List of Tables	xix
List of Abbreviations	xxi
List of Publications	xxiii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 The background cosmology	1
1.2 Content of the Universe	4
1.3 Hierarchical structure formation	4
1.4 Environmental dependence of galaxy properties in observations	6
1.5 Modelling the environmental dependence of galaxy properties	7
1.6 Marked statistics	8
1.7 Format of this thesis	10
2 Data	11
2.1 Galaxy and Mass Assembly	11
2.2 Sloan Digital Sky Survey	14
2.3 CosmoDC2 synthetic sky catalogue	16
3 Statistics of the large-scale structure	19
3.1 The galaxy two-point correlation function	19
3.2 A data sample for demonstration	20
3.3 Random galaxy sample	21
3.4 How to estimate 2pCF?	22
3.4.1 Correlation functions with different number of random galaxies	24

3.5	Redshift-space distortions and projected two-point correlation function	27
3.6	Uncertainties in the correlation function	30
3.6.1	Bootstrap method of error estimation	31
3.6.2	Jackknife method of error estimation	32
3.7	Estimation of power-law parameters	32
3.7.1	Projected 2pCF (demonstration with sample \mathcal{O}):	33
3.7.2	Test for the limit of integration π_{\max}	35
3.8	Dependence of clustering on galaxy properties	36
3.9	Marked correlation function	39
3.9.1	How to compute the marked correlation function?	42
3.9.2	Marked correlation function in sample \mathcal{O}	43
3.9.3	Rank-ordered marked correlation function	43
3.9.4	Uncertainties in MCF	45
3.10	A few words about the code	49
4	Tracing galaxy environment using the marked correlation function in GAMA	51
4.1	Introduction	51
4.2	Sample selection	52
4.2.1	Random samples	54
4.3	Measurement methods	54
4.4	Results: Two-point and marked correlation functions	56
4.5	Discussion	58
4.5.1	Environmental dependence of optical to near-IR luminosities, stellar mass and SFR	58
4.5.2	<u>u</u> -band luminosity and star formation rate dependence on the environment	59
4.5.3	The most reliable tracer of galaxy environment	60
4.5.4	<i>K</i> -band luminosity as a proxy for stellar mass	61
4.6	Summary and conclusions	63
5	Mid-infrared properties as tracers of galaxy environment in the GAMA survey	65
5.1	Introduction	65
5.2	Data	67
5.2.1	Galaxy properties	67
	GAMA catalogue	67
	GAMA- <i>WISE</i> catalogue	68
	ProSpect catalogue	68
5.2.2	W1 magnitude and redshift binned samples	68
5.2.3	W1 to W4 selection of the W1 magnitude limited samples	71
5.2.4	Random samples	71

5.3	Results	72
5.3.1	Dependence of 2pCF on W1 luminosity	72
5.3.2	Dependence of 2pCF on redshift	74
5.3.3	Dependence of 2pCF on W1 to W4 selection	75
5.3.4	Marked correlation functions	75
5.3.5	Comparison with u band and K band	79
5.4	Discussion	79
5.4.1	W1 magnitude dependence of galaxy clustering	79
5.4.2	Redshift evolution of galaxy clustering	83
5.4.3	<i>WISE</i> -derived properties as tracers of galaxy clustering	83
5.4.4	Environmental dependence of different estimates of stellar mass and SFR	84
5.4.5	Selection effects on galaxy clustering	86
5.5	Summary and conclusions	87
6	Influence of flux-limit on clustering measurements	89
6.1	Introduction	89
6.2	Data	90
6.2.1	Sample selection in GAMA	90
6.2.2	Sample selection in SDSS	93
6.3	Results with GAMA and SDSS	94
6.3.1	Dependence on flux limit	94
6.3.2	Comparison with the SDSS	96
6.4	Mass incompleteness effect of flux-limited galaxies	97
6.5	Conclusions	99
7	Environmental dependence of galaxy properties in the LSST DESC CosmoDC2 catalogue	101
7.1	Introduction	101
7.2	Sample selection	101
7.2.1	Random catalogue	102
7.3	Stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering	103
7.4	GAMA-cosmoDC2 comparison	104
7.4.1	Mock GAMA sample from cosmoDC2	104
7.4.2	Correlation functions in cosmoDC2 and GAMA	105
7.4.3	Stellar mass incompleteness effect in the cosmoDC2 catalogue	108
7.5	Conclusions	110
8	Summary and conclusions	113

A	Equatorial coordinate system	115
B	Some basic equations	117
	B.1 Calculation of separation between two galaxies	117
	B.2 Determination of the maximum distance scale for CF measurements	117
C	Different estimators of 2pCF	119
D	Luminosity evolution of the W1 band	121

List of Figures

1.1	The 3-dimensional map of the distribution of galaxies as observed by the SDSS. The centre point marks the Earth, and each other point represents a galaxy. The galaxies are colour-coded on the basis of the ages of their stars, with the redder galaxies made of older stars. The labels on the outer circles represent the right ascension (RA) and the galaxies are with the declination (Dec) between -1.25 and 1.25 (see Appendix A for a detailed description of RA and Dec.) The region between the wedges covers the Milky Way galaxy. Galaxies in that region cannot be observed because dust in the Milky Way obscures the view of the distant Universe in these directions. Image Credit: M. Blanton and SDSS	2
2.1	Redshift cone plot and sky coverage of GAMA equatorial regions (white points) in comparison with other popular surveys in the field. Image credit: Driver et al. (2009)	12
2.2	Sky coverage of the SDSS LOWZ galaxies in the North Galactic Cap.	15
2.3	Sky coverage of the cosmoDC2 galaxies in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.11$	16
3.1	Redshift and r -band absolute magnitude distribution of galaxies in the entire G15 region of GAMA. Top histogram shows the corresponding redshift distribution. The yellow lines show the selected sample \mathcal{O}	23
3.2	Sky coverage of the real and random galaxies of the sample \mathcal{O} . Here we show only $1 \times N_d$ number of random galaxies in the right panel for clarity.	24
3.3	Redshift space correlation function $\xi(r)$ of the sample \mathcal{O} . The vertical grey lines mark the edges of bins in r	25
3.4	Redshift space correlation function $\xi(r)$ of the sample \mathcal{O} with different number of random galaxies.	26
3.5	Schematic diagram showing the RSD. The blue circles represent galaxies that are far away from the cluster centre (yellow star) and red ones represent the galaxies that are close to the centre. The blue and red dashed ellipses show how a real spherical distribution of galaxies observed in real space (blue solid circle) changes when observed in the redshift space - the red one showing fingers of god effect and the blue one showing Kaiser effect.	28
3.6	Schematic representation of the decomposition of separation s into r_p and π	29

3.7	Two-dimensional correlation function $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ of the sample \mathcal{O}	30
3.8	Bootstrap copies: the top left panel shows the real sample \mathcal{O} and the rest of the panels show five bootstrap copies of the sample \mathcal{O}	31
3.9	Jackknife copies: the top left panel shows the real sample \mathcal{O} and the rest of the nine panels show the jackknife copies with different areas excluded from the sample.	32
3.10	Correlation matrix of the sample \mathcal{O}	34
3.11	<i>Left:</i> The projected 2pCF of the sample \mathcal{O} . The solid line represents the ω_p values obtained from substituting the best-fitting power-law parameters in Eq. 3.10. <i>Right:</i> The 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours associated with the power-law parameters.	36
3.12	Projected 2pCFs of the sample \mathcal{O} computed with different values of π_{\max} . The red marker and line represents the best choice, i.e. $\pi_{\max} = 40 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$	37
3.13	Dependence of 2pCFs on galaxy properties when the parent sample is split based on mean of the properties.	38
3.14	Dependence of 2pCFs on galaxy properties when the parent sample is split based on median of the properties.	40
3.15	The MCFs measured using luminosities in u, g, r, J, K bands and linear stellar mass directly as mark.	44
3.16	Ranked and unranked MCFs measured using r -band absolute magnitude, r -band luminosity, stellar mass, and log of stellar mass.	46
3.17	<i>Left:</i> Unweighted correlation function and weighted correlation functions in Sample \mathcal{O} with absolute magnitudes in $u, g, r, J,$ and K bands and stellar mass as marks. <i>Right:</i> Marked correlation functions with the same properties as marks.	47
3.18	Rank-ordered MCFs measured using the properties as marks (as labelled). The errorbars on markers represent the uncertainty obtained from 9 jackknife regions. The shaded regions correspond to the uncertainty obtained from random shuffling method. In the bottom panel, we show the combined error calculated using Eq. 3.23.	48
4.1	Selection of galaxy sample $\mathcal{A1}$ used in this chapter. The grey dots represent the GAMA galaxies with flux limit $r < 19.8$. The top and right histograms show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively. The red lines represent the stellar mass cut and the redshift limit of the sample $\mathcal{A1}$. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	53
4.2	Redshift distribution of the real and random galaxies of sample $\mathcal{A1}$	55
4.3	Sky distribution of the real and random galaxies of sample $\mathcal{A1}$ in the three separate field GAMA equatorial regions. The gray points represent the random galaxies and the red ones represent the real galaxies.	55

4.4	Projected 2pCF $\omega_p(r_p)$ with a power-law fit (filled markers; left panel) and rank-ordered projected MCFs $M_p(r_p)$ (unfilled markers; right panel) for Sample $\mathcal{A}1$ described in Sect. 4.2. In the left panel, error bars of $\omega_p(r_p)$ are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained using nine jackknife region. In the right panel the different symbols represent measurements with different marks (as labelled), and the error bars are obtained by random scrambling of the marks. The error bars of $M_p(r_p)$ are too small to be visible. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	56
4.5	The power-law fit parameters (filled star) and the corresponding 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively) of sample $\mathcal{A}1$	57
4.6	Projected correlation functions (left panel) and corresponding projected marked correlation functions (right panel) for the five volume-limited samples listed in Table 4.2. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2020)	61
5.1	Selection of subsamples used to study the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF (top panel), redshift dependence of 2pCF (middle panel), and environmental dependence of galaxy properties using MCF (bottom panel). Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	69
5.2	Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to different W1 absolute magnitude bins (as labelled) in four different redshift bins: $0.07 \leq z < 0.15$ (<i>upper left panel</i>), $0.15 \leq z < 0.25$ (<i>upper right panel</i>), $0.25 \leq z < 0.35$ (<i>lower left panel</i>), and $0.35 \leq z < 0.43$ (<i>lower right panel</i>). The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	73
5.3	Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to different redshift bins (as labelled) in the magnitude ranges $-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$ (<i>left panel</i>) and $M_{W1} \leq -24$ (<i>right panel</i>). The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	75
5.4	Dependence of the power-law fit parameters on the median W1 absolute magnitude color coded with the median redshift of the sample.	77

5.5	Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to the W1, W2, W3, and W4 selections applied in the samples \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} corresponding to redshift ranges $0.07 \leq z < 0.15$, $0.15 \leq z < 0.25$, $0.25 \leq z < 0.35$, and $0.35 \leq z < 0.43$, respectively. The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	78
5.6	Rank-ordered projected MCFs obtained using different properties (as labelled) in subsamples obtained from the W1 to W4 selection in Sample \mathcal{P} . The error bars are obtained by random scrambling of marks. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	80
5.7	Rank-ordered projected MCFs obtained using different properties (as labelled) in subsamples obtained from the W1 to W4 selection in Sample \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} . Each row represents the samples in the same redshift bin and each column represents the samples with the same selection. The error bars are obtained by random scrambling of marks. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	81
5.8	Luminosities as proxies of stellar mass (<i>left panel</i>) and SFR (<i>right panel</i>). Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (submitted)	82
5.9	Dependence of 2pCF power-law parameters on the wavelength in which the sample is selected. The samples with same redshift range are color-coded as labelled.	86
6.1	Redshift and stellar mass distribution of galaxies in stellar-mass-selected samples $\mathcal{B}1$ ($r < 19.8$; brown dots) and $\mathcal{B}2$ ($r < 17.8$; green circles). The top and right histograms show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	91
6.2	Redshift and stellar mass distribution of stellar-mass-selected samples mentioned in Table 6.1. The left panel represents the $\mathcal{C}1$ ($r < 19.8$; black dots), $\mathcal{C}2$ ($r < 18.8$; red circles), and $\mathcal{C}3$ ($r < 17.8$; green squares) galaxy samples from GAMA and the right panel shows the $\mathcal{C}4$ ($r < 17.8$; blue dots) and $\mathcal{C}5$ ($r < 16.8$; orange squares) galaxy samples from SDSS. The top and right histograms of both the panels show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	93
6.3	Rank-ordered projected MCFs $M_p(r_p)$ for samples $\mathcal{B}1$ (left) and $\mathcal{B}2$ (right) with different flux limits, as labelled. The different symbols represent different marks considered for the $M_p(r_p)$ measurement (as labelled) and the error bars are obtained by random scrambling of the marks. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	94

6.4	Projected 2pCFs $\omega_p(r_p)$ for samples $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ (filled markers; left panel) and the ratio $M_{\mathcal{B}2}/M_{\mathcal{B}1}$ between MCFs obtained for these two samples (unfilled markers; right panel). The different symbols in the right panel represent the ratio between different MCFs measured with corresponding galaxy property chosen as a mark. Small offsets along x-axis have been added for clarity. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively). In the right panel, the errors are calculated in quadrature. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	95
6.5	Projected 2pCFs (filled markers; left panel) and stellar mass MCFs (unfilled markers; right panel) in GAMA and SDSS surveys. The different symbols represent the measurements in different samples as labelled. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method and those for $M_p(r_p)$ are obtained by random scrambling of the marks. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively). Small offsets along x-axis have been added for clarity. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2021)	96
6.6	Dependence of 2pCF parameters on the apparent flux limit of the GAMA and SDSS surveys.	97
7.1	Redshift distribution of the cosmoDC2 galaxies. The red curve shows the gaussian model from which the random galaxies are drawn. The red vertical lines represent the redshift limits of the galaxies used in this work.	103
7.2	Stellar mass binned samples selected from the cosmoDC2 catalogue.	105
7.3	<i>Left:</i> Projected 2pCFs in stellar-mass binned samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ of cosmoDC2 catalogue. <i>Right:</i> The corresponding best-fitting power-law parameters and 1σ error contours.	106
7.4	Redshift-stellar mass distribution of stellar-mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 and GAMA with flux limit $r < 19.8$. The yellow dots represent the cosmoDC2 galaxies and green ones represent the GAMA galaxies. The boxes represent the redshift and stellar mass limits and the red horizontal line corresponds to $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.3$	107
7.5	Projected 2pCFs (left panel) and rank-ordered MCFs (right panel) obtained in the stellar mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 and GAMA with the flux limit $r < 19.8$, redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, and stellar mass range $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$	108
7.6	Projected 2pCFs (left panel) and rank-ordered stellar mass MCFs (right panel) obtained in the stellar mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 (dashed lines with shaded regions) and GAMA (solid line with markers) with the flux limit $r < 19.8$ and redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$	109

7.7	Dependence of 2pCFs power-law fit parameters r_0 and γ on the median stellar mass of the stellar-mass-selected samples used in Sect. 7.3 and Sect. 7.4.2. . . .	110
7.8	Same comparison between GAMA and cosmoDC2 as in the right panel of Fig. 7.6. Here the marks are the absolute magnitudes in u , g , and r bands.	111
7.9	<i>Left panel:</i> Projected 2pCFs for samples with $r < 17.8$ and $r < 19.8$ in GAMA (solid lines with markers) and cosmoDC2 (dashed lines with shaded region). <i>Right panel:</i> The ratio $M_{17.8}/M_{19.8}$ between MCFs obtained for these two samples. The different symbols in the right panel represent the ratio between different MCFs measured with corresponding galaxy property chosen as a mark. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ error contours. In the right panel, the errors are calculated in quadrature.	112
A.1	The celestial sphere. Image credit: Las Cumbres Observatory	115
A.2	Equatorial coordinate system. Image credit: Las Cumbres Observatory	116
C.1	Redshift space 2pCF of sample \mathcal{O} calculated using three estimators: ξ_{DP} (Davis and Peebles, 1983), ξ_{Ham} (Hamilton, 1993), and ξ_{LS} (Landy and Szalay, 1993). .	120
D.1	Green circles are the selected points extracted from the black dotted curve in Fig. 7(a) of Lake et al. (2018). The red curve is the polynomial fit given by Eq. D.1. Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)	122

List of Tables

2.1	An overview of GAMA sky regions.	11
3.1	The pair counts and the correlation function measurements for the sample \mathcal{O}	25
3.2	Summary statistics of the properties of galaxies in the sample \mathcal{O} ($N_{\text{gal}}^{\text{total}} = 5805$).	37
4.1	Properties of the sample $\mathcal{A}1$	54
4.2	Properties of the volume-limited samples selected based on different properties. The columns represent the property in which the sample is complete, the cut used to select the sample and the number of galaxies.	61
5.1	Definitions and the number of galaxies of different galaxy subsamples used for studying the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF.	70
5.2	Definitions of the galaxy subsamples used for studying the redshift dependence of 2pCF.	70
5.3	Definitions of the galaxy subsamples used for studying the environmental dependence of galaxy properties using MCFs.	71
5.4	Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF.	72
5.5	Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study redshift dependence of 2pCF.	74
5.6	Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study dependence of 2pCF on W1 to W4 selection.	76
6.1	Definitions of the galaxy samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, as used in this study. The columns represent the stellar mass cut, sample label, survey of origin, flux limit, and number of galaxies.	90
6.2	Properties of the galaxy samples defined in Table 6.1. The columns represent the sample label, mean absolute magnitudes in the u, g, r, J , and K bands, mean stellar mass, and 16-, 50- (median), and 84-percentiles of SFR and sSFR of the corresponding sample. The uncertainty with each property mean represents its standard deviation within the sample.	92
6.3	Best-fitting power-law parameters for all the galaxy samples used in this work.	98

7.1	Stellar mass binned samples selected from the cosmoDC2 catalogue.	104
7.2	Stellar mass selected samples from the cosmoDC2 catalogue and the GAMA survey.	106
7.3	Stellar mass selected samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ with the same stellar mass limit ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$) but different flux limits from the cosmoDC2 catalogue and the GAMA survey.	109
7.4	Power-law parameters of the samples selected from GAMA and cosmoDC2 with different flux limits but same stellar mass limit.	111

List of Abbreviations

LSS	Large-scale structure
CMB	Cosmic Microwave Background
CDM	Cold dark matter
RA	Right ascension
Dec	Declination
CF	Correlation function
2pCF	Two-point correlation function
MCF	Marked correlation function
SFR	Star formation rate
sSFR	Specific star formation rate
GAMA	Galaxy and Mass Assembly
SDSS	Sloan Digital Sky Survey
WISE	Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer
IR	Infrared
UV	Ultraviolet
HOD	Halo occupation distribution
SED	Spectral energy distribution
FLRW	Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker
LSST	Legacy Survey of Space and Time
DESC	Dark Energy Science Collaboration
DMU	Data Management Unit
SVD	Singular value decomposition
BOSS	Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey
RSD	Redshift-space distortion
SPS	Stellar population synthesis

List of Publications

The results described in this thesis are published or submitted as the following papers:

1. **Sureshkumar, U.**, Durkalec, A., Pollo, A., Bilicki, M.
Galaxy properties and their environmental dependence in GAMA survey
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3. **Sureshkumar, U.**, Durkalec, A., Pollo, A., Bilicki, M., Cluver, M. E., Bellstedt, S., Farrow, D. J., Loveday, J., Taylor, E. N., Bland-Hawthorn, J.
Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA): Mid-infrared properties as tracers of galaxy environment
(submitted to *Astronomy&Astrophysics*; [arXiv:2201.10480](https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.10480))
4. **Sureshkumar, U.**, Durkalec, A., Pollo, A.
Proxies for stellar mass and SFR in galaxy clustering studies
(submitted to the *Proceedings of the Polish Astronomical Society*)

Chapter 1

Introduction

A clear night sky fascinates probably all of us. The secret behind it has always been a matter of interest for mankind. Many curious minds explored the field and established different understandings of the Universe at different times. Thanks to the technological developments in the field of cosmology, we can now map the 3-dimensional structure of the Universe. Such advances reveal that stars combine with gas, dust, and dark matter to form galaxies and that the galaxies get gravitationally bound together to form groups or clusters. There also exists superclusters which are groups of galaxy clusters. These galaxy structures embedded in the underlying structures of dark matter form the large-scale structure (LSS) of the Universe. The understanding of formation and evolution of such structures in an expanding Universe is one of the most important challenges of modern cosmology.

Local galaxy observations reveal that the LSS of the Universe is a rich network of nodes, filaments, walls, and voids (de Lapparent et al., 1986; Bond et al., 1996). We also call it the *cosmic web*. The nodes correspond to densely populated clusters of galaxies. The filaments are elongated, and the walls are sheet-like structures. The voids are the underdense regions that contain very few galaxies. Fig. 1.1 shows the cosmic web observed by the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al., 2000). The web-like structures in the figure represent small-scale inhomogeneities in the Universe. However, the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation maps reveal the nearly homogeneous nature of the Universe when it was 400,000 years old (Penzias and Wilson, 1965; Planck Collaboration et al., 2020). The tiny fluctuations observed in the CMB maps are believed to be the signatures of the tiny fluctuations in the density field which led to the formation of the first structures in the Universe.

1.1 The background cosmology

The standard model of cosmology is based on cosmological principle and Einstein's general theory of relativity. The cosmological principle states that the Universe is spatially homogeneous and isotropic, which means that the Universe looks the same at each point and in all directions. Einstein's general theory of relativity connects the curvature of spacetime to the mass distribution in the Universe.

FIGURE 1.1: The 3-dimensional map of the distribution of galaxies as observed by the SDSS. The centre point marks the Earth, and each other point represents a galaxy. The galaxies are colour-coded on the basis of the ages of their stars, with the redder galaxies made of older stars. The labels on the outer circles represent the right ascension (RA) and the galaxies are with the declination (Dec.) between -1.25 and 1.25 (see Appendix A for a detailed description of RA and Dec.) The region between the wedges covers the Milky Way galaxy. Galaxies in that region cannot be observed because dust in the Milky Way obscures the view of the distant Universe in these directions.

Image Credit: M. Blanton and SDSS

The combination of the cosmological principle and general relativity demands that the Universe be expanding or contracting, and not static. The Einstein field equations are given by

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (1.1)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci curvature tensor, R is the Ricci scalar, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor, Λ is the cosmological constant, G is the gravitational constant, and c is the speed of light.

Then the geometry of the spacetime can be described by the Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker (FLRW) metric given by

$$ds^2 = -c^2dt^2 + a^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \right] \quad (1.2)$$

where k (with values of $+1$, 0 , or -1) describes the curvature of space, t is the time variable, r , θ , ϕ are the comoving spherical polar coordinates. In Eq. 1.2, $a(t)$, known as the scale factor, describes the relative expansion of the Universe.

The time evolution of the scale factor $a(t)$ is described by the Friedmann equations by providing FLRW metric to the Einstein field equations. The Friedmann equations are given by

$$H^2 = \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{kc^2}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (1.3)$$

and

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = \frac{-4\pi G}{3}\left(\rho + \frac{3p}{c^2}\right) + \frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (1.4)$$

where H or $H(t)$ is the Hubble parameter and ρ and p are the energy density and pressure of matter in the Universe, respectively.

The density parameter of the i th component of the Universe evaluated at the present time, i.e. at redshift $z = 0$ can be defined as

$$\Omega_{i,0} = \frac{\rho_{i,0}}{\rho_{c,0}} \quad (1.5)$$

where $\rho_{c,0}$ is the present day critical density of the Universe¹ (Einstein and de Sitter, 1932) given by

$$\rho_{c,0} = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}. \quad (1.6)$$

Here H_0 is the present value of the Hubble parameter and is parameterised via $h = H_0/100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (see Croton, 2013, for an interesting discussion of this parameterisation).

The total density parameter of the Universe Ω_{tot} has contributions from matter with the density parameter Ω_M , radiation with the density parameter Ω_r , and dark energy with the density parameter Ω_Λ . The contribution of Ω_r is negligible in the current matter-dominated era. Then the total density parameter defines the curvature of the Universe Ω_k , given by

$$\Omega_{\text{tot}} = \Omega_r + \Omega_M + \Omega_\Lambda = 1 - \Omega_k. \quad (1.7)$$

Therefore, a model for the Universe can be described by giving values of all the density parameters and the Hubble constant.

¹The present day critical density of the Universe is equal to $2.7754 \times 10^{11} h^2 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ Mpc}^{-3}$.

1.2 Content of the Universe

The Λ cold dark matter (Λ CDM) model, of many cosmological models, agrees the best with various observations. According to it, the Universe is made up of three components- dark energy, cold dark matter, and visible matter. The dark energy has a 68.3% share of the total content of the Universe and is believed to be the cause of the accelerated expansion of the Universe. About 26.8% of the Universe is the dark matter that interacts only via gravitational force. The third component is the visible matter that we see as stars and galaxies, and it contributes only 4.9% to the total content of the Universe (Planck Collaboration et al., 2020).

The dark matter interacts only via gravitational force and not via electromagnetic force. So, it is not possible to “see” the dark matter, but its presence is observed indirectly. The existence of dark matter in galaxies and space between galaxies can be indirectly observed through phenomena such as galaxy rotation curve (Rubin et al., 1980), velocity dispersion in galaxy clusters (Zwicky, 1933; Smith, 1936), and gravitational lensing (Kaiser and Squires, 1993).

1.3 Hierarchical structure formation

As mentioned before in this chapter, the tiny perturbations in the CMB map are believed to be the footprints of the small-scale density fluctuations in the early Universe. The origin of these perturbations is not yet fully understood. One of the possible explanations is given by the inflation scenerio, based on which these initial perturbations were formed during the *Inflation* epoch - the rapid exponential expansion of the Universe at the early stages of its evolution. These initially tiny perturbations then started to evolve and grow over time by gravitationally attracting matter in the expanding Universe.

We can quantify these initial density perturbations using *density contrast* defined at any point with matter density ρ , as

$$\delta \equiv \frac{\rho - \bar{\rho}}{\bar{\rho}} \quad (1.8)$$

where $\bar{\rho}$ is the mean matter density of the Universe.

The density contrast δ , if non-zero, grows under the influence of gravity. Its evolution in the linear regime ($\delta \ll 1$) can be defined using the Newtonian theory of small perturbations (Peebles, 1980; Padmanabhan, 1993; Mo et al., 2010). In this framework, the evolution of the density field ρ and velocity field \mathbf{u} of a non-relativistic fluid with pressure P under the influence of a gravitational potential ϕ is given by the following equations:

- Continuity equation (describing mass conservation)

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0. \quad (1.9)$$

- Euler equation (the equation of motion)

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = \frac{-\nabla P}{\rho} - \nabla \phi. \quad (1.10)$$

- Poisson equation (describing the gravitational field)

$$\nabla^2 \phi = 4\pi G \rho. \quad (1.11)$$

To extend these equations to describe the evolution of density fluctuations in the expanding Universe, one should rewrite them in the comoving frame by using the comoving position \mathbf{x} , peculiar velocity \mathbf{v} , density contrast δ , and the gravitational potential $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

Based on the cosmological principle (homogeneous Universe) dominated by collisionless dark matter in the linear regime, the dynamics of δ is described by the second-order differential equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \delta}{\partial t^2} + 2H(t) \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial t} - 4\pi G \bar{\rho} \delta = 0. \quad (1.12)$$

The solutions of this equation describe the rate at which the perturbations grow, which is dependent on the cosmological model (Mo et al., 2010).

The regions with an initial density greater than the average gravitationally pull matter towards them and become more overdense. At the same time, the underdense regions loose matter from them and became more underdense. This amplification of density perturbations is known as gravitational instability (Jeans, 1902). The density fluctuations evolve due to the gravitational instability to form the present LSS (Gamow and Teller, 1939; Lifshitz, 1946; Springel et al., 2005).

In the linear regime ($\delta \ll 1$), the fluctuations grow in size due to the expansion of the Universe. As the fluctuations evolve and reach $\delta \sim 1$, they break away from the expansion, dark matter segregates from baryonic matter and collapses to form self-bound clumps called dark matter haloes. Such haloes provide the gravitational potential to trap baryonic matter and thereby form galaxies at their centres through several complex processes such as gas cooling, star formation, feedback, and so on (Press and Schechter, 1974; White and Rees, 1978). We refer the reader to Longair (2007) and Mo et al. (2010) for a detailed description of the hierarchical structure formation.

On the basis of this galaxy formation scenario, it is expected that the properties of the parent halo play a major role in defining galaxy properties such as luminosity, stellar mass, colour, and star formation rate (SFR). The halo mass is believed to strongly influence the halo clustering and hence the properties of hosted galaxies (e.g. Zheng et al., 2005; More et al., 2009; Gu et al., 2016); this is referred to as 'halo bias'. The large and massive haloes have potentials strong enough to give birth to massive and luminous galaxies. Nevertheless, it was also observed that the clustering of haloes depends on properties other than halo mass— in large part on the halo assembly history

that is commonly referred to as ‘halo assembly bias’ (Zentner et al., 2014; Croton et al., 2007; Mao et al., 2018b). This means that the halo properties correlate with the environment (Sheth and Tormen, 2004). These two dependences, namely those between the halo properties and the galaxy properties, and between the halo properties and the environment, prompt a correlation between the galaxy properties and the environment (see Wechsler and Tinker, 2018, for a review) which we refer to in this thesis as *environmental dependence of galaxy properties*. Studies on the dependences between galaxy properties and environment are crucial to understand structure formation in the Universe.

1.4 Environmental dependence of galaxy properties in observations

The galaxy two-point correlation function (2pCF; Peebles, 1980) is a powerful statistical tool that quantifies the spatial distribution of galaxies in the LSS and its dependences on galaxy properties. The 2pCF have been extensively used to study the clustering behaviour of galaxy samples with different selection functions and to prove the dependence of galaxy clustering on the following properties.

- Luminosity in various passbands:
 - In the optical range, the clustering dependence on luminosity was studied in g band (Skibba et al., 2014), B band (Davis et al., 1988; Hamilton, 1988; Norberg et al., 2001; Pollo et al., 2006; Coil et al., 2006; Meneux et al., 2006; Marulli et al., 2013), and r band (Zehavi et al., 2011; Guo et al., 2015; Farrow et al., 2015). These authors observed that galaxies that are brighter in the optical band show stronger clustering than fainter galaxies.
 - In the infrared (IR) regime, the CF measurements indicated a stronger clustering of IR galaxies than those measured for optical galaxies (de la Torre et al., 2007; Oliver et al., 2004; Sobral et al., 2010; Pollo et al., 2013a,b; Solarz et al., 2015).
 - However, Heinis et al. (2004) and Milliard et al. (2007) reported weaker clustering of ultraviolet (UV) galaxies in the local Universe compared to optical and IR galaxies.
- Stellar mass – many studies showed that more massive galaxies exhibit stronger clustering than less massive galaxies (Meneux et al., 2008; Marulli et al., 2013; Beutler et al., 2013; Dolley et al., 2014; Skibba et al., 2015; Durkalec et al., 2018).
- SFR – it was observed that star-forming galaxies exhibit stronger clustering at high redshifts ($z \sim 1.5$) and that the strength decreases at low redshift ($z \sim 0$) (Hartley et al., 2010; Mostek et al., 2013).

- Colour – it was found that redder galaxies exhibit a stronger clustering than bluer galaxies (Zehavi et al., 2011; Coil et al., 2008; Skibba et al., 2014).
- Spectral type – it was observed that early-type galaxies (ellipticals and lenticulars) are more strongly clustered than late-type galaxies (spirals and irregulars) (Davis and Geller, 1976; Loveday et al., 1995; Norberg et al., 2002; Meneux et al., 2006).

The general conclusion from all these studies is that the galaxy clustering strongly depends on the galaxy properties. That is, more luminous, massive, redder, and early-type galaxies exhibit stronger clustering than their less massive, bluer, and later-type counterparts. In other words, it is more probable that we will see more luminous, massive, redder, and early-type galaxies in the denser regions of the LSS than their counterparts. These observations are consistent with the framework of the Λ CDM cosmology and the model of hierarchical structure formation.

The environmental dependence of galaxy properties are also being studied using galaxy mass functions (e.g. Bolzonella et al., 2000), luminosity functions (e.g. Zucca et al., 2009), and galaxy local density (e.g. Cucciati et al., 2006, 2010). All these results imply that different galaxy properties trace the local environment differently. A better understanding of how different galaxy properties trace the environment is needed to establish better constraints on galaxy formation and evolution models.

The main aim of this thesis is to contribute to the existing knowledge on the environmental dependence of galaxy properties, in particular to demonstrate how different galaxy properties trace small-scale galaxy clustering using observed galaxy data from Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA; Driver et al., 2009) and SDSS. We majorly explore the environmental correlations of luminosities in the optical to mid-IR bands, stellar mass, and SFR. In addition, we try to understand how the flux limit of a survey affects the measured clustering and what steps are needed to account for the resulting inaccuracies.

1.5 Modelling the environmental dependence of galaxy properties

Cosmological galaxy formation models have become an essential tool for understanding galaxy formation and evolution. Over the past decade there has been remarkable progress in the development of models describing connections between dark matter haloes and their galaxies. Those models, known as empirical models, include Halo Occupation Distribution (HOD) models (e.g. Berlind and Weinberg, 2002; Zheng et al., 2005), conditional luminosity function models (van den Bosch et al., 2007), and sub-halo abundance matching models and related techniques (e.g. Behroozi et al., 2010; Yang et al., 2012; Moster et al., 2020; Grylls et al., 2020). These models

use observations to constrain the set of parameters describing the dark to bright matter connection at a given epoch. We refer the reader to [Wechsler and Tinker \(2018\)](#) for a review of the empirical models.

On the other hand there are also physical models that predict the galaxy properties by modelling the physical processes involved in the process of galaxy formation. Such models include numerical hydrodynamic techniques (e.g. [McCarthy et al., 2012](#); [Vogelsberger et al., 2013](#); [Schaye et al., 2015](#)) and semi-analytic models (e.g. [Baugh, 2006](#); [Benson, 2012](#); [Linke et al., 2020](#)). The hydrodynamic techniques simultaneously solve gravity, hydrodynamic, and thermodynamic equations for particles or grid cells with dark matter, gas, and stars. Although numerical hydrodynamic techniques are computationally expensive, they facilitate the study of kinematics, global properties, and spatial distribution of galaxies. The semi-analytic models, on the other hand, do not involve solving any fundamental equations. They combine the numeric dark matter-only simulations and analytic models of baryonic physics. They track how much gas accretes into haloes, how much hot gas converts into stars, and about the feedback processes. For an extensive review of the physical models, see [Somerville and Davé \(2015\)](#).

Using all these models, we are now able to simulate the physics of galaxy formation and, to some extent, link galaxy properties to the host halo properties. For example, simulations have been used, such as UNIVERSEMACHINE ([Behroozi et al., 2019](#)), which reasonably parameterises the galaxy growth-halo assembly correlation, and SHARK ([Lagos et al., 2018](#)), which agrees fairly well with observations ([Bravo et al., 2020](#)). Despite all these advances, there is still a need for improvement in understanding the process of galaxy formation (see [Naab and Ostriker, 2017](#), for a review). There has not yet been a method that would perfectly reconstruct the observed dependence of galaxy properties on environment and their redshift evolution.

In this work, we try to verify if the state-of-the-art simulation catalogue cosmoDC2 ([Korytov et al., 2019](#)), which was developed to mimic the upcoming Vera C. Rubin observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST; [LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009](#)), reproduces the observed environmental correlations of galaxy properties.

1.6 Marked statistics

The main methodology of this thesis relies on marked statistics tools ([Stoyan and Stoyan, 1994](#)), in particular on measurements of the galaxy marked correlation function (MCF), which has been proven to be very sensitive to the environment ([Sheth and Tormen, 2004](#); [Skibba et al., 2013](#)). In this method, each galaxy is assigned a ‘mark’ that is defined as any measurable property of the galaxy. The MCF accounts for the clustering of positions of the marks (i.e. galaxies of a given property). Therefore, MCF measurements with different galaxy properties as marks help us to study how these different properties trace the galaxy clustering, particularly on small scales ([Sheth, 2005](#)). We refer the reader to Sect. 3.9 for a detailed explanation of the MCFs.

Many works studied the segregation of galaxies based on their properties using marked statistics. The luminosity and morphological segregation survey in the framework of marked point processes was discussed in [Beisbart and Kerscher \(2000\)](#). Various mark-weighted conditional correlation functions were introduced and discussed in this work. It has been observed that the luminosity correlations are scale-dependent, and the average luminosities of galaxy pairs are enhanced for pairs closer than $15 h^{-1}$ Mpc. [Beisbart et al. \(2002\)](#) applied the framework of marked point processes on the distribution and clustering of galaxies as well as craters on the surface of Mars, and pores in the sandstone!

The environmental dependence of halo formation was studied by [Sheth and Tormen \(2004\)](#), in which MCFs were shown to be suitable for studying environmental correlations. They presented evidence that halo formation is weakly correlated with the surrounding density field. In [Sheth et al. \(2005\)](#), measurements of marked statistics in semi-analytic galaxy formation models were done with luminosity, stellar mass, colour, and SFR as the marks. In the results, close pairs of galaxies were observed to be red, to have more stellar mass, and to have fewer SFR. [Sheth et al. \(2006\)](#) used an MCF analysis of SDSS galaxies using ages, metallicities, and star formation histories to show that close galaxy pairs tend to host stellar populations which are older than average.

The measurements of the redshift-space luminosity-weighted correlation function in SDSS were done by [Skibba et al. \(2006\)](#). They observed that the dense regions are populated by galaxies brighter in u , g , and r bands. [Skibba and Sheth \(2009\)](#) used the HOD approach to study the dependence of galaxy clustering on colour. The environmental dependence of the galaxy morphology and colour was studied by [Skibba et al. \(2009\)](#). They measured MCF using P_{sp} and P_{el} (the likelihoods of a galaxy being a spiral or an elliptical) as the marks. The work showed that overdense environments are dominated by early-type galaxies and spiral galaxies are mostly found in less dense regions. [Skibba et al. \(2012\)](#) used MCF to quantify the environmental dependence of the likelihood of bar and bulge as a function of the projected separation between galaxies. It was concluded that redder and massive disc galaxies are more likely to have bars than their blue, low-mass counterparts. It was also observed that barred and bulge-dominated disc galaxies tend to be found in denser environments than unbarred and disc-dominated galaxies.

[Gunawardhana et al. \(2018\)](#) used marked statistics to conclude that specific star formation rate (sSFR) is a better tracer of interactions between star-forming galaxies than colour. [Rutherford et al. \(2021\)](#) explored the environmental dependence of stellar mass and spin using MCFs. [Riggs et al. \(2021\)](#) explored the clustering of galaxy groups using MCF. Marked statistics have also been used to constrain modified gravity theories ([White, 2016](#); [Valogiannis and Bean, 2018](#); [Armijo et al., 2018](#); [Hernández-Aguayo et al., 2018](#); [Satpathy et al., 2019](#); [Alam et al., 2020](#)).

1.7 Format of this thesis

This thesis is divided into a total of eight chapters, including the Introduction (current chapter) and Conclusions (Chapter 8).

In Chapter 2, I provide a brief introduction to the three data sources used in this thesis- GAMA, SDSS, and cosmoDC2.

In Chapter 3, I provide a detailed explanation of the tools used in this thesis, i.e. 2pCF and MCF. In that chapter, I also provide a step-by-step procedure on how to compute these quantities using a trial set of galaxies from the GAMA public data.

In Chapter 4, I explain the work that my collaborators and I implemented using the optical and near-IR data from the GAMA survey. In that chapter, we compute the 2pCF and MCF on stellar-mass-selected samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ using absolute magnitudes in the u, g, r, J , and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR of galaxies as marks. The results shown in that chapter are published as [Sureshkumar et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#).

In Chapter 5, I show the results obtained when we extended the study using mid-IR properties of the GAMA galaxies. The mid-IR properties are taken from the *Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE)* survey. We explore the possibility of using the *WISE* bands to trace the environment. We used a set of $3.4 \mu\text{m}$ -selected galaxy samples from the GAMA-*WISE* catalogue in the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$. Using MCF, we checked how the *WISE* bands trace the galaxy clustering. We also compared how stellar masses and SFRs from three different estimates (GAMA, *WISE*, and ProSpect) trace the environment using MCFs. Additionally, using 2pCF we studied the luminosity dependence and redshift evolution of galaxy clustering. The results of this chapter are submitted to be published ([Sureshkumar et al., 2022](#)).

In Chapter 6, I explain the work in which we explore the effect of apparent flux limits on the correlation between small-scale clustering and galaxy properties. For this purpose, we impose various flux limits on the parent sample from the GAMA survey. Further, we compare the MCFs using different marks to see how these functions are affected by the change in flux limit. We also compare the measurements in our GAMA sample with those from the SDSS. The results are published in [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#).

In Chapter 7, we extend the analysis to the cosmoDC2 synthetic sky catalogue ([Korytov et al., 2019](#)) starting with a conventional analysis to demonstrate the stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering. Then we measure 2pCFs and MCF in various stellar-mass-limited samples from GAMA and cosmoDC2 and compare the results to see the effect of stellar mass incompleteness in cosmoDC2. A publication with the results of this chapter is in preparation.

Throughout the thesis, I adopt a flat Λ CDM cosmological model with $\Omega_{\text{M}} = 0.3$ and $\Omega_{\Lambda} = 0.7$. The Hubble constant is parameterized via $h = H_0/100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. All galaxy properties are measured using $h = 0.7$, unless otherwise specified. The distances are expressed in comoving coordinates and are in units of $h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$.

Chapter 2

Data

This thesis deals with the study of the environmental dependence of galaxy properties in two galaxy redshift surveys Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA; [Driver et al., 2009](#)) and Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; [York et al., 2000](#)) as well as one synthetic sky catalogue cosmoDC2 ([Korytov et al., 2019](#)). In this chapter, I give a brief overview about GAMA in Sect. 2.1, SDSS in Sect. 6.2.2, and cosmoDC2 in Sect. 2.3.

2.1 Galaxy and Mass Assembly

The GAMA survey is a multiwavelength and spectroscopic galaxy survey, carried out on the Anglo-Australian telescope that aims to test the Λ CDM model of structure formation and study galaxy evolution through the latest generation of ground-based and space-borne wide-field survey facilities ([Driver et al., 2009, 2011](#); [Liske et al., 2015](#)). It provides a comprehensive survey of galaxies by gathering data from eight ground-based surveys and four space missions. The GAMA covers three equatorial regions named G09, G12, and G15 and two southern regions G02 and G23 on the sky (see Table 2.1 for an overview). The spatial distribution of GAMA in comparison with a few other surveys is shown in Fig. 2.1. Detailed descriptions of various aspects of the GAMA survey are provided in [Driver et al. \(2009\)](#), [Robotham et al. \(2010\)](#), [Driver et al. \(2011\)](#), and [Liske et al. \(2015\)](#). For the most updated data release of GAMA (data release 4), see [Driver et al. \(2022\)](#).

TABLE 2.1: An overview of GAMA sky regions.

Region	RA range	Dec range	Flux limit
G02	30.2 - 38.8	-10.25 - -3.72	$r < 19.8$
G09	129.0 - 141.0	-2 - +3	$r < 19.8$
G12	174.0 - 186.0	-3 - +2	$r < 19.8$
G15	211.5 - 223.5	-2 - +3	$r < 19.8$
G23	339.0 - 351.0	-35 - -30	$i < 19.2$

FIGURE 2.1: Redshift cone plot and sky coverage of GAMA equatorial regions (white points) in comparison with other popular surveys in the field.

Image credit: [Driver et al. \(2009\)](#)

We exploit the main r -band limited data from GAMA II equatorial regions with targets drawn primarily from SDSS DR7 (Abazajian et al., 2009). For extinction-corrected r -band Petrosian magnitudes (Petrosian, 1976) limited at $r < 19.8$, GAMA provides high spatial completeness and an overall redshift completeness of 98.5% in the equatorial regions. This excellent completeness of GAMA is achieved by repeated surveying of the same field (Robotham et al., 2010). Moreover, the GAMA galaxies do not suffer from fibre collisions that affect close galaxy pairs (Robotham et al., 2010). It also provides reliable measurements of redshift, absolute magnitudes in a wide wavelength range, stellar masses, and SFR. The redshifts of GAMA objects are measured using the software AUTOZ, as described in Baldry et al. (2014), and are corrected for the local flow via the Tonry et al. (2000) model, tapered smoothly to the cosmic microwave background rest frame for $z \geq 0.03$. Liske et al. (2015) provide a detailed assessment of the quality and reliability of these redshifts. Due to these advantages, GAMA is an ideal survey for clustering measurements and environmental studies. The GAMA survey has been used for various aspects of environmental effects, in particular the impact of group, cluster, local, and large-scale environment on galaxy properties (Wijesinghe et al., 2012; Burton et al., 2013; Brough et al., 2013; McNaught-Roberts et al., 2014; Alpaslan et al., 2015; Davies et al., 2016; Schaefer et al., 2017; Grootes et al., 2017; Barsanti et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Davies et al., 2019a,b; Schaefer et al., 2019; Vázquez-Mata et al., 2020).

There have been many studies in GAMA using 2pCF in the past. Christodoulou et al. (2012) used CF as a tool to check the robustness of their photometric redshift estimates. The clustering properties of low-redshift ($z < 0.3$) submillimeter galaxies detected at 250 μm in the Herschel-ATLAS using the redshift information from GAMA was carried out by van Kampen et al. (2012). Large-scale clustering of radio galaxies in the Very Large Array FIRST survey over the GAMA survey area was studied by Lindsay et al. (2014). The dependence of projected galaxy clustering on various properties was studied by Farrow et al. (2015). Jarrett et al. (2017) analysed the spatial distribution of mid-IR *WISE* sources observed in the G12 equatorial region of GAMA. van Uitert et al. (2018) used angular CF of GAMA galaxies as one of the probes to constrain cosmological parameters. Loveday et al. (2018) used 2pCF to measure the pairwise velocity distribution in a set of luminosity-selected samples from GAMA.

Recently, Gunawardhana et al. (2018) used marked statistics on a set of luminosity- and stellar-mass-selected galaxy samples from GAMA with SFR, specific SFR (sSFR; defined as SFR per unit stellar mass), and $(g-r)_{\text{rest}}$ colour as marks. They observed that sSFR is a better tracer of interactions between star-forming galaxies than colour. The clustering measurements in GAMA were also used by Alam et al. (2021) to model the redshift space distortions. Riggs et al. (2021) used MCF to explore the clustering of galaxy groups in GAMA. In our work, we examine how galaxy clustering depends on various galaxy properties, such as luminosities in different passbands, stellar mass, and SFR using MCF.

Whenever we use GAMA data in this thesis, we first apply a series of common filters to the

GAMA Data Management Unit (DMU) TILINGCAT (Baldry et al., 2010). That is, we select galaxies from the GAMA II main survey (`SURVEY_CLASS` ≥ 4) in the equatorial regions. We only use secure redshifts with quality flag `nQ` ≥ 3 , which assures that the redshift has $> 90\%$ chance of being correct. In addition to this redshift quality cut, we only select objects with `VIS_CLASS` = 0, `VIS_CLASS` = 1, or `VIS_CLASS` = 255, so that we avoid sources that are visually classified to be deblends of star or parts of other galaxies (Baldry et al., 2010).

2.2 Sloan Digital Sky Survey

The SDSS is one of the advanced multi-filter imaging and spectroscopic redshift surveys (York et al., 2000). It produces both imaging and spectroscopic surveys covering more than a quarter of the sky. The project is funded by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, the U.S. Department of Energy, and various institutions. It uses a dedicated 2.5-meter telescope at Apache Point Observatory, New Mexico that is equipped with a large-format 120-megapixel camera imaging 1.5 square degrees of sky in five optical bands. It also has two digital spectrographs connected with optical fibres to obtain 600 galaxies and quasars in a single observation.

In this work, we use the SDSS LSS catalogue and the corresponding random catalogue¹ generated from SDSS III Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey (BOSS; Dawson et al., 2013) Data Release 12 (Alam et al., 2015, DR;). The SDSS BOSS DR12 catalogue encompasses massive galaxies partitioned into two non-overlapping redshift bins named as 'LOWZ' and 'CMASS' that cover galaxies in the redshift ranges $z < 0.43$ and $z > 0.43$, respectively. Reid et al. (2016) describe the methods used in the target selection of the SDSS galaxy data sets, and give details of the MKSAMPLE code used to create the LSS catalogue and random catalogue. The total sky coverage of the LOWZ DR12 sample is 8337.47 deg².

In this work, we make use of LOWZ galaxies in the North Galactic Cap in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$. The sky coverage of the North LOWZ catalogue is shown in Fig. 2.2. All the galaxies in the LSS catalogue are assigned the r -band apparent magnitude from `SPECPHOTOALL` table by matching the angular position within $2''$. Stellar masses are then assigned by cross-matching with the table `STELLARMASSSTARFORMINGPORT` using `specObjID`. The stellar masses are estimated from the best-fit Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) obtained from the stellar population model of Maraston et al. (2009). The fits are performed on the observed $ugriz$ -magnitudes of BOSS galaxies with the spectroscopic redshift determined using an adaptation of Hyper-Z code of Bolzonella et al. (2000). The magnitudes used are extinction-corrected model magnitudes that are scaled to the i -band `cmodel` magnitude.

¹<https://data.sdss.org/sas/dr12/boos/lss/>

FIGURE 2.2: Sky coverage of the SDSS LOWZ galaxies in the North Galactic Cap.

2.3 CosmoDC2 synthetic sky catalogue

CosmoDC2 (Korytov et al., 2019) is a large synthetic galaxy catalogue designed to support the upcoming Vera C. Rubin Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009, LSST;). It is the starting point for the second data challenge carried out by the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST DESC; LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration, 2012). The cosmoDC2 takes Outer Rim run (Heitmann et al., 2019) as its input. The Outer Rim run is a 4.225 Gpc^3 box gravity-only N-body simulation carried out using Hybrid/Hardware Accelerated Cosmology Code (HACC; Habib et al., 2016). It is generated using an approach that combines empirical methods with semi-analytic models using Galacticus code (Benson, 2012). Data from AlphaQ simulation and the UNIVERSEMACHINE (Behroozi et al., 2019) modelling approach are used for the construction of the catalogue.

The cosmoDC2 aims to improve analysis pipelines in advance of the arrival of LSST data. The catalogue contains about 2.26 billion galaxies spread over a sky region of 440 deg^2 in the redshift range $0 < z < 3$. The galaxies are also provided with many physical properties (see Appendix B of Korytov et al., 2019). The sky coverage of a small subset of cosmoDC2 galaxies is shown in Fig. 2.3.

FIGURE 2.3: Sky coverage of the cosmoDC2 galaxies in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.11$.

The cosmoDC2 catalogue is publicly available from the LSST DESC data portal and LSST DESC provides a Python package `GCRCatalogs` (Mao et al., 2018a) to facilitate user access to cosmoDC2. The `GCRCatalogs` can be setup² and used to access the cosmoDC2 catalogues³. We refer the reader to Korytov et al. (2019) for a detailed description of the catalogue.

²https://data.lsstdesc.org/doc/install_gcr

³<https://data.lsstdesc.org/doc/cosmodc2>

Chapter 3

Statistics of the large-scale structure

In this chapter, I explain the methodology that we use to compute the two-point correlation function (2pCF) and the marked correlation function (MCF). After formally defining the galaxy 2pCF in Sect. 3.1, we define a sample in Sect. 3.2 to demonstrate the computation of correlation function (CF). Its corresponding random catalogue is described in Sect. 3.3. In Sect. 3.4, we provide a step-by-step explanation on how to estimate the 2pCF. We discuss the effect of redshift-space distortion (RSD) and projected 2pCF in Sect. 3.5. Various methods to estimate the uncertainties associated with the 2pCF measurements are given in Sect. 3.6. Section 3.7 deals with the steps to estimate the power-law parameters of 2pCF. In Sect. 3.8, we demonstrate the dependence of galaxy clustering on galaxy properties. In Sect. 3.9, we define the MCF and its uncertainties. In Sect. 3.10, I briefly describe the C code that I developed for implementing the methodology described in this chapter.

I have written this chapter as a guide to the scientists who are new in this field. I dedicate this chapter to those young minds and I hope this chapter helps them to have a good start with the measurement of correlation functions.

3.1 The galaxy two-point correlation function

Let the galaxies be distributed in the Universe with an average number density \bar{n} . Consider two points in the space x and y with volume elements dV around them. The probability of finding a galaxy in the dV element around x is given by

$$P_1 = \bar{n} dV. \quad (3.1)$$

The same is the probability of finding a galaxy in the dV element around y . Taking into account that the distribution of galaxies is not random (as we discussed in Chapter 1), the joint probability of finding a galaxy in dV around x and finding a galaxy in dV around y is given by

$$P_2 = (\bar{n} dV)^2 [1 + \xi(r)] \quad (3.2)$$

where r is the distance between the points x and y . $\xi(r)$ is known as *two-point correlation function* (2pCF; Peebles, 1980).

If the distribution of the galaxies is random, then $\xi = 0$ and the probability in Eq. 3.2 becomes the product of the individual probabilities of finding a galaxy in dV around x and finding a galaxy in dV around y . In other words, 2pCF measures the excess probability of finding another galaxy at a distance r from a given galaxy, relative to a random distribution.

Already in early observations, the correlation function on the intermediate scales has been approximated by the power law (Groth and Peebles, 1977) given by

$$\xi(r) = \left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^{-\gamma}, \quad (3.3)$$

where the power-law fit parameters r_0 and γ are the correlation length and slope, respectively.

In the power-law approximation, these two parameters quantify the strength of the clustering of a sample. A higher value of r_0 signifies a larger amplitude of the correlation function, hence a stronger clustering of the sample, and a higher value of γ signifies a faster change in the strength of galaxy clustering at different scales.

The 2pCFs can also be modelled using halo occupation distribution models (HOD; Seljak, 2000; Zehavi et al., 2004; Zheng et al., 2005). The HOD models reveal more information about the parent dark matter haloes of the galaxies. It has been shown that galaxies occupying the same dark matter halo exhibit a different clustering behaviour from those in separate haloes and hence have to be quantified by different relations. The HOD framework divides the correlation function into two terms: the one-halo term which describes the galaxy clustering in the same dark matter halo and the two-halo term which describes the contribution from the galaxy pairs located in separate haloes. However, HOD modelling is beyond the scope of this thesis.

3.2 A data sample for demonstration

To better explain the idea of 2pCF and how it is estimated, we use a set of galaxies from the Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA; Driver et al., 2009) survey public release 3. A detailed description of the GAMA survey is given in Sect. 2.1. We use the GAMA Data Management Units (DMUs) TILINGCAT¹ (Baldry et al., 2010) and STELLARMASSSLAMBDAR² (Taylor et al., 2011). These DMUs can be matched using the GAMA unique identifier CATAID using a data management software (for e.g. TOPCAT; Taylor, 2005) so that the galaxies can be assigned properties such as absolute magnitudes in different passbands and stellar mass.

After matching, we filter GAMA II galaxies with well measured redshift by applying the following selections:

¹<http://www.gama-survey.org/dr3/schema/table.php?id=3>

²<http://www.gama-survey.org/dr3/schema/table.php?id=44>

- We select the galaxies of GAMA II main survey by filtering them using $\text{SURVEY_CLASS} \geq 4$.
- Then, we select only galaxies with secure redshifts with quality flag $nQ \geq 3$, which assures that the redshift measurement has $> 90\%$ chance of being correct.
- Then, we only select objects with $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 0$ or $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 1$ or $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 255$, so that we avoid sources that are visually classified to be deblends of star or parts of other galaxies (Baldry et al., 2010).
- We select only the G15 region ($211.5 < \text{RA} < 223.5$, $-2 < \text{Dec} < +3$).
- Finally, to select a volume-limited sample³ that is not affected by the Malmquist bias⁴ due to the flux limit of GAMA ($r_{\text{petro}} < 19.8$), we apply two cuts: one in redshift ($0.1 < z < 0.2$) and the other in r -band absolute magnitude ($-22.0 < M_r < -21.0$).

Throughout this chapter, we refer to the resulting sample as Sample \mathcal{O} . The sample \mathcal{O} contains 5805 galaxies. The $z - M_r$ distribution of sample \mathcal{O} is shown using the yellow lines in Fig. 3.1 and the sky coverage of sample \mathcal{O} is shown in the left panel of Fig. 3.2.

3.3 Random galaxy sample

A random sample is required for the computation of 2pCF of a given galaxy sample because 2pCF compares the observed distribution of galaxies with a random distribution. To have a meaningful comparison, it is essential that this random sample reflects the same sky distribution and redshift distribution of the real galaxy sample.

For the sample \mathcal{O} , we select a random sample from the RANDOMS DMU⁵ (Farrow et al., 2015) of the GAMA public data release. On a simple note, Farrow et al. (2015) use the method of Cole (2011) that generates clones of real galaxies, where the number of clones generated for a given galaxy is proportional to the ratio of the maximum volume out to which that galaxy is visible to the same volume weighted by the number density with redshift, as well as accounting for targeting and redshift incompleteness. The public version of the DMU covers the G15 region and provides the sky positions, redshift, r -band apparent and absolute magnitudes of random galaxies. The redshift distribution of the full random catalogue is shown as a red curve in the top panel of Fig. 3.1. We apply the same redshift and M_r cuts of the sample \mathcal{O} to the random catalogue and then randomly select the required number of random galaxies.

Typically, the number of random galaxies (N_r) should be significantly greater than the number of real galaxies (N_d) to avoid distortions in the 2pCF on smaller scales. For our purpose, we

³Volume-limited sample is limited by both redshift and the given property, so that the selected sample is complete within the spatial volume.

⁴The Malmquist bias is an effect in flux-limited surveys that leads to a preferential detection of luminous objects (Malmquist, 1922; Efron and Petrosian, 1992).

⁵<http://www.gama-survey.org/dr3/schema/table.php?id=106>

consider $N_r = 5 \times N_d = 29025$. A test on the influence of N_r on the correlation function measurements is given in Sect. 3.4.1.

3.4 How to estimate 2pCF?

In practice, due to the limitations of galaxy surveys, various estimators of $\xi(r)$ have been proposed to minimise the effects related to the limited number of objects and the limited survey area (e.g. Davis and Peebles, 1983; Hamilton, 1993; Landy and Szalay, 1993). A detailed description of the different estimators is given in Appendix. C. We choose the most commonly used Landy and Szalay (1993) estimator. It has been proven to reduce cosmic bias caused by edge effects due to the finite limit of the survey area, and is therefore often preferred over the other estimators (Bernardeau et al., 2002).

The Landy and Szalay (1993) estimator is defined by

$$\xi(r) = \frac{\langle DD(r) \rangle - 2\langle DR(r) \rangle + \langle RR(r) \rangle}{\langle RR(r) \rangle}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $DD(r)$ is the observed number of galaxy-galaxy pairs separated by r in the real galaxy sample, $RR(r)$ is the expected number of such pairs from the random sample, $DR(r)$ is the number of cross pairs of galaxies between the real and random samples, and $\langle \rangle$ refers to the quantity normalised by the total number of such pairs.

In the following, we explain the step-by-step procedure on how to compute 2pCF $\xi(r)$ using the real and random galaxies of the sample \mathcal{O} .

1. Define the minimum and maximum separation scales for the 2pCF. The minimum separation should ideally be decided by the separation of the closest pair in the sample, but it is also influenced by the number of random galaxies (see Sect. 3.4.1). In our case for $5 \times N_d$ number of random galaxies, the minimum scale that we could probe is $r = 0.15 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. The maximum separation can be determined using the survey sky coverage and the redshift limits of the sample (see Appendix. B.2). In our case, the sky coverage is 60 deg^2 and the minimum and maximum redshifts are 0.1 and 0.2 respectively and hence the maximum separation can be $\sim 100 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. However, considering the possible noises at the extreme bins, we restrict the measurements to $\sim 30 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$.
2. Define the r bins equally spaced in either log or linear scale. For the demonstration with sample \mathcal{O} , we choose 10 log-scaled bins with an equal width of $\Delta(\log r) = 0.25 \text{ dex}$.
3. Pair each real galaxy in the sample with all other real galaxies and calculate their separation as described in Appendix. B.1. Count the number of such pairs falling in each bin - that pair count defines the $DD(r)$. Repeat the procedure by pairing random-random galaxies (giving $RR(r)$) and real-random galaxies (giving $DR(r)$).

FIGURE 3.1: Redshift and r -band absolute magnitude distribution of galaxies in the entire G15 region of GAMA. Top histogram shows the corresponding redshift distribution. The yellow lines show the selected sample \mathcal{O} .

FIGURE 3.2: Sky coverage of the real and random galaxies of the sample \mathcal{O} . Here we show only $1 \times N_d$ number of random galaxies in the right panel for clarity.

4. All the pair counts thus obtained are to be normalised by the number of such pairs to account for the difference in the number of real and random galaxies:

$$\langle DD \rangle = \frac{DD}{\frac{1}{2}N_d(N_d - 1)}; \langle RR \rangle = \frac{RR}{\frac{1}{2}N_r(N_r - 1)}; \langle DR \rangle = \frac{DR}{N_d N_r}.$$

5. Use Eq. 3.4 to compute the *redshift-space correlation function* $\xi(r)$.

We show the $\xi(r)$ thus measured in the sample \mathcal{O} in Fig. 3.3. The pair counts DD , DR , and RR and the $\xi(r)$ values in each r bins are given in Table 3.1.

3.4.1 Correlation functions with different number of random galaxies

In this section, we demonstrate a test for the impact of the number of random galaxies on the 2pCF measurements. For the sample \mathcal{O} , we repeat the 2pCF measurements with different N_r/N_d values from 1 to 100. The result is shown in Fig. 3.4.

We observe a general agreement between 2pCFs with $N_r \geq 5 \times N_d$. However, for $N_r = 1 \times N_d$ and $N_r = 2 \times N_d$, the 2pCFs are affected at the smaller scale. For this reason, it is always important to consider as many random galaxies as possible. Although we see a slight difference between $N_r = 5 \times N_d$ and $N_r = 10 \times N_d$ at the smallest bin $r = 0.15 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$, we choose to continue with $N_r = 5 \times N_d$ as an optimal choice between accuracy and computational time. This is because the computation of RR is an $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ calculation where N is the number of galaxies in the random sample (Moore et al., 2001). That is, since we have to compute the separation

TABLE 3.1: The pair counts and the correlation function measurements for the sample \mathcal{O} .

r ($h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$)	DD	RR	DR	ξ
0.15	25	16	8	37.57
0.27	73	77	25	23.08
0.47	307	372	154	19.56
0.84	1039	2008	843	11.84
1.50	3242	11476	4570	6.07
2.67	10395	62444	25063	3.16
4.74	34227	334366	135101	1.54
8.44	118121	1723796	708852	0.66
15.00	416798	8195939	3366704	0.22
26.67	1425144	32649339	13082037	0.09
47.43	3503482	87829767	34393689	0.04

FIGURE 3.3: Redshift space correlation function $\xi(r)$ of the sample \mathcal{O} . The vertical grey lines mark the edges of bins in r .

FIGURE 3.4: Redshift space correlation function $\xi(r)$ of the sample \mathcal{O} with different number of random galaxies.

between all galaxies in the sample, the computation time increases by an order of magnitude proportional to N^2 .

3.5 Redshift-space distortions and projected two-point correlation function

We use the redshift to estimate the line-of-sight comoving distance of a galaxy (see Appendix B.1). Using redshift as an indicator of distance is based on the assumption that the redshift is purely cosmological, i.e. occurring due to the expansion of the Universe. However, galaxies in cluster environments possess random motions (*peculiar motions*), in addition to the expansion of the space, due to the local gravitational field. Hence, the positions of the galaxies in the *redshift space* (where the observed redshift is used as a proxy for distance) differ from that in the *real space* (where the physical distance is considered). This effect, known as *Redshift-space distortion* (RSD), influences the spatial distribution of galaxies if their positions are plotted in the redshift space.

Imagine that we are observing a spherical galaxy cluster (see Fig. 3.5). All the galaxies in the cluster are moving away from us with nearly the same Hubble expansion velocity. At the same time, individual galaxies carry peculiar velocities. The galaxies that are far away from the centre of the cluster have peculiar velocities that are directed towards the centre of the cluster; however, their peculiar velocities are not large enough to compensate for the velocity of Hubble expansion. Therefore, the observed redshift of the galaxies being on the farther side of the cluster (opposite side of centre to us) reduces and that on the nearer side enhances. This makes the shell appear squashed along the line-of-sight in the redshift space. This is called *Kaiser effect* (Kaiser, 1987).

At the same time, in the overdense regions of the cluster (near to the centre), the galaxies carry stronger random peculiar velocities that can overrule the expansion velocity. So, the galaxies on the nearer side of the cluster possess a net velocity greater than the Hubble velocity. This makes the galaxies on the nearer side appear to be on the farther side. Similarly, the galaxies on the farther side possess a net velocity smaller than the Hubble velocity and hence appear to be on the nearer side. The shell then appears elongated along the line-of-sight in redshift space. This is referred to as the *fingers of god effect* (Jackson, 1972; Kaiser, 1987; Scoccimarro, 2004; Mo et al., 2010).

As the RSD significantly alters the observed distribution of galaxies, the effect propagates to the redshift space correlation functions. This problem can be solved by dividing the redshift-space separation (s) into two components - parallel (π) and perpendicular (r_p) to the line-of-sight (see Fig. 3.6). That is, consider two galaxies separated by a comoving real-space separation r with redshift-space positions \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 . We can define the redshift separation vector $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_2$ and the line-of-sight vector $\mathbf{l} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2)$. We can then define π and r_p as

FIGURE 3.5: Schematic diagram showing the RSD. The blue circles represent galaxies that are far away from the cluster centre (yellow star) and red ones represent the galaxies that are close to the centre. The blue and red dashed ellipses show how a real spherical distribution of galaxies observed in real space (blue solid circle) changes when observed in the redshift space - the red one showing fingers of god effect and the blue one showing Kaiser effect.

FIGURE 3.6: Schematic representation of the decomposition of separation s into r_p and π .

$$\pi = \frac{\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{l}}{|\mathbf{l}|}$$

$$r_p = \sqrt{\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{s} - \pi^2}$$

Then the 2pCF can be computed in the form of a two-dimensional grid $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ using the [Landy and Szalay \(1993\)](#) estimator defined by

$$\xi(r_p, \pi) = \frac{\langle DD(r_p, \pi) \rangle - 2\langle DR(r_p, \pi) \rangle + \langle RR(r_p, \pi) \rangle}{\langle RR(r_p, \pi) \rangle}, \quad (3.5)$$

The $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ contours are shown in Fig. 3.7 in which the dashed contours represent the expected $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ in the absence of RSD. We clearly see anisotropy in the correlation functions in Fig. 3.7.

To account for the distortions in 2pCF measurements caused by the RSD, the two-dimensional correlation function $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ can be integrated over the line-of-sight which essentially smoothens the distortions (which are only along the line-of-sight). This integration gives us the projected 2pCF, $\omega_p(r_p)$, which can be used to recover the real space 2pCF devoid of RSD ([Davis and Peebles, 1983](#)). It is defined as

$$\omega_p(r_p) = 2 \int_0^{\pi_{\max}} \xi(r_p, \pi) d\pi. \quad (3.6)$$

The limit of integration π_{\max} has to be reasonable enough to include all correlated pairs and reduce the noise in the estimator. The test for the best π_{\max} is given in Sect. 3.7.2.

FIGURE 3.7: Two-dimensional correlation function $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ of the sample \mathcal{O} .

3.6 Uncertainties in the correlation function

Correct estimation of errors in ξ is a difficult but important task. There are various methods for estimating uncertainties in 2pCF measurements (see [Norberg et al., 2009](#)). Let us consider a data sample for which we are interested in an error of some quantity. In general, the error of that quantity is estimated from the variance of a collection of independent samples which are equivalent to our sample. But in the case of 2pCF, our sample is a realisation of the underlying galaxy distribution, and it is not practical (and frequently impossible) to have independent realisations that are equivalent to our galaxy sample. Therefore, we have to rely on internal error estimates where we generate such independent realisations by perturbing the parent sample in various ways. In this section, we explain the two most common approaches: bootstrap ([Efron, 1979](#)) and jackknife ([Tukey, 1958](#)) methods.

Additionally, we describe the covariance matrix associated with both methods. Since the galaxies are clustered and the pair counts in different separation bins can include the same galaxies, the bins are correlated. Therefore, the errors associated with clustering measurements are estimated using the covariance matrix obtained from various methods of error estimation. The square root of the diagonal elements of the covariance matrix gives the error for the 2pCF in the corresponding bin.

FIGURE 3.8: Bootstrap copies: the top left panel shows the real sample \mathcal{O} and the rest of the panels show five bootstrap copies of the sample \mathcal{O} .

3.6.1 Bootstrap method of error estimation

In the bootstrap method, we first divide the parent sample into N_{sub} subsamples of equal area. Then a copy of the parent sample is generated by selecting N_{sub} subsamples at random with replacement (Efron, 1979). This copy is referred to as a bootstrap copy. Therefore, a few of the subsamples will not be present and a few will be repeated in the bootstrap copy. Similarly N_{bs} bootstrap copies of the parent sample can be generated and $\xi(r)$ or $\omega_p(r_p)$ can be measured in each bootstrap copy. In Fig. 3.8, we present five such bootstrap copies of the sample \mathcal{O} . Please note that the random sample of each bootstrap copy used to measure the CF should follow exactly the same selection.

The bootstrap copies can also be generated by randomly selecting individual galaxies rather than subsamples. However, this method can underestimate the errors in voids and overestimate in clusters (Fisher et al., 1994; Mo et al., 1992).

The covariance matrix associated with the bootstrap method is given by

$$C_{ij} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{bs}} - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{bs}}} (\xi_i^k - \bar{\xi}_i) (\xi_j^k - \bar{\xi}_j), \quad (3.7)$$

where ξ_j^k represents the measurement of ξ at $r = r_j$ in the k th bootstrap copy and $\bar{\xi}$ is the average from N_{bs} copies.

FIGURE 3.9: Jackknife copies: the top left panel shows the real sample \mathcal{O} and the rest of the nine panels show the jackknife copies with different areas excluded from the sample.

3.6.2 Jackknife method of error estimation

In the jackknife method (Quenouille, 1956; Tukey, 1958; Shao, 1995), we divide the parent sample into N_{jk} equal subsamples. An easy method to do that is to divide the sky region into subsamples of equal area. Once the sample is divided, a copy of the parent sample can be created by omitting one of the N_{jk} subsamples. This copy is referred to as a jackknife copy. Similarly N_{jk} such unique jackknife copies of the main sample can be created and $\xi(r)$ or $\omega_p(r_p)$ can be measured in each jackknife copy. In Fig. 3.9, we show the nine jackknife samples of sample \mathcal{O} . It is important that the same selection is also applied to the random sample used to CF measurement.

Then the covariance matrix associated with the jackknife method is given by

$$C_{ij} = \frac{N_{\text{jk}} - 1}{N_{\text{jk}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{jk}}} (\xi_i^k - \bar{\xi}_i) (\xi_j^k - \bar{\xi}_j), \quad (3.8)$$

where ξ_j^k represents the measurement of ξ at $r = r_j$ in the k th jackknife copy and $\bar{\xi}$ is the average from N_{jk} copies.

The number of jackknife copies can influence the error estimates. Norberg et al. (2009) observed that the error estimates are insensitive to the N_{jk} on scales greater than $1 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$, while on smaller scales, higher number of jackknife copies overestimates the errors. At the same time, a smaller number of jackknife copies can make the covariance matrix noisy.

3.7 Estimation of power-law parameters

As described in Sect. 3.1, power-law parameters of the 2pCF signify the strength of the galaxy clustering. In the absence of RSD, the power-law parameters can be estimated using the $\xi(r)$ measurements and the full covariance matrix estimated using one of the methods described in

Sect. 3.6 (Fisher et al., 1994; Pollo et al., 2005). Then we minimise the χ^2 defined by

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i,j} (\xi^{\text{mod}}(r_i) - \xi(r_i)) C_{ij}^{-1} (\xi^{\text{mod}}(r_j) - \xi(r_j)), \quad (3.9)$$

where C_{ij}^{-1} is the inverse of the covariance matrix, $\xi(r_i)$ is the measured value of real space 2pCF at $r = r_i$ and ξ^{mod} is the power-law model value given by Eq. 3.3.

To estimate the power-law parameters r_0 and γ , we compute ξ^{mod} for a range of r_0 and γ , i.e. in a grid of (r_0, γ) with intervals of $\Delta r_0 = 0.01$, $\Delta \gamma = 0.01$ and then substitute to Eq. 3.9, and choose the (r_0, γ) that gives the minimum χ^2 value. The 1σ confidence region for the r_0 and γ parameters is defined by an error contour that corresponds to $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.3$. We refer the reader to Chapter 15.6 of Press et al. (1992) for more details.

3.7.1 Projected 2pCF (demonstration with sample \mathcal{O}):

The projected 2pCF $\omega_p(r_p)$ is related to the real space 2pCF parameters (Davis and Peebles, 1983). For the power-law form of $\xi(r)$, the analytical relation is given by

$$\omega_p(r_p) = r_p \left(\frac{r_p}{r_0} \right)^{-\gamma} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}) \Gamma(\frac{\gamma-1}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\gamma}{2})}, \quad (3.10)$$

there $\Gamma(n)$ is Euler's Gamma function.

From Fig. 3.7, it is clear that the redshift-space 2pCF estimated in the sample \mathcal{O} is affected by the RSD. Therefore, we have to compute the projected 2pCF and recover the real-space 2pCF parameters. The methodology to recover the real-space 2pCF parameters is a bit different in the case of projected 2pCFs. The step-by-step procedure is given below.

1. Estimate the two-dimensional 2pCF $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ from the parent sample \mathcal{O} and its jackknife copies using, e.g., the Landy-Szalay estimator (Eq. 3.5). We set $r_p^{\text{init}} = 0.15 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ and chose 10 logarithmic scaled r_p bins with an equal width of 0.25 dex. In the case of π , we set the initial bin at $0.5 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ and considered equally spaced linear bins with a width of $1.0 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$.
2. Integrate $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ using Eq. 3.6 to get $\omega_p(r_p)$. Following Appendix B of Loveday et al. (2018) and our own test given in Sect. 3.7.2, we choose the value of π_{max} to be $40 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$.
3. Estimate the covariance matrix as explained in Sect. 3.6.2 using

$$C_{ij} = \frac{N_{\text{jk}} - 1}{N_{\text{jk}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{jk}}} (\omega_p^k(r_i) - \bar{\omega}_p(r_i)) (\omega_p^k(r_j) - \bar{\omega}_p(r_j)), \quad (3.11)$$

FIGURE 3.10: Correlation matrix of the sample \mathcal{O} .

where $\omega_p^k(r_j)$ represents the measurement of ω_p at $r_p = r_j$ in the k th jackknife copy and $\bar{\omega}_p$ is the average from N_{jk} copies.

The correlation matrix \tilde{C}_{ij} (normalised covariance matrix) is more useful to see the strength of the correlation between bins. It is given by

$$\tilde{C}_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sigma_i \sigma_j}, \quad (3.12)$$

where $\sigma_i = \sqrt{C_{ii}}$, the error bar associated with the ω_p measurement at the i th bin. The correlation matrix thus obtained for the sample \mathcal{O} is shown in Fig. 3.10.

4. Compute the χ^2 value using the equation

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i,j} (\omega_p^{\text{mod}}(r_i) - \omega_p(r_i)) C_{ij}^{-1} (\omega_p^{\text{mod}}(r_j) - \omega_p(r_j)), \quad (3.13)$$

where ω_p^{mod} is the model value given by Eq. 3.10. This χ^2 can be minimised to estimate the best-fitting power-law parameters of the real-space 2pCF.

However, we can see in Fig. 3.10 that the correlation matrix is noisy. That means that we have strong off-diagonal elements. This noise is introduced by the limited number of jackknife copies that we used which can lead to unreliable power-law fit parameters. As

described in Sect. 3.6.2, we cannot solve this problem by increasing the number of jackknife copies as it leads to the overestimation of errors. Hence, we adopt the fitting procedure previously performed on the GAMA data by [Farrow et al. \(2015\)](#).

In this procedure, the correlation matrix \mathbf{C} is transformed into a matrix \mathbf{D} using singular value decomposition (SVD) given by $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{U}$. The diagonal matrix \mathbf{D} has $\Lambda_{ij}^2 \delta_{ij}$ as elements, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. The columns of the matrix \mathbf{U} are the eigenmodes of the correlation matrix, where $\Lambda_{ij}^2 \delta_{ij}$ are their corresponding eigenvalues. The inverse of the diagonal matrix \mathbf{D} is given by $D_{ij}^{-1} = (1/\Lambda_{ij}^2) \delta_{ij}$. Then we transform the correlation matrix back using $\mathbf{C}^{-1} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D}^{-1} \mathbf{U}^T$ and while doing this calculation, we set $D_{ii}^{-1} = 0$ for eigenvalues $\Lambda_{ii}^2 < \sqrt{2/N_{\text{jk}}}$ ([Gaztañaga and Scoccimarro, 2005](#)). This effectively removes the influence of least significant eigenmodes that are more likely to suffer from noise.

The transformed inverse of the correlation matrix is then used to minimise χ^2 that is defined as

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i,j} \frac{(\omega_p^{\text{mod}}(r_i) - \omega_p(r_i))}{\sigma_i} \tilde{C}_{ij}^{-1} \frac{(\omega_p^{\text{mod}}(r_j) - \omega_p(r_j))}{\sigma_j}, \quad (3.14)$$

where $\omega_p(r_i)$ is the measured value of 2pCF at $r_p = r_i$, ω_p^{mod} is the power-law model value given by Eq. 3.10, and $\sigma_i = \sqrt{C_{ii}}$. The power-law parameters can be estimated by minimising the χ^2 in Eq. 3.14. [Gaztañaga and Scoccimarro \(2005\)](#) and [Marín et al. \(2013\)](#) provide detailed descriptions of the fitting procedure using SVD to estimate the power-law parameters.

From these procedures applied in the sample \mathcal{O} , we obtained the best-fitting power-law parameters as $r_0 = 5.82 \pm 1.11 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ and $\gamma = 1.78 \pm 0.13$. The correlation function and the associated error contours are shown in Fig. 3.11.

3.7.2 Test for the limit of integration π_{max}

In this section, we demonstrate the test to choose the best π_{max} that is used to compute the projected 2pCF (Eq. 3.6). In Fig. 3.12, we show the projected 2pCFs of the sample \mathcal{O} computed with different values of π_{max} from 10 to 200 $h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$. The inset panels show the corresponding r_0 and γ values with 1σ uncertainty.

We observe that the r_0 and γ values converge from 40 $h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ onwards. However, for $\pi_{\text{max}} > 40 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$, the uncertainties also increase. So we choose $\pi_{\text{max}} = 40 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ to be the best choice for this sample.

FIGURE 3.11: *Left:* The projected 2pCF of the sample \mathcal{O} . The solid line represents the ω_p values obtained from substituting the best-fitting power-law parameters in Eq. 3.10. *Right:* The 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours associated with the power-law parameters.

3.8 Dependence of clustering on galaxy properties

In this section, we explain how the 2pCF can be used to study the dependence of clustering on galaxy properties such as absolute magnitudes in different bands and stellar mass. For each galaxy in the sample \mathcal{O} , we assign the galaxy properties from the `STELLARMASSSLAMBDA` (Taylor et al., 2011) DMU (see Sect. 3.2). The properties and their corresponding columns in the DMU are:

1. absolute magnitude in u band (M_u): `absmag_u`,
2. absolute magnitude in g band (M_g): `absmag_g`,
3. absolute magnitude in r band (M_r): `absmag_r`,
4. absolute magnitude in J band (M_J): `absmag_J`,
5. absolute magnitude in K band (M_K): `absmag_K`, and
6. logarithm of stellar mass in units of solar mass ($\log(M_*/M_\odot)$): `logmstar`.

The summary statistics of these properties such as the minimum, maximum, mean, median, and the standard deviation are given in Table 3.2. For each property, we divide the sample \mathcal{O} into two subsamples based on its mean value. Those subsamples containing galaxies which are brighter (with lower absolute magnitude values) or massive are referred to as 'higher', and their

FIGURE 3.12: Projected 2pCFs of the sample \mathcal{O} computed with different values of π_{\max} . The red marker and line represents the best choice, i.e. $\pi_{\max} = 40 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$.

TABLE 3.2: Summary statistics of the properties of galaxies in the sample \mathcal{O} ($N_{\text{gal}}^{\text{total}} = 5805$).

Property	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Standard deviation	$N_{\text{gal}}^{\text{lower}}$	$N_{\text{gal}}^{\text{higher}}$
M_u	-21.34	-18.24	-19.47	-19.46	0.44	2944	2861
M_g	-21.75	-19.95	-20.79	-20.77	0.30	2999	2806
M_r	-22.00	-21.00	-21.43	-21.40	0.28	3090	2715
M_J	-23.40	-21.28	-22.32	-22.31	0.34	2972	2833
M_K	-23.78	-20.96	-22.35	-22.35	0.39	2918	2887
$\log(M_*/M_\odot)$	9.60	11.12	10.59	10.62	0.22	2612	3193

FIGURE 3.13: Dependence of 2pCFs on galaxy properties when the parent sample is split based on mean of the properties.

complementary subsamples are referred to as 'lower'. The number of galaxies in each subsample is given in the 7th and 8th columns of the Table 3.2.

We compute the projected 2pCF for all these 10 subsamples and estimate their power-law parameters. The results are shown in Fig. 3.13. We can clearly see that the 2pCF varies between brighter/massive galaxies and fainter/less massive galaxies. However, the dependence of 2pCF on the properties varies for different properties.

We repeat the same experiment by dividing the sample \mathcal{O} based on the median values so that the higher and lower subsamples are equally populated. The results are presented in Fig. 3.14.

In the case of stellar mass, we observe that the massive subsample exhibits a higher amplitude for the 2pCF and hence shows a higher r_0 value. This means that massive galaxies exhibit stronger clustering, that is, the massive galaxies tend to exist in the denser regions of the Universe. The same observation applies to the absolute magnitude in the J and K bands. However, the difference between 2pCFs is reduced in the r and g bands. In the case of the u -band, the trend switches and the fainter subsample gives a higher amplitude for 2pCF than the brighter subsample. These observations remain the same regardless of whether the mean or median is used to divide the parent sample. This agrees with the well-known observation that the most massive and luminous galaxies (in the r , J , and K bands) are mostly found in dense regions of the LSS (Norberg et al., 2002; Coil et al., 2006; Pollo et al., 2006; Meneux et al., 2009; Bolzonella et al., 2010; Abbas and Sheth, 2006; Abbas et al., 2010; Zehavi et al., 2011; Marulli et al., 2013; Farrow et al., 2015; Durkalec et al., 2018; Cochrane et al., 2018). It was also observed that the UV-selected galaxies exhibit low clustering in the local Universe (Heinis et al., 2004, 2007; Milliard et al., 2007).

All these observations show that the galaxy properties are correlated with the environment in which the galaxies live and such correlations vary for different properties. These environmental dependences of galaxy properties can be additionally studied using marked correlation functions (MCFs) which we explain in the upcoming sections.

3.9 Marked correlation function

In the previous sections, we described the galaxy 2pCF and how it can be used to quantify the distribution of galaxies in the large-scale structure. In general, the 2pCF could be used to understand how galaxy properties correlate with the environment in which the galaxies live. However, as we show in Sect. 3.8, such studies are usually done by dividing the parent sample into different subsamples based on the property of interest. Then the 2pCF is computed in the subsamples by treating all the galaxies equally. In other words, 2pCF does not weight the galaxies. However, there are a few problems associated with this methodology:

- The value of the property that is used to split the parent sample is arbitrary.

FIGURE 3.14: Dependence of 2pCFs on galaxy properties when the parent sample is split based on median of the properties.

- Once the splitting is done, we are left with lesser number of galaxies in each subsample and hence it can influence the 2pCF measurements.

These problems can be overcome by using MCFs. The MCF is defined for a particular property (referred to as *mark*) and is a function of the spatial separation between galaxies, just like 2pCF. However, the galaxies are weighted using the corresponding property to compute the MCF. The MCF allows us to study the galaxy clustering by taking the properties of each galaxy in the sample into account. These properties can be continuous values such as luminosity, colour, stellar mass, and SFR or discrete values like morphological type.

In the following, we present a quantitative description of the MCF. We refer the reader to [Beisbart and Kerscher \(2000\)](#) for a detailed explanation.

Consider a sample of N galaxies $X = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ given by the spatial coordinates $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and number density \bar{n} . All galaxies carry a physical property which we use to assign a mark m_i to each point x_i . Hence we obtain a marked sample of galaxies $X^M = \{(x_i, m_i)\}_{i=1}^N$.

Let us recall the definition of $\xi(r)$ from Sect. 3.1. Eq. 3.2 gives the joint probability of finding a galaxy in dV around x_1 and finding galaxy in dV around x_2 . This probability deals with the correlation between positions of the galaxies (spatial correlation) only, and hence can be rewritten as

$$P_2^S(x_1, x_2) = (\bar{n} dV)^2 [1 + \xi(r)] \quad (3.15)$$

where $r = |x_1 - x_2|$.

We define the joint probability of finding a galaxy in dV around x_1 with mark m_1 and finding a galaxy in dV around x_2 with mark m_2 as

$$P_2^{SM}[(x_1, m_1), (x_2, m_2)] = (\bar{n} dV)^2 [1 + W(r)] \quad (3.16)$$

where $W(r)$ is the two-point weighted correlation function obtained using m_1 and m_2 as weights.

The conditional probability of finding the marks m_1 and m_2 at two galaxies located in dV around x_1 and x_2 , under the condition that galaxies at x_1 and x_2 are present in the sample is given by

$$M(m_1, m_2|r) = \frac{P_2^{SM}[(x_1, m_1), (x_2, m_2)]}{P_2^S(x_1, x_2)} = \frac{1 + W(r)}{1 + \xi(r)} \quad (3.17)$$

The $M(m_1, m_2|r)$ or simply $M(r)$ is referred to as the two-point marked correlation function. $M(r) = 1$ means $W(r) = \xi(r)$ and that the marks of the galaxies are not correlated with their spatial distribution. In other words, $M(r) = 1$ implies a lack of correlation between the marks or the property and the environment. $M(r) > 1$ implies a positive environmental correlation and $M(r) < 1$ implies an anti-correlation. That is, for a given property, $M(r) > 1$ signifies a higher probability of finding galaxy pairs separated by r in which both galaxies are stronger in

that property. Similarly, $M(r) < 1$ signifies a lower probability. The deviation of the MCF from unity signifies the strength of the environmental dependence.

3.9.1 How to compute the marked correlation function?

To compute the MCF for a given property, we first define the marks for each galaxy in the real sample. A mark is a function of the value of the property— either be the property itself or its rank in the sample (see Sect. 3.9.3 for more details). Using the mark, we assign a weight to each real galaxy which is the mark of the galaxy expressed as mean mark of all galaxies in the sample. That is, if m_i is the mark of the i th galaxy in a sample with the mean mark \bar{m} , then the weight of the galaxy is given by $w_i = m_i/\bar{m}$.

Then we estimate the weighted correlation function $W(r)$ defined by the [Landy and Szalay \(1993\)](#) estimator as

$$W(r) = \frac{\langle WW(r) \rangle - 2\langle WR(r) \rangle + \langle RR(r) \rangle}{\langle RR(r) \rangle}. \quad (3.18)$$

where $WW(r)$ is the weighted number of real-real galaxy pairs, $RR(r)$ is the number of random-random galaxy pairs, $WR(r)$ is the number of cross pairs of galaxies between the real and random samples with only the real galaxy carrying the weight, and $\langle \rangle$ refers to the quantity normalised by the total number of such pairs.

The steps to compute $W(r)$ remain the same as those of $\xi(r)$ (as explained in Sect. 3.4) except that $WW(r)$ and $WR(r)$ are the weighted pair counts, that is,

$$WW(r) = \sum_{ij} w_i \times w_j, \quad (3.19)$$

It should be noted that $\xi(r)$ is the same as $W(r)$ but with all galaxies carrying unit weight (all galaxies being treated equally).

To account for the RSD (see Sect. 3.5), we compute the two-dimensional weighted correlation function given by

$$W(r_p, \pi) = \frac{\langle WW(r_p, \pi) \rangle - 2\langle WR(r_p, \pi) \rangle + \langle RR(r_p, \pi) \rangle}{\langle RR(r_p, \pi) \rangle} \quad (3.20)$$

and then integrate it along π to give projected weighted correlation function,

$$W_p(r_p) = 2 \int_0^{\pi_{\max}} W(r_p, \pi) d\pi. \quad (3.21)$$

Then we define the projected MCF as

$$M_p(r_p) = \frac{1 + W_p(r_p)/r_p}{1 + \omega_p(r_p)/r_p}. \quad (3.22)$$

In Eq. 3.22, the W_p and ω_p are divided by r_p because they both have a dimension of length and M_p is dimensionless.

3.9.2 Marked correlation function in sample \mathcal{O}

In this section, we present the MCF measurements in the sample \mathcal{O} using marks defined by six different galaxy properties: luminosities in the u, g, r, J, K bands and stellar mass. We consider the same properties as given in Sect. 3.8. As explained in Sect. 3.9.1, first we assign marks to the galaxies in the sample \mathcal{O} . For the time being, let us use the value of the property directly so that for a given property, each galaxy carries a weight equal to the ratio of the property to the mean property of the sample.

Using the weights, we compute $W_p(r_p)$ using Eq. 3.20 and Eq. 3.21. The $\omega_p(r_p)$ is computed using Eq. 3.5 and Eq. 3.6. Then we use Eq. 3.22 to compute $M_p(r_p)$. The MCFs measured using six different properties as marks are shown in Fig. 3.15.

We observe that all MCFs deviate from unity on smaller scales and approach unity on larger scales ($r_p > 10 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$). This shows the small-scale environmental dependence of these properties. Also, it should be noted that different MCFs deviate from unity in different manner. The u -band and g -band MCFs take values below unity on smaller scales, whereas the r -band, J -band, K -band and stellar mass MCFs take values above unity. This means that u -band and g -band luminosities are anti-correlated with the environment, that is, there is less probability of finding pairs of galaxies that are both brighter in u and g bands in denser environment. However, the case is opposite for r -band, J -band, and K -band – galaxies that are brighter in these bands are more probable to be found in denser environment. In other words, galaxies that are brighter in the r, J, K bands and massive are strongly clustered than their fainter/less massive counterparts and vice versa for the u and g bands. This is exactly what we observed in Fig. 3.13 (see Sect. 3.8 for a discussion on this). Using MCF, we could reach the same qualitative conclusion without splitting the parent sample.

3.9.3 Rank-ordered marked correlation function

As explained earlier in this section, the amplitude of the MCF measured using a property as a mark signifies the strength of the correlation between that property and the environment. Therefore, MCFs can be a useful tool to compare the environmental dependence of different properties. However, using the value of the property directly as the mark is not ideal, especially when a comparison between different MCFs is required. The reasons are as follows:

- *Range*: In Table 3.2, we present the range of properties of galaxies in the sample \mathcal{O} . Since different properties have different ranges, the weights we use are not uniform if the value of the mark is used directly. This can lead to unreliable comparisons between MCFs measured using different properties.

FIGURE 3.15: The MCFs measured using luminosities in u, g, r, J, K bands and linear stellar mass directly as mark.

- *Convention*: The absolute brightness of a galaxy can be expressed as either luminosity or absolute magnitude. While a galaxy with a higher value of luminosity is brighter, one with a higher value of absolute magnitude is fainter. This difference in convention can create discrepancies in MCF for the same galaxies when the value is used directly as mark.
- *Scale*: Absolute magnitude and luminosity have a dimensionally logarithmic relation. Similarly in some catalogues, stellar masses are given in the logarithmic scale. Although we use the ratio of the mark to the mean mark as the weight, the marks and their mean in a sample can vary between linear and logarithmic scales. Hence, the scale in which a property is represented influences the MCF.

These problems can be solved if the galaxies carry weight corresponding to their rank in the sample (Skibba et al., 2013). For a given property, we assign ranks to galaxies based on the strength of the property and use these ranks as the marks. For example, in case of stellar mass for a sample of N galaxies, we rank the galaxies so that the most massive galaxy in the sample carries a rank N and the least massive one carries a rank 1. Then this rank is considered as the mark and its ratio with the mean mark is used as the weight to compute the MCF. Each galaxy carries different weights for different properties, but all of the weights are in the range of $(0, 2)$. This makes the MCFs computed using different properties comparable, thereby allowing us to understand how the strength of environmental dependence varies for different properties. The MCF measured using the ranks is called the *rank-ordered MCF*.

In Fig. 3.16, we demonstrate the advantage of rank-ordered MCFs. The environmental dependence of galaxy properties should remain the same even if their stellar mass is expressed in linear scale or log scale, or their brightness is expressed as luminosity or absolute magnitude. We can clearly see that the unranked MCFs changes between the r -band luminosity and the absolute magnitude and between linear and log-scaled stellar mass. However, the rank-ordered MCFs remain the same. The property that is more dependent on environment is the one having a larger rank-ordered MCF. As the main aim of this thesis is to have a comparison between the environmental dependence of various properties, all the MCFs presented are rank-ordered, unless otherwise specified.

The 2pCFs (unweighted and weighted using different properties) and their corresponding rank-ordered MCFs in sample \mathcal{O} are presented in Fig. 3.17.

3.9.4 Uncertainties in MCF

In Sect. 3.6, we explain how uncertainties are estimated for 2pCF and its power-law model parameters. In this section, we deal with the uncertainties of MCFs. There are two major uncertainties in the case of MCFs due to the role of both spatial positions and marks of the galaxies. The one from the spatial distribution of galaxies can be estimated using internal error estimation methods such as the jackknife method (Sect. 3.6.2). The other deal with the correlation between marks

FIGURE 3.16: Ranked and unranked MCFs measured using r -band absolute magnitude, r -band luminosity, stellar mass, and log of stellar mass.

FIGURE 3.17: *Left:* Unweighted correlation function and weighted correlation functions in Sample \mathcal{O} with absolute magnitudes in u , g , r , J , and K bands and stellar mass as marks. *Right:* Marked correlation functions with the same properties as marks.

and positions. Its significance can be estimated from the variance over redistribution of the marks randomly among the galaxies. That is, we randomly shuffle the marks among the galaxies in the sample and then remeasure the MCF. The standard deviation over a number of MCF measurements with such shuffled marks (~ 100 times) gives the uncertainty in the MCF (Beisbart and Kerscher, 2000; Skibba et al., 2006).

As both of these errors are important, we present a combined error calculated using

$$\sigma_{\text{combined}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\sigma_{\text{JK}}^2} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{\text{shuffle}}^2}}} \quad (3.23)$$

where σ_{JK} and σ_{shuffle} are the standard deviations obtained using the jackknife method and the random shuffling method, respectively.

The MCFs measured in the sample \mathcal{O} using absolute magnitudes in u , g , r , J , K bands and stellar mass as marks are shown in Fig. 3.18. The error bars on the markers represent the uncertainty obtained from the jackknife method. The shaded regions correspond to the uncertainty obtained from the random shuffling method. In the bottom panel, we show the combined error calculated using Eq. 3.23. A detailed discussion on the comparison between MCFs measured using different properties is given in the following chapters.

FIGURE 3.18: Rank-ordered MCFs measured using the properties as marks (as labelled). The errorbars on markers represent the uncertainty obtained from 9 jackknife regions. The shaded regions correspond to the uncertainty obtained from random shuffling method. In the bottom panel, we show the combined error calculated using Eq. 3.23.

3.10 A few words about the code

During the first year of my PhD, I invested significant efforts to develop, from scratch, a well-performing C code for computing 2pCF and MCF. The code inputs real and random catalogues with RA, Dec, redshift, and physical properties (only for real galaxies) as well as the jackknife/-bootstrap samples. It also inputs a few parameters such as the cosmological parameters, details regarding the r_p and π bins, and the number of bootstrap/jackknife copies for error estimation. The code computes the paircounts, both weighted and unweighted. It uses OpenMP (Dagum and Menon, 1998) to compute the weighted paircount for different properties parallelly. That is, it computes the MCF with different marks parallelly. The code also parallelly computes CFs for several jackknife/bootstrap copies. I have also written a separate code for power-law modelling of 2pCF using the covariance matrix and generalised χ^2 -minimisation.

My codes will, of course, need more modifications in terms of their speed, memory usage, and applications in the advanced modelling of CF (e.g. HOD modelling). I hope to implement such modifications in the future. I have published my code in github⁶. The repository also includes the data sample \mathcal{O} and random sample used for demonstration in this chapter. Please feel free to contact me by email for more details (ukp1513@gmail.com).

⁶https://github.com/ukp1513/2pcf_mcf

Chapter 4

Tracing galaxy environment using the marked correlation function in GAMA

This chapter is the combination of a part of ‘Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA): Tracing galaxy environment using the marked correlation function’ by Sureshkumar et al. (2021); Astronomy&Astrophysics, 653, A35 (arXiv:2102.04177) and ‘Galaxy properties and their environmental dependence in GAMA survey’ by Sureshkumar et al. (2020); Proceedings of the Polish Astronomical Society, Volume 10, 346-348. All of the works described in this chapter were done by me.

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we explore the dependence of galaxy clustering on the optical and near-IR properties of galaxies. The two-point correlation function (2pCF; Peebles, 1980) is a powerful tool to explore the dependence of galaxy clustering on various properties such as luminosity (Norberg et al., 2001; Pollo et al., 2006; Zehavi et al., 2011; Farrow et al., 2015), stellar mass (Meneux et al., 2008; Skibba et al., 2015; Durkalec et al., 2018), star formation rate (SFR; Hartley et al., 2010; Mostek et al., 2013), colour (Zehavi et al., 2005; Coil et al., 2008; Skibba et al., 2014), and spectral type (Norberg et al., 2002; Meneux et al., 2006). However it has been observed that clustering of luminosity-selected and stellar mass-selected samples are not identical (e.g. Marulli et al., 2013; Durkalec et al., 2018, and also see Chapter 1 for more details). This means that luminosity and stellar mass are correlated with environment differently. But, which one is strongly correlated with environment? Is this correlation similar for all the photometric bands? Answers to these questions may help us establish better constraints on galaxy formation and evolution models. In this chapter, we try to provide these answers using 2pCF and marked correlation function (MCF) measured for the galaxies selected from the Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA; Driver et al., 2009) survey in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$.

The main aim of this chapter is to demonstrate how different galaxy properties such as luminosities in different passbands, stellar mass, SFR, and specific SFR (sSFR) trace the small-scale galaxy clustering. In particular, we show which property is the best (or stronger) tracer of

the galaxy environment (understand as a galaxy over-density around the object).

Frequently, in the literature, luminosity and stellar mass are considered to be one-to-one correlated: more luminous galaxies are assumed to be more massive (Blanton and Moustakas, 2009). We also aim to study which photometric passband best serves as a proxy for stellar mass in the absence thereof. Previously it has been shown that near-IR luminosity is a good proxy of the galaxy stellar mass (Kochanek et al., 2001). Mid-IR bands, particularly those with $3.4 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.6 \mu\text{m}$ wavelengths, are also reliable tracers of galaxy stellar mass (Jarrett et al., 2013; Cluver et al., 2014). For instance, K -band selected samples are used to construct stellar mass limited samples with high completeness (van Dokkum et al., 2006; Taylor et al., 2009). However, it is not yet clear whether such samples can be used as a perfect proxy for clustering measurements. A better understanding of this issue will give us a better idea on the precautions to be taken while using these types of proxy samples for clustering studies.

This chapter is structured as follows. In Sect. 4.2 we describe the samples we used for study. We give a brief summary of the methodology in Sect. 4.3. The clustering measurements are presented in Sect. 4.4. The results are discussed and compared with other works in Sect. 4.5 and finally concluded in Sect. 4.6.

4.2 Sample selection

In this work, we select galaxy samples from the GAMA survey. We have described the survey in Sect. 2.1. In this section, we describe the properties of the galaxy samples used in this work. We make use of STELLARMASSSELAMBDA RV20 DMU (Taylor et al., 2011; Wright et al., 2016). The stellar masses are based on the methods of Taylor et al. (2011) applied to the LAMBDA R photometry of Wright et al. (2016). These methods are based on the stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling of broadband photometry using stellar evolution models by Bruzual and Charlot (2003), assuming a Chabrier (2003) initial mass function and Calzetti et al. (2000) dust law. The DMU also provides absolute magnitudes that are inferred from the SPS fits and are corrected for internal dust extinction and k -corrected to $z = 0$. As the fits are constrained to the rest-frame wavelength range 300 - 1100 nm, the J and K -band absolute magnitudes we use are extrapolations of the fit to data. The stellar masses and absolute magnitudes are fluxscale corrected as described in Taylor et al. (2011) to account for the difference in aperture matched and Sérsic photometry. Galaxies with physically unrealistic fluxscale values are not considered for our analysis.

We cross-match the GAMA TILINGCATV46 and STELLARMASSSELAMBDA RV20 catalogues using CATAID. All the galaxies have reliable spectroscopic redshift and well-measured absolute magnitudes, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR. The SFRs and sSFRs are taken from the MAGPHYSV06 DMU and are estimated using the energy balance spectral energy distribution (SED)-fitting code MAGPHYS (da Cunha et al., 2008).

Then we define Sample $\mathcal{A}1$ using the following filters:

- $\text{SURVEY_CLASS} \geq 4$, $nQ \geq 3$, $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 0$ or $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 1$ or $\text{VIS_CLASS} = 255$. We refer the reader to Sect. 3.2 for explanations of these filters.
- r -band apparent magnitude limit: $r < 19.8$
- Redshift: $0.1 < z < 0.16$. The redshift range is chosen to optimally select volume-limited samples that include low-mass galaxies.
- Stellar mass limit: $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \geq 9.3$. This value for stellar mass is decided to efficiently avoid Malmquist bias in the selected sample.

As a representative example of the selection technique, in Fig. 4.1 we show the selection cut for the sample $\mathcal{A}1$. More details of the sample $\mathcal{A}1$ are given in Table 4.1.

FIGURE 4.1: Selection of galaxy sample $\mathcal{A}1$ used in this chapter. The grey dots represent the GAMA galaxies with flux limit $r < 19.8$. The top and right histograms show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively. The red lines represent the stellar mass cut and the redshift limit of the sample $\mathcal{A}1$.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

TABLE 4.1: Properties of the sample $\mathcal{A}1$.

Sample $\mathcal{A}1$	
z_{range}	$0.1 < z < 0.16$
r_{lim}	19.8
$\log (M_{\star}/M_{\odot})^{\text{min}}$	9.3
N_{gal}	32401
$M_u^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	-18.78 ± 0.84
$M_g^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	-20.00 ± 0.87
$M_r^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	-20.58 ± 0.93
$M_J^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	-21.41 ± 1.03
$M_K^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	-21.43 ± 1.07
$\log (M_{\star}/M_{\odot})^{\text{mean}\pm 1\sigma}$	10.18 ± 0.50
$\text{SFR}^{(16\%,50\%,84\%)} (M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1})$	(0.04, 0.69, 2.50)
$\text{sSFR}^{(16\%,50\%,84\%)} (\times 10^{-12} \text{yr}^{-1})$	(1.45, 63.50, 336.40)

4.2.1 Random samples

To estimate 2pCF of a galaxy sample, we require a random sample that reflects the redshift and sky distribution of the real sample. To generate random sample for the sample $\mathcal{A}1$, we use the GAMA random galaxy catalogue (RANDOMSV02 DMU) by [Farrow et al. \(2015\)](#). This DMU provides around 400 random galaxies per real GAMA galaxy and these random galaxies share the CATAID and all the physical properties of the real galaxy. Using the CATAID, we assign the stellar mass to each random galaxy. Then a set of random galaxies are selected by applying the redshift and stellar mass limits: $0.1 < z < 0.16$ and $\log (M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \geq 9.3$. Then we select 162005 (5 times N_{gal}) galaxies randomly from that set. After applying all these selections, we confirm the agreement between the redshift and sky distributions of the real and random samples (see Fig. 4.2 and Fig. 4.3).

4.3 Measurement methods

We use galaxy 2pCF and MCF to quantify galaxy clustering and its dependence on environment. We follow the same methodology as explained in Chapter 3. We refer the reader to that chapter for a detailed step-by-step instruction on how to compute 2pCF and MCF. As a short summary, we measure the two-dimensional 2pCF $\xi(r_p, \pi)$ and integrate it along the π direction with $\pi_{\text{max}} = 40 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ to obtain the projected 2pCF $\omega_p(r_p)$ (Sect. 3.5). Then we use 12 jackknife samples

FIGURE 4.3: Sky distribution of the real and random galaxies of sample $\mathcal{A}1$ in the three separate field GAMA equatorial regions. The gray points represent the random galaxies and the red ones represent the real galaxies.

to compute the covariance matrix C_{ij} and then use SVD method to estimate the power-law fit parameters (Sect. 3.7). We also compute the MCF as described in Sect. 3.9.

4.4 Results: Two-point and marked correlation functions

FIGURE 4.4: Projected 2pCF $\omega_p(r_p)$ with a power-law fit (filled markers; left panel) and rank-ordered projected MCFs $M_p(r_p)$ (unfilled markers; right panel) for Sample $\mathcal{A}1$ described in Sect. 4.2. In the left panel, error bars of $\omega_p(r_p)$ are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained using nine jackknife region. In the right panel the different symbols represent measurements with different marks (as labelled), and the error bars are obtained by random scrambling of the marks. The error bars of $M_p(r_p)$ are too small to be visible.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

In this section, we present our results of the environmental dependence of galaxy luminosity, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR. We measure 2pCF and rank-ordered MCF for the sample $\mathcal{A}1$ described in Table 4.1 selected from GAMA. Each 2pCF is fitted with a power-law model and the MCFs are measured using eight different properties as marks: absolute magnitudes in u, g, r, J , and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR. In all the samples, we could reliably measure the CFs in the range $0.1 < r_p < 10 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$. The errors in $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from 12 jackknife realisations and the errors in $M_p(r_p)$ are obtained by randomising the marks (100 times) as described in Sect. 3.9.4.

In Fig. 4.4, we show the 2pCF and MCFs obtained for sample $\mathcal{A}1$. The left panel shows the projected 2pCF $\omega_p(r_p)$, which at first approximation obeys a power-law model. The best-fit parameters are correlation length $r_0 = 5.06 \pm 0.70 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ and slope $\gamma = 1.78 \pm 0.05$. The error contours are shown in Fig. 4.5. These results can be compared with the results of [Farrow](#)

FIGURE 4.5: The power-law fit parameters (filled star) and the corresponding 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively) of sample $\mathcal{A}1$.

et al. (2015), although their samples vary from ours. To be compared with our sample $\mathcal{A}1$, the most appropriate sample of theirs is the one with mass limits $10 < \log M_*/M_\odot h^{-2} < 10.5$ in the redshift range $0.14 < z < 0.18$. The parameter values for that sample were measured to be $r_0 = 5.94 \pm 0.46 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ and $\gamma = 1.86 \pm 0.05$. The correlation length varies by a factor of 1.1σ from our result. This small deviation in correlation length is expected as their stellar mass cuts vary from ours.

The right panel of Fig. 4.4 presents rank-ordered MCFs $M_p(r_p)$ obtained for different galaxy properties used as marks (as described in the legend). The presented MCFs strongly deviate from unity on small scales ($r_p < 1 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$) for all luminosity, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR marks. This deviation then decreases, but still remains at larger scales. In general, a stronger deviation of MCF from unity, means stronger correlation of the corresponding galaxy property with the environment (as described in Sect. 3.9). As shown in Fig. 4.4, deviation of the stellar mass MCF from unity is greater than any of the luminosity MCFs. This means that stellar mass catches the galaxy over-density in small scales stronger than other properties used in this work. Thus, stellar mass can be considered as stronger tracer of environment than luminosity (in any passband) and SFR.

Among the MCFs measured using luminosities in different passbands, the K -band MCF has

the highest amplitude and the u -band MCF has the lowest. This means that the K -band luminosity traces the environment better than any other band of those used in this work. Moreover, the K -band MCF shows similar, although not exactly the same, behaviour as the stellar mass MCF; the K -band luminosity and stellar mass are therefore correlated with the environment in a similar fashion. This, in turn, confirms that K -band luminosity can be used as a tracer (or a proxy) of stellar mass when we lack the measurements of stellar mass (Kochanek et al., 2001; Baldry et al., 2012). At the same time, our observation reveals that this connection between K band and stellar mass is not perfect (see 4.5.4 for discussion).

On the other hand, SFR and sSFR MCFs behave opposite to the stellar mass MCF; this presents low values (high deviation from unity) on small scales and high values (close to unity) on large scales. This means that there is only a small number of close pairs of galaxies with strong star formation activity. That is the densest regions of the local Universe are mainly populated by old or quiescent galaxies. Similar, although weaker, behaviour is presented by the u -band MCF. This indicates that the u -band luminosity traces galaxy SFRs (or at least serves as a proxy; Madau and Dickinson, 2014) in the context of environment.

4.5 Discussion

4.5.1 Environmental dependence of optical to near-IR luminosities, stellar mass and SFR

The MCF is a useful tool to study the environmental dependence of galaxy properties. Empirically, it is a ratio of the weighted and the unweighted CF. For a given galaxy property, all galaxy pairs in a sample carry a weight, that is the product of property values for both galaxies in units of its mean value. At each spatial scale, the MCF signal depends on the value of the weights at that scale; the larger amplitude of rank-ordered MCF, measured using a particular galaxy property, implies it has a stronger correlation with environment.

As described in Sect. 4.4 and shown in Fig. 4.4, we observe different amplitudes for MCFs measured using different galaxy properties. All galaxy properties (luminosities, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR) correlate with the environment, each in a different way. For example, the stellar mass and luminosity (in the g , r , J , and K bands) MCFs take values higher than unity on small scales, indicating an abundance of close galaxy pairs with these property values greater than the average of the sample. This agrees with the well-known observation that the most massive and luminous galaxies (in g , r , J , and K bands) are mostly found in dense regions (Norberg et al., 2002; Coil et al., 2006; Pollo et al., 2006; Meneux et al., 2009; Bolzonella et al., 2010; Abbas and Sheth, 2006; Abbas et al., 2010; Zehavi et al., 2011; Marulli et al., 2013; Skibba et al., 2014; Farrow et al., 2015; Durkalec et al., 2018; Cochrane et al., 2018). This phenomenon can be explained

in the framework of the hierarchical structure formation (Press and Schechter, 1974; White and Rees, 1978; Mo and White, 1996; Springel et al., 2005).

4.5.2 *u*-band luminosity and star formation rate dependence on the environment

We observe that the *u*-band marked correlation shows different behaviour in comparison to other passbands (*g*, *r*, *J*, and *K*, see Fig. 4.4). The *u*-band MCF takes values smaller than unity on scales $r_p < 3 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$, indicating low probability of finding pairs of two galaxies similarly bright in this band. This is in complete opposition to the results from other bands, where the most *g*, *r*, and *K* luminous galaxies were the most strongly clustered. This special behaviour of the *u*-band MCF has also been observed by Deng (2012) and it agrees with the semi-analytical galaxy formation models (see Fig. 2 of Sheth et al., 2005).

The *u*-band and UV light are thought to be primarily emitted by starburst galaxies with young stellar populations (Cram et al., 1998). The UV-selected galaxies exhibit low clustering in the local Universe (Heinis et al., 2004, 2007; Milliard et al., 2007). Heinis et al. (2004) measured a correlation length of $r_0 = 3.2_{-2.3}^{+0.8} h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ for low-redshift UV galaxies from the FOCA survey and Milliard et al. (2007) found it to be $3.7 \pm 0.6 \text{Mpc}$ from the GALEX survey. Both these observations confirm the weak clustering of UV-selected galaxies in the local Universe. This result agrees with the work done by Barsanti et al. (2018) using GAMA groups, in which they found a rise in star formation in galaxies that are located away from the group centre compared to those in the central regions.

Similarly, SFR and sSFR MCFs also have values smaller than unity on all scales. The similar behaviour of SFR and sSFR MCFs show that both these properties correlate with environment in a similar way. This means that actively star-forming galaxies are rarely found in close proximity to each other. This observation can be connected to the known fact that, at low redshifts, active star formation takes place mainly in low-density environments (Lewis et al., 2002; Gómez et al., 2003): less evolved (young) galaxies that formed in less dense regions exhibit strong star formation activity. Our observations agree with the SFR MCF measurements by Sheth et al. (2005) and, to some extent, with recent GAMA studies by Gunawardhana et al. (2018); their results show however weaker deviation of SFR and sSFR MCF from unity than ours. This can be due to the apparent absence of the SFR-density relationship as a consequence of selecting the star-forming sample of galaxies (McGee et al., 2011; Wijesinghe et al., 2012). Gunawardhana et al. (2018) measurements were made for samples of actively star-forming galaxies.

The similar behaviour of *u* band and SFR MCFs has a practical interpretation. The SFR of a galaxy can be estimated by applying a scaling factor to the luminosity measurements sensitive to star formation (Condon, 1992; Kennicutt, 1998; Madau and Dickinson, 2014). Since the *u*-band light is dominated by starburst galaxies with young stellar populations, it is more closely correlated

to SFR than to stellar mass in galaxies (Hopkins et al., 2003) and is hence considered to be an indicator of SFR. This correlation is reflected in our results; u -band MCF follows SFR MCF in tracing the galaxy environment at small scales. This suggests that u -band luminosity can be a good proxy of SFR in the context of galaxy clustering.

4.5.3 The most reliable tracer of galaxy environment

The amplitude of rank-ordered MCFs, computed using various marks, can be used to find the galaxy property with the strongest environmental dependence. Our observations suggest that this parameter is the stellar mass. We therefore are in agreement with the past results saying that the distribution of massive galaxies is strongly correlated with dark matter overdensities (Kauffmann et al., 2004; Scodeggio et al., 2009; Davidzon et al., 2016). This dependence is expected from the hierarchical structure formation theory according to which the local density contrast is connected to the properties of the hosting halo, which is further related to the galaxy stellar mass (Moster et al., 2010; Wechsler and Tinker, 2018). The strong correlation between stellar mass and environment has been taken into account in studies that explore the environmental dependence of galaxy properties (e.g. Kauffmann et al., 2004; Peng et al., 2010).

Our observations can be also interpreted in terms of galaxy evolution. The dark matter halo mass which is correlated with the environment is the main driver of galaxy evolution. It is tightly correlated with stellar mass which plays an important role in shaping galaxy star formation history (Gavazzi et al., 1996; Kauffmann et al., 2003; Heavens et al., 2004), and therefore, the stellar mass is strongly correlated with the local environment of a galaxy (Kauffmann et al., 2004; Blanton et al., 2005).

It is important to note a feature of our studies that might influence our results, namely the galaxy sample selection. In this work we measure MCFs in stellar mass selected samples only. That is our samples are nearly complete only in stellar mass and not in other properties. Our observation – stellar mass MCF being more enhanced than other MCFs – could be an outcome of this selection. We test this by repeating the measurements using samples selected based on each different property, rather than only stellar mass. That is, we measure u -band MCF in the sample selected based on u -band absolute magnitude, r -band MCF in the sample selected based on r -band absolute magnitude, and so on. The limiting values selected used to select those samples are given in Table. 4.2.

Then the 2pCF and MCF were measured in these volume-limited samples. The left panel of Fig. 4.6 shows the 2pCF measured for the volume-limited samples, while the right panel shows the MCF measured for the same samples. While we do not observe almost any difference between the 2pCF measured for galaxies selected according to their different properties, measurements of MCF clearly show that the distinct properties trace the structure in a different way, with stellar mass being more correlated with environment than any of the luminosities. We observe similar

TABLE 4.2: Properties of the volume-limited samples selected based on different properties. The columns represent the property in which the sample is complete, the cut used to select the sample and the number of galaxies.

Property	Limiting value	N_{gal}
u band	$M_u < -17.6$	32651
g band	$M_g < -19$	29831
r band	$M_r < -19.6$	28062
K band	$M_K < -19.8$	31285
Stellar mass	$\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$	32150

trends as before, ruling out the effect of sample selection on our observation. This result was published in [Sureshkumar et al. \(2020\)](#).

FIGURE 4.6: Projected correlation functions (left panel) and corresponding projected marked correlation functions (right panel) for the five volume-limited samples listed in Table 4.2.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2020\)](#)

4.5.4 K -band luminosity as a proxy for stellar mass

In our work we also study the behaviour of MCFs measured using different photometric wavebands and we find clear differences between MCFs marked with u , g , r , J , and K luminosities (see Fig. 4.4). This means that luminosities in different passbands correlate differently with the environment. Most significantly, the K band (the reddest considered) shows a stronger environmental dependence than bluer bands. This means that there is higher probability to find close pairs of galaxies similarly luminous in the K band than in other bands. In other words,

galaxies luminous in the K band are strongly clustered. This observation is in agreement with various clustering studies (e.g. [Oliver et al., 2004](#); [de la Torre et al., 2007](#)). In particular, [Sobral et al. \(2010\)](#), using sample of $H\alpha$ emitters from HiZELS survey, show a strong increase in galaxy clustering with increasing K -band luminosity, but a weak trend in case of the B band. This difference in clustering strength between various bands is reflected in the varying amplitude of MCFs in [Fig. 4.4](#).

Comparing the amplitudes of stellar mass and K -band MCFs, we observe that these galaxy properties trace the environment in a similar way. This means that the K -band luminosity can be used as the second-most reliable galaxy property (among those considered here), after galaxy stellar mass, to trace the environment. In other words, a sample that is complete in K -band luminosity can be a good substitute of a stellar-mass-complete sample.

This observation agrees with the existing results. It has been shown that longer-wavelength luminosities (e.g. K band) are dominated by evolved stellar populations and are least affected by dust extinction, making them directly related to the galaxy stellar mass ([Cowie et al., 1994](#); [Gavazzi et al., 1996](#); [Kauffmann and Charlot, 1998](#); [Kochanek et al., 2001](#); [Baldry et al., 2012](#); [Jarrett et al., 2013](#); [Cluver et al., 2014](#)). [Kauffmann and Charlot \(1998\)](#) pointed out that infrared light is a much more robust tracer of stellar mass than optical light out to $z \sim 1 - 2$. They observed that galaxies of the same stellar masses have the same K -band luminosities, independent of their star formation histories. Additionally, near-IR (mainly K -band) luminosity functions were well utilised to estimate stellar mass distribution in the local Universe ([Cole et al., 2001](#); [Kochanek et al., 2001](#); [Bell et al., 2003](#); [Drory et al., 2004](#); [Zhu et al., 2010](#); [Meidt et al., 2014](#)). Using a matched GAMA-*WISE* catalogue, [Cluver et al. \(2014\)](#) explored the usability of mid-IR wavelengths ($3.4 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.6 \mu\text{m}$) for stellar mass estimation.

However, the relation between K -band luminosity and stellar mass is not entirely direct ([van der Wel et al., 2006](#); [Kannappan and Gawiser, 2007](#)). In our results, we also observe the differences between stellar mass and K -band MCFs on small scales (see [Fig. 4.4](#)). The close galaxy pairs ($r_p < 1 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$) show stronger signals when weighted using stellar mass than when weighted with K -band luminosity. Given the fact that the latter is proportional to stellar mass, one possible reason for the difference between both MCFs could be the environmental dependence of the correlation between stellar mass and K -band luminosity. This is in qualitative agreement with the predictions of semi-analytic galaxy formation models proposed by [Sheth et al. \(2005\)](#). Their measurements were made on a volume-limited sample with $z = 0.2$ with a limiting stellar mass of $2 \times 10^{10} h^{-1}M_\odot$ that corresponds to $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.45$ in our cosmological model. Using the observed difference between K -band and stellar mass MCFs (see [Fig. 5](#) of [Sheth et al. \(2005\)](#)), they concluded that the correlation between both these properties depends on environment. The difference in K -band and stellar mass MCFs could also be the result of the stronger correlation between stellar mass and halo mass with respect to K -band luminosity ([Moster et al., 2010](#)). Hence the stellar mass MCF picks up the environmental dependence of halo mass better than

K -band MCF.

There is yet another caveat in using K -band luminosity selected samples as a proxy for stellar mass selection. By using this approximation, the most evolved (red) galaxy pairs in the sample are missed, especially on small scales. [Cochrane et al. \(2018\)](#) observed that K -band derived stellar masses are underestimated with respect to full SED stellar masses. This means that some red galaxies might wrongly end up below the applied stellar mass cut and not be selected when K -band stellar mass approximation is used. This is extremely important for high-detail clustering studies. It has been shown that red galaxies tend to occupy dense environments (see e.g. [Zehavi et al., 2005](#); [Coil et al., 2008](#); [Zehavi et al., 2011](#); [Palamara et al., 2013](#)). Samples unrepresented owing to the K -band selection might, therefore, show weaker than actual clustering properties.

4.6 Summary and conclusions

In this paper, we studied the environmental dependence of galaxy properties such as luminosity (in u, g, r, J , and K bands), stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ using a spectroscopic sample of galaxies from the GAMA survey. We checked which of these properties is a stronger tracer of the environment, and showed how the results of clustering measurements can be influenced by selecting samples using different properties. To achieve these aims, we measured the 2pCF and MCF in a nearly stellar-mass-complete sample with a flux limit $r < 19.8$ and stellar mass cut $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$. The MCFs were measured using different marks: luminosities in the u, g, r, J , and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR.

The summary of main results and conclusions of this chapter is as follows.

- We observed that different galaxy properties trace the environment differently in the separation scales $r_p < 10 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. Based on the behaviour of MCFs in [Fig. 4.4](#), we concluded that the close pairs of galaxies are more luminous in the g, r, J , and K bands than distant pairs. It is also more probable to find close pairs of massive galaxies (with masses above sample average) than pairs including one less massive galaxy. However, this trend is reversed if the luminosity is measured in the u band. The u -band luminous galaxies tend to occupy less dense regions and the faint u -band galaxies tend to exist in denser regions. The same is true for actively star-forming galaxies, which tend to occupy less dense environments.
- Using the comparisons of the amplitudes of rank-ordered luminosity, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR MCFs in [Fig. 4.4](#), we concluded that stellar mass has a stronger correlation with the galaxy environment than the other properties.
- We showed that a sample complete in K -band luminosity can be a good substitute for a stellar-mass-complete sample. But in such a case we tend to miss closer pairs of evolved, red galaxies.

- From the similarity in behaviour of different MCFs, we suggested the usefulness of u -band luminosity as a proxy of SFR in the context of galaxy clustering. However, the u band does not work as a perfect proxy of SFR to trace the environment.

The analyses described in this chapter are parts of the published works [Sureshkumar et al. \(2020, 2021\)](#) and I prepared all the presented research. Our measurements are the first of this kind in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ and with galaxies as faint as $r < 19.8$. These measurements can be a useful reference for clustering studies with flux-limited surveys, especially the next-generation galaxy surveys such as Vera C. Rubin Observatory ([LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009](#)) and Euclid ([Laureijs et al., 2011](#)).

Chapter 5

Mid-infrared properties as tracers of galaxy environment in the GAMA survey

This chapter originally appears as 'Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA): Mid-infrared properties as tracers of galaxy environment' by Sureshkumar et al. (2022); submitted to Astronomy&Astrophysics; arXiv:2201.10480. This chapter also contains results from 'Proxies for stellar mass and SFR in galaxy clustering studies' by Sureshkumar et al. (submitted to the Proceedings of the Polish Astronomical Society). All the research works described in this chapter were done by me.

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we study the correlations between mid-IR properties of galaxies and environment. In Chapter 4, we used two-point correlation function (2pCF) and marked correlation function (MCF) to study how properties such as luminosities in u, g, r, J, K bands, stellar mass, SFR and specific SFR trace small-scale clustering in the Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA; Driver et al., 2009) survey. We observed a hierarchy of luminosity passbands in which the redder K band appears to trace the galaxy clustering better than $u, g, r,$ and J bands. In addition, we observed that the photometric K band ($2.2 \mu\text{m}$) follows the stellar mass and the u band ($0.4 \mu\text{m}$) follows the SFR in tracing the environment.

In this context, it is interesting to explore how even longer wavelengths, i.e. the IR bands trace the galaxy clustering. The clustering of IR galaxies is of particular interest because different parts of the IR spectrum trace different physical processes. The near-IR emission of a galaxy is primarily from the evolved stellar populations and hence serves as a good indicator of its stellar mass (Kauffmann and Charlot, 1998; Cole et al., 2001). The mid-IR region has dual capability: lower wavelengths are sensitive to light from the evolved population of stars and higher wavelengths are sensitive to star formation (Meidt et al., 2012; Wen et al., 2013; Jarrett et al., 2013; Cluver et al., 2014). The far-IR region has also been proven to be a good indicator of SFR (Calzetti et al., 2010).

There have been studies of clustering of galaxies selected in near-IR wavelengths (e.g. [Baugh et al., 1996](#); [Roche et al., 1998, 1999](#); [Daddi et al., 2000](#); [Kümmel and Wagner, 2000](#); [Maller et al., 2005](#)). The clustering of mid-IR selected galaxies is also well studied using surveys and telescopes such as the Infrared Astronomical Satellite (IRAS, [Fisher et al., 1994](#)), European Large-Area *ISO* survey (ELAIS; [Gonzalez-Solares et al., 2004](#); [D’Elia et al., 2005](#)), *Spitzer* ([Fang et al., 2004](#); [Oliver et al., 2004](#); [Gilli et al., 2007](#); [de la Torre et al., 2007](#); [Waddington et al., 2007](#)). In the far-IR region, clustering studies are done with Herschel ([Cooray et al., 2010](#); [Maddox et al., 2010](#); [Magliocchetti et al., 2011](#)) and AKARI ([Pollo et al., 2013a,b](#); [Solarz et al., 2015](#)). It is observed that in general, the IR selected galaxies show stronger clustering than optically selected ones.

In the mid-IR regime, *Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer* (*WISE*; [Wright et al., 2010](#)) covers the entire sky at four bands – W1 (3.4 μm), W2 (4.6 μm), W3 (12 μm), and W4 (22 μm). The W1 and W2 bands, being closer to near-IR bands, trace the continuum emission from evolved stars with minimal extinction. The W3 and W4 bands are good indicators of the interstellar medium and star formation activity – W3 being dominated by the stochastically heated 11.3 μm polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) and 12.8 μm [Ne II] emission features and W4 traces the dust continuum that is a combination of warm and cold small grains in equilibrium ([Jarrett et al., 2013](#); [Cluver et al., 2014](#)). As different *WISE* bands trace different galaxy properties, *WISE* photometric data can be useful to study how various mid-IR properties follow the galaxy environment.

The main aim of this chapter is to utilise 2pCF and MCF to explore the environmental dependence of *WISE* band properties in GAMA. We use a set of galaxy samples from the GAMA survey enhanced with mid-IR properties from *WISE* ([Cluver et al., 2014, 2020](#)). Due to its high completeness ($> 98.5\%$) down to $r < 19.8$, GAMA has been abundantly used for clustering studies (e.g. [Christodoulou et al., 2012](#); [Lindsay et al., 2014](#); [Farrow et al., 2015](#); [Loveday et al., 2018](#); [Gunawardhana et al., 2018](#); [Sureshkumar et al., 2021](#)). In particular using the *WISE* photometry, the clustering of galaxies in the G12 region of GAMA was studied by [Jarrett et al. \(2017\)](#). In this chapter, we study how the *WISE* luminosities, trace galaxy clustering in all the three equatorial regions of GAMA (G09, G12, and G15) using MCFs. We also explore the dependence of galaxy clustering on the W1 absolute magnitude and redshift using 2pCFs.

In addition, we check the consistency between different estimates of stellar mass and SFR in tracing the galaxy clustering. The different techniques involved in the estimation of these properties often severely affect the estimates ([Mitchell et al., 2013](#); [Mobasher et al., 2015](#)). So it is important to check if such differences influence the way in which these properties trace the environment. For that, we use three different independent estimates of stellar mass in GAMA: one from stellar population synthesis (SPS) modelling by [Taylor et al. \(2011\)](#), a second one based on mid-IR photometry by [Cluver et al. \(2014\)](#), and a third one derived using the PROSPECT code ([Robotham et al., 2020](#)). Similarly we also use a few independent SFR estimates. In addition

to the MAGPHYSV06 SFR (da Cunha et al., 2008), there are SFRs based on the W3 and W4 bands by Cluver et al. (2017) and from PROSPECT code. The Taylor et al. (2011) and Cluver et al. (2014) stellar masses were checked for consistency between each other by Kettlety et al. (2018). In this work, we measure and compare MCFs using these different estimates as marks to check the consistency in tracing the galaxy clustering.

This chapter is organized as follows. In Sect. 5.2 we describe properties of the GAMA-WISE and ProSpect catalogues, our sample selection methods, and the random catalogue. The results of our measurements are presented in Sect. 5.3, discussed and compared with other works in Sect. 5.4, and finally concluded in Sect. 5.5.

5.2 Data

Galaxy and Mass Assembly is a spectroscopic survey that observes galaxies down to extinction-corrected r -band Petrosian magnitudes $r_{\text{petro}} < 19.8$ mag (Driver et al., 2009). A description of the GAMA survey is given in Sect. 2.1. Here, we describe the properties of the galaxy samples used in this work. As the primary data, we use the r -band limited data from GAMA II equatorial regions (G09, G12, and G15). We select GAMA main survey galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts in the range $0.07 < z < 0.43$. We choose $z_{\text{min}} = 0.07$ to avoid our samples being dominated by local structures, whereas we choose $z_{\text{max}} = 0.43$ to optimally select populous volume-limited samples.

5.2.1 Galaxy properties

In this work, we first use 2pCF to study the dependence of galaxy clustering on the W1 absolute magnitude and redshift. Then we use MCFs to explore the environmental dependence of 11 galaxy properties: four luminosities (L_{W1} , L_{W2} , L_{W3} , and L_{W4}), three stellar mass estimates (M_{GAMA}^* , M_{WISE}^* , and M_{ProSpect}^*), and four SFR estimates (SFR_{GAMA} , $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$, $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$, and $\text{SFR}_{\text{ProSpect}}$). All galaxy properties except those from the ProSpect catalogue are measured using $h = 0.7$. The ProSpect catalogue was created using $h = 0.678$ (Bellstedt et al., 2020b).

GAMA catalogue

As a base for comparison, we use the stellar mass (M_{GAMA}^*) and star formation rate (SFR_{GAMA}) from the main GAMA catalogue. M_{GAMA}^* is from STELLARMASSES LAMB DARV20 DMU (Taylor et al., 2011; Wright et al., 2016). These stellar mass estimates are based on the methods of Taylor et al. (2011) applied to the LAMB DAR photometry of Wright et al. (2016). Since the photometry is aperture-matched, it is necessary to scale the inferred stellar mass to account for flux lying beyond the finite aperture. For that, we apply the `fluxscale` (ratio between the r band aperture flux and the total Sérsic flux) correction to M_{GAMA}^* as described in Taylor et al.

(2011). In addition to the filtering described in Sects. 2.1 and 5.2, we retain only those galaxies with $0 < \text{fluxscale} < 50$. We choose this range to avoid extreme fluxscale corrections and at the same time not reduce the sample size significantly. We use this set of galaxies as our parent sample. SFR_{GAMA} is taken from the `MAGPHYSV06` DMU and is estimated using the energy balance spectral energy distribution (SED)-fitting code `MAGPHYS` (da Cunha et al., 2008).

GAMA-WISE catalogue

We take the quantities L_{W1} , L_{W2} , L_{W3} , L_{W4} , M_{WISE}^* , $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$, and $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$ from the GAMA-WISE catalogue. It is a source-matched catalogue developed by cross-matching GAMA galaxies with the WISE All-Sky Catalogue using a $3''$ cone search radius. The galaxy properties such as M_{WISE}^* is derived as a function of W1–W2 color (Cluver et al., 2014) and $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$ and $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$ are derived using the W3 and W4 luminosities respectively (Cluver et al., 2017). We refer the reader to Cluver et al. (2014, 2020) for a detailed description of the construction of this catalogue.

ProSpect catalogue

The ProSpect catalogue was made using `PROSPECT` SED-fitting code (Robotham et al., 2020) applied to the `PROFOUND` photometry from GAMA (Bellstedt et al., 2020a). As described in Bellstedt et al. (2020b), the SEDs are generated using the stellar population template by Bruzual and Charlot (2003) and dust attenuation law by Charlot and Fall (2000). M_{ProSpect}^* and $\text{SFR}_{\text{ProSpect}}$ used in this work are taken from this ProSpect catalogue.

5.2.2 W1 magnitude and redshift binned samples

Our parent sample consists of galaxies with a flux limit of $r_{\text{petro}} < 19.8$ in a redshift range of $0.07 < z < 0.43$. We select all galaxies in the parent sample with matches in the GAMA-WISE catalogue and assign W1 absolute magnitudes by a cross-matching technique using GAMA's unique source identifier `CATAID`. The W1 absolute magnitudes are then corrected for luminosity evolution using the model from Lake et al. (2018) as described in Appendix D. Then we select various sets of volume-limited subsamples using corrected W1 absolute magnitudes.

To study the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF, we first bin the galaxies into four different redshift bins: \mathcal{A} ($0.07 \leq z < 0.15$), \mathcal{B} ($0.15 \leq z < 0.25$), \mathcal{C} ($0.25 \leq z < 0.35$), and \mathcal{D} ($0.35 \leq z < 0.43$). Each redshift bin is further divided into different W1 absolute magnitude bins giving a total of 11 samples (named from $\mathcal{A}1$ to $\mathcal{D}4$). This selection is shown in top panel of Fig. 5.1 and the details such as sample name, redshift range, W1 absolute magnitude range, and number of galaxies are given in Table 5.1.

FIGURE 5.1: Selection of subsamples used to study the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF (top panel), redshift dependence of 2pCF (middle panel), and environmental dependence of galaxy properties using MCF (bottom panel).

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

TABLE 5.1: Definitions and the number of galaxies of different galaxy subsamples used for studying the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF.

Sample	z^{range}	M_{W1}^{range}	N_{gal}
$\mathcal{A}1$	$0.07 \leq z < 0.15$	$-22 < M_{W1} \leq -21$	7487
$\mathcal{A}2$		$-23 < M_{W1} \leq -22$	10758
$\mathcal{A}3$		$-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$	9945
$\mathcal{A}4$		$M_{W1} \leq -24$	5040
$\mathcal{B}1$	$0.15 \leq z < 0.25$	$-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$	23521
$\mathcal{B}2$		$-25 < M_{W1} \leq -24$	14657
$\mathcal{B}3$		$M_{W1} \leq -25$	2267
$\mathcal{C}1$	$0.25 \leq z < 0.35$	$-25 < M_{W1} \leq -24$	26608
$\mathcal{C}2$		$M_{W1} \leq -25$	5704
$\mathcal{D}1$	$0.35 \leq z < 0.43$	$-25 < M_{W1} \leq -24$	10191
$\mathcal{D}2$		$M_{W1} \leq -25$	4770

TABLE 5.2: Definitions of the galaxy subsamples used for studying the redshift dependence of 2pCF.

Sample	M_{W1}^{range}	z^{range}	N_{gal}
$\mathcal{M}1$	$-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$	$0.07 \leq z < 0.15$	9945
$\mathcal{M}2$		$0.15 \leq z < 0.25$	23521
$\mathcal{N}1$	$M_{W1} \leq -24$	$0.07 \leq z < 0.15$	5040
$\mathcal{N}2$		$0.15 \leq z < 0.25$	16924
$\mathcal{N}3$		$0.25 \leq z < 0.35$	32312
$\mathcal{N}4$		$0.35 \leq z < 0.43$	14961

To study the redshift dependence of 2pCF, we need subsamples with varying redshift in the same magnitude range. For that, we first create two magnitude bins \mathcal{M} ($-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$) and \mathcal{N} ($M_{W1} \leq -24$). Each magnitude bin is further divided into different redshift bins giving a total of six subsamples (named from $\mathcal{M}1$ to $\mathcal{N}4$) as shown in the middle panel of Fig. 5.1. The properties of these subsamples such as sample name, W1 absolute magnitude range, redshift range, and number of galaxies are given in Table 5.2.

Although we define a total of 17 samples in Table 5.1 and Table 5.2, some of the samples are overlapping ($\mathcal{A}3$ - $\mathcal{M}1$, $\mathcal{A}4$ - $\mathcal{N}1$, and $\mathcal{B}1$ - $\mathcal{M}2$) leaving 14 unique samples. However, we name them differently for clarity and easier interpretation.

TABLE 5.3: Definitions of the galaxy subsamples used for studying the environmental dependence of galaxy properties using MCFs.

Sample	z^{range}	M_{W1}^{lim} (upper)	$N_{\text{gal}}^{\text{selection}}$			
			W1	W2	W3	W4
\mathcal{P}	$0.07 \leq z < 0.15$	-21	31555	30991	25862	16799
\mathcal{Q}	$0.15 \leq z < 0.25$	-23	38135	38115	30529	19877
\mathcal{R}	$0.25 \leq z < 0.35$	-24	30265	30263	23034	15023
\mathcal{S}	$0.35 \leq z < 0.43$	-24	14224	14222	10564	6447

5.2.3 W1 to W4 selection of the W1 magnitude limited samples

By a cross-matching technique using CATAID, we select the galaxies in the parent sample with matches in the GAMA-*WISE* and ProSpect catalogues. Then we assign L_{W1} , L_{W2} , L_{W3} , L_{W4} , M_{WISE}^* , $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$, and $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$ from the GAMA-*WISE* catalogue and M_{ProSpect}^* and $\text{SFR}_{\text{ProSpect}}$ from ProSpect catalogue. As demonstrated in the bottom panel of Fig. 5.1, we select only the galaxies above a certain W1 absolute magnitude limit in each redshift bin. This gives four samples: \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} .

Further in each of these four samples, we apply four different selections based on their luminosities in W1, W2, W3, and W4 bands resulting in a total number of 16 subsamples. Specifically in this context, we define a selection in a particular band as selecting only those galaxies with available luminosity measurements in the respective band. That is, the W1 selection selects only those galaxies with W1 luminosity available, W2 selection selects only those galaxies with W2 luminosity available, and so on. For example, in sample \mathcal{P} , there are 31555, 30991, 25862, and 16799 galaxies having the W1, W2, W3, and W4 luminosities, respectively. The differences between these selections are due to the difference in sensitivity of *WISE* bands with W3 and W4 being less sensitive than the W1 and W2 bands (Wright et al., 2010; Jarrett et al., 2013).

The properties of these subsamples such as sample name, redshift range, upper limiting W1 absolute magnitude, and number of galaxies in W1, W2, W3, and W4 selections are given in Table 5.3. For each of the 16 subsamples, we measure the 2pCFs and MCFs using those properties that have available measurements in that particular selection.

5.2.4 Random samples

We generate random samples in the similar way as described in Sect. 4.2.1. In this case, we assign the W1 absolute magnitude to each random galaxy using the CATAID. Then for all the selected samples, random samples are created by applying the corresponding redshift and magnitude limits

TABLE 5.4: Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study the W1 absolute magnitude dependence of 2pCF.

Sample	$r_0 (h^{-1}\text{Mpc})$	γ	χ^2
A1	3.94 ± 0.59	1.62 ± 0.10	0.82
A2	5.39 ± 0.87	1.66 ± 0.10	0.08
A3	5.99 ± 0.98	1.71 ± 0.17	0.01
A4	6.83 ± 3.89	1.72 ± 0.77	0.01
B1	5.16 ± 0.36	1.74 ± 0.06	1.21
B2	5.68 ± 0.54	1.82 ± 0.06	0.10
B3	7.14 ± 1.10	1.87 ± 0.27	4.20
C1	5.52 ± 0.28	1.78 ± 0.04	0.04
C2	7.38 ± 0.45	1.85 ± 0.07	6.08
D1	5.78 ± 0.31	1.77 ± 0.05	3.44
D2	6.56 ± 0.52	2.04 ± 0.07	15.70

as given in Tables 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3 and randomly selecting 5-10 times the number of galaxies in the corresponding real samples.

5.3 Results

In this section, we present the measurements of 2pCF and MCFs in the various W1-absolute magnitude selected subsamples defined in Sect. 5.2.2 and Sect. 5.2.3. A detailed description of how to compute 2pCF and MCF is given in Chapter 3. The MCFs are measured using the luminosities in WISE bands, stellar masses and SFRs computed by Taylor et al. (2011), Cluver et al. (2014, 2017), and Robotham et al. (2020). All the 2pCFs are fitted with power-law models. The errors of 2pCFs are obtained from nine jackknife realizations and that of MCFs are obtained by the random scrambling method.

5.3.1 Dependence of 2pCF on W1 luminosity

In Fig. 5.2 we show the measurements of 2pCF with their corresponding power-law fits for 11 samples described in Table 5.1. The four different panels of Fig. 5.2 show the measurements in four different redshift bins, whereas in each panel we show the 2pCF for samples with varying W1 absolute magnitude cuts, as labelled (the markers and lines of samples representing similar magnitude cuts have similar colors in all the panels). In the insets of each panel, we show the best-fitting power-law parameters with corresponding 1σ error contours. The parameters are also listed in Table 5.4.

FIGURE 5.2: Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to different W1 absolute magnitude bins (as labelled) in four different redshift bins: $0.07 \leq z < 0.15$ (upper left panel), $0.15 \leq z < 0.25$ (upper right panel), $0.25 \leq z < 0.35$ (lower left panel), and $0.35 \leq z < 0.43$ (lower right panel). The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

By comparing the correlation length and slope of samples that differ in the W1 absolute magnitude but fall in the same redshift range, we confirm that brighter galaxies cluster more strongly than fainter ones (Jarrett et al., 2017). The correlation length increases by 1.8σ between $\mathcal{A}1$ and $\mathcal{A}3$, by 1.7σ between $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}3$, by 3.5σ between $\mathcal{C}1$ and $\mathcal{C}2$, and 1.3σ between $\mathcal{D}1$ and $\mathcal{D}2$. We do not consider the sample $\mathcal{A}4$ for comparison here because of the large uncertainties in its power-law fit parameters caused by the relatively small number of galaxies and the stronger off-diagonal elements of its covariance matrix.

5.3.2 Dependence of 2pCF on redshift

In Fig. 5.3, we show the 2pCF measurements of six samples described in Table 5.2. The left panel shows the measurements at different redshift ranges for the fainter galaxies in W1 and the right panel shows those for the brighter galaxies. The same colored curves in the panels represent the same redshift ranges. The best-fitting power-law parameters for these samples are given in Table 5.5.

TABLE 5.5: Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study redshift dependence of 2pCF.

Sample	r_0 ($h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$)	γ	χ^2
$\mathcal{M}1$	5.99 ± 0.98	1.71 ± 0.17	0.01
$\mathcal{M}2$	5.16 ± 0.36	1.74 ± 0.06	1.21
$\mathcal{N}1$	6.83 ± 3.89	1.72 ± 0.77	0.01
$\mathcal{N}2$	5.47 ± 0.45	1.90 ± 0.06	3.58
$\mathcal{N}3$	5.83 ± 0.29	1.82 ± 0.04	0.05
$\mathcal{N}4$	6.00 ± 0.27	1.81 ± 0.05	1.32

We study the redshift evolution of the correlation function of galaxy samples that are equally limited by the W1 absolute magnitude. From the best fitting power law parameters, it is observed that the clustering strength does not significantly vary between galaxy samples at different redshifts. The correlation lengths of $\mathcal{M}1$ and $\mathcal{M}2$ are comparable within 1σ . Same is the case with $\mathcal{N}2$ and $\mathcal{N}4$. We omit sample $\mathcal{N}1$ from this comparison because of its unreliable measurements of power-law fit parameters with large uncertainties.

In Fig. 5.4, we show the parameters r_0 and γ as a function of the median W1 absolute magnitude color-coded with the median redshift of all the unique samples mentioned in Sect. 5.2.2. We omit the $\mathcal{A}4$ (same as $\mathcal{N}1$) sample in this figure due to its large errorbars. We see a gradual decrease in the correlation length r_0 with increase in the absolute magnitude (decrease in luminosity) in W1 band at all redshift. That implies the stronger clustering of W1-bright galaxies in the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$.

FIGURE 5.3: Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to different redshift bins (as labelled) in the magnitude ranges $-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$ (left panel) and $M_{W1} \leq -24$ (right panel). The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

5.3.3 Dependence of 2pCF on W1 to W4 selection

In this section, we study the dependence of 2pCF on W1, W2, W3, and W4 selections. As explained in Sect. 5.2.3, we apply these four selections in samples \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} and compute the 2pCF in the resulting 16 subsamples. The 2pCF measurements and best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contours in those 16 subsamples are shown in Fig. 5.5. Each panel of the figure represents a different redshift range and different curves in each panel represent different selections as labelled. The best-fit parameter values are tabulated in Table 5.6.

It is to be noted in Table 5.3 that W1 and W2 selections select almost the same galaxies in \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} samples. This makes their power-law parameters very similar. Hence in the insets of Fig. 5.5, the W2 selection contour overlaps the W1 contour in \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} . In all the panels except for \mathcal{Q} , we observe a difference in correlation lengths between W1 and W4 selections. W4 selected galaxies exhibit a weaker clustering than W1 selected galaxies.

5.3.4 Marked correlation functions

In this section, we present the measurements of MCFs in 16 subsamples described in Table 5.3. MCFs are computed using 11 galaxy properties as marks: L_{W1} , L_{W2} , L_{W3} , L_{W4} , M_{GAMA}^* , M_{WISE}^* , M_{ProSpect}^* , SFR_{GAMA} , $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$, $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$, and $\text{SFR}_{\text{ProSpect}}$. The results in the lower redshift bin (Sample \mathcal{P}) are shown in Fig. 5.6 and those in the rest of the samples are shown in Fig. 5.7.

TABLE 5.6: Best-fitting power-law parameters for the galaxy samples used to study dependence of 2pCF on W1 to W4 selection.

Selection	$r_0 (h^{-1}\text{Mpc})$	γ	χ^2
Sample \mathcal{P} ($0.07 \leq z < 0.15$)			
W1	5.61 ± 0.57	1.67 ± 0.03	0.10
W2	5.43 ± 0.54	1.67 ± 0.04	2.60
W3	4.93 ± 0.57	1.65 ± 0.04	1.53
W4	4.74 ± 0.57	1.67 ± 0.05	1.34
Sample \mathcal{Q} ($0.15 \leq z < 0.25$)			
W1	5.39 ± 0.42	1.83 ± 0.05	0.13
W2	5.39 ± 0.42	1.83 ± 0.05	0.13
W3	5.00 ± 0.46	1.79 ± 0.06	0.82
W4	4.89 ± 0.48	1.79 ± 0.07	3.13
Sample \mathcal{R} ($0.25 \leq z < 0.35$)			
W1	5.86 ± 0.21	1.83 ± 0.04	3.24
W2	5.86 ± 0.21	1.83 ± 0.04	3.25
W3	5.61 ± 0.20	1.77 ± 0.05	2.10
W4	5.49 ± 0.20	1.75 ± 0.05	1.55
Sample \mathcal{S} ($0.35 \leq z < 0.43$)			
W1	6.16 ± 0.23	1.83 ± 0.05	1.77
W2	6.16 ± 0.23	1.83 ± 0.05	1.76
W3	5.78 ± 0.23	1.79 ± 0.06	0.92
W4	5.65 ± 0.24	1.82 ± 0.06	2.02

FIGURE 5.4: Dependence of the power-law fit parameters on the median W1 absolute magnitude color coded with the median redshift of the sample.

In Fig. 5.6, each panel represents one of the W1 to W4 selections applied on the Sample \mathcal{P} . In Fig. 5.7, each row shows the measurements in different redshift bins (Samples \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S}), whereas each column deals with the W1 to W4 selections applied. In each selection, we present MCFs with only those properties with available measurements in the catalogue (as described in the legends of Fig. 5.6). For instance, not all the galaxies in the W1 selection have their W4 luminosities measured. So we cannot measure the L_{W4} MCF in the W1 selection. But on the other side, all galaxies in the W4 selection have their W1 luminosity measured. That enables us to measure and present the L_{W1} MCF in the W4 selection.

For a given property (mark), the strength of deviation of its MCF from unity implies the strength of the correlation (MCF > 1) or anti-correlation (MCF < 1) between that property and the environment. In all the panels of Fig. 5.6 and Fig. 5.7, all the MCFs deviate from unity in small scales and approach unity at larger scales. That shows the environmental dependence of all the properties that we considered for the analysis.

All presented MCFs are rank-ordered. So, a simple comparison of MCFs obtained using different properties can tell us which property is more dependent on environment (Skibba et al., 2013). In Fig. 5.6, we see that the stellar mass MCFs (M_{GAMA}^* , M_{WISE}^* , and M_{ProSpect}^*) are the strongest in the scales $r_p > 0.1 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ in all the panels. The luminosity MCFs L_{W1} and L_{W2} follow stellar mass MCFs. But L_{W3} and L_{W4} show an opposite pattern and closely follow

FIGURE 5.5: Projected two-point correlation functions corresponding to the W1, W2, W3, and W4 selections applied in the samples \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} , and \mathcal{S} corresponding to redshift ranges $0.07 \leq z < 0.15$, $0.15 \leq z < 0.25$, $0.25 \leq z < 0.35$, and $0.35 \leq z < 0.43$, respectively. The insets show the best fitting power-law parameters with 1σ error contour. The error bars on the markers are the square root of the diagonals of the covariance matrix obtained from jackknife resampling method.

Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (2022)

SFR12_{WISE} and SFR22_{WISE} respectively.

5.3.5 Comparison with u band and K band

In this section, we present such a comparative study in the context of galaxy clustering. For that purpose we use the W4 selection of sample Q with the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.15$ and W1-absolute magnitude limit $M_{W1}^{\text{lim}} \leq -21$ (see Table. 5.3). In Fig. 5.8, we present the measurements of MCFs obtained using galaxy luminosities in u , K , W1, W2, W3, W4 bands, stellar mass and SFR as marks.

From the comparison of amplitudes of MCFs obtained using luminosities in K , W1, W2 bands, and stellar mass (left panel of Fig. 5.8), we see that they trace the environment in a similar fashion. However, none of the luminosities provides an amplitude of MCF as strong as stellar mass itself. The closest to stellar mass are the K band and W1 band luminosities, with the K band MCF behaviour being systematically slightly closer but consistent with respect to the error bars. This implies that the K band can be regarded as a more robust proxy for stellar mass than the mid-infrared bands in terms of galaxy clustering. This may be due to the larger contribution from asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars relative to those from red giant branch (RGB) stars at the longer wavelength, with AGB stars being more sensitive to star formation than RGB stars (Lacey et al., 2008).

In the right panel of Fig. 5.8, we see a similarity in the behaviour of u , W3, W4 bands, and the SFR MCFs, however none of them properly agree with each other. From our measurement it is clear that none of the single band luminosities we considered (u , W3, and W4) can serve as a perfect proxy for SFR in clustering studies (see Sect. 5.4.3 for discussion). We have already seen the case of u band in the Sect. 4.5.2. However, the closest one appears to be the W3 band.

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 W1 magnitude dependence of galaxy clustering

Two-point correlation function is an efficient tool to study the clustering of galaxies and its dependence on galaxy properties. The correlation lengths of different samples can be compared to conclude which sample exhibits stronger clustering – higher amplitude implies stronger clustering (see Sect. 3.1 for details). In Sect. 5.3.1, we compare the correlation lengths obtained in different samples with varying W1 absolute magnitude limits.

We observed a clear dependence of galaxy clustering on the W1 absolute magnitude in all the redshift bins in the range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$ (Fig. 5.2). The galaxies that are brighter in the W1 band cluster stronger than those that are fainter. This means that in the redshift range of $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$, galaxies that are brighter in the W1 band tend to exist in denser regions of the LSS than their fainter counterparts. This result is in agreement with Jarrett et al. (2017) as

FIGURE 5.6: Rank-ordered projected MCFs obtained using different properties (as labelled) in subsamples obtained from the W1 to W4 selection in Sample \mathcal{P} .

The error bars are obtained by random scrambling of marks.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

FIGURE 5.7: Rank-ordered projected MCFs obtained using different properties (as labelled) in subsamples obtained from the W1 to W4 selection in Sample Q , R , and S . Each row represents the samples in the same redshift bin and each column represents the samples with the same selection. The error bars are obtained by random scrambling of marks.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

FIGURE 5.8: Luminosities as proxies of stellar mass (*left panel*) and SFR (*right panel*).

Image credit: Sureshkumar et al. (submitted)

they observed that when the galaxies are divided based on the apparent W1 absolute magnitude, brighter galaxies cluster more strongly than the fainter ones do. The dependence of clustering on W1 ($3.4 \mu\text{m}$) magnitude can be compared to that on the K ($2.2 \mu\text{m}$) magnitude because both the bands are sensitive to the similarly evolved galaxy population (Jarrett et al., 2017). Many studies showed an enhancement in the clustering amplitude of brighter galaxies in the K band in comparison to the fainter ones (Baugh et al., 1996; Daddi et al., 2003; Maller et al., 2005; Sobral et al., 2010). We note that these wavelengths are dominated by older stellar populations (Kauffmann and Charlot, 1998). The W1 mass-to-light ratio is relatively constant for different stellar populations (Wen et al., 2013; Meidt et al., 2014; Kettley et al., 2018). So galaxies brighter in the W1 band are preferably evolved (hence massive) and are expected to cluster more due to the stronger clustering behaviour of massive galaxies (Cochrane et al., 2018; Durkalec et al., 2018).

Our observation – galaxies that are more luminous in the W1 band tend to cluster more – can be explained in the context of galaxy formation and evolution. According to the hierarchical model of structure formation, small initial perturbations in the density field of the Universe evolved under gravity and formed the present LSS (Press and Schechter, 1974; Mo and White, 1996). The stronger over-densities resulted in dark matter haloes in which the galaxies were born. The massive dark matter haloes provided the potential strong enough to form the massive galaxies. That means the halo mass is tightly correlated with the galaxy mass (Moster et al., 2010). Since W1 selected galaxies are preferably massive ones due to their relatively constant mass-to-light ratios (Meidt et al., 2014), the clustering of W1 selected galaxies is expected to be driven by the clustering of more massive haloes (Conroy et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2007).

5.4.2 Redshift evolution of galaxy clustering

Due to the evolution of the density field of the Universe over time, it is expected that the galaxy clustering strength increases with decreasing redshift. In Sect. 5.3.2, we compare the correlation lengths of samples with the same magnitude range, but different redshift ranges. As shown in Fig. 5.2, contrary to the expectations we do not observe a redshift evolution of clustering of W1 selected galaxies between $z = 0.07$ and $z = 0.43$ for galaxies limited by $M_{W1} \leq -24$ and between $z = 0.07$ and $z = 0.25$ for galaxies in the magnitude range $-24 < M_{W1} \leq -23$. Although there is a slight decrease of correlation length between samples $\mathcal{M}1$ and $\mathcal{M}2$, the difference is insignificant as it falls in the measurement uncertainty.

We propose two reasons for the lack of redshift dependence of clustering of W1 selected galaxies. First, the GAMA survey is flux-limited with $r < 19.8$. This imposed flux limit can cause an incompleteness in the samples selected by galaxy properties such as absolute magnitudes and stellar mass. Indeed, this effect has been observed in Sureshkumar et al. (2021), where a stellar mass incompleteness imposed by the flux limit impacted the clustering measurements in GAMA. Since the W1 band traces the stellar mass (Jarrett et al., 2013), we expect the same incompleteness in the W1 absolute magnitude, especially in higher redshift bins. So although with the same W1 absolute magnitude limit, the higher redshift bins select more luminous galaxies than lower redshift bins. For example, the median M_{W1} of the higher redshift sample $\mathcal{N}4$ is -24.78 , whereas that of the lower redshift sample $\mathcal{N}1$ is -24.40 (middle panel of Fig. 5.1). So, the higher redshift samples exhibit stronger clustering. This effect counteracts the expected intrinsic evolution of galaxies (e.g. Arnouts et al., 1999) and might be responsible for the lack of evolution of clustering in our observation. Secondly, it is to be noted that the redshift ranges that we consider ($0.07 \leq z < 0.43$) could be too narrow to see a significant evolution.

It is also worth to comment on the poorly constrained power law fit parameters measured for the $\mathcal{N}1$ sample. The large error contour of this sample is due to the stronger off-diagonal elements of the covariance matrix (Eq. 3.11) that is caused by the finite-volume effect. Our volume-limited samples at different redshift bins span different volumes of the LSS - the lowest redshift slice covering smallest volume, and the highest redshift sample covering the biggest volume. As a result the low redshift samples tend to miss out the brighter galaxies. Since brighter galaxies are expected to be more clustered, this effect distorts the CF at the smallest r_p scales. In the inset of the right panel of Fig. 5.3, this effect is seen as a decrease in the slope of the 2pCF of $\mathcal{N}1$ in comparison with other samples (although within the error bars). This effect was observed similarly by Zehavi et al. (2011, see Fig. 9) in their brightest galaxy sample.

5.4.3 WISE-derived properties as tracers of galaxy clustering

In Sect. 5.3.4, we present the results of MCF measurements in which the galaxies are weighted using the luminosities in W1, W3, W3, W4 bands, stellar masses, and SFRs. In general we observe

two different behaviours among two sets of *WISE* luminosities. Firstly, W1 and W2 luminosity MCFs closely follow the stellar mass MCFs – in particular the *WISE* stellar mass M_{WISE}^* . This is not surprising since M_{WISE}^* is estimated empirically as a function of W1 – W2 color (Cluver et al., 2014). The reason for such an approach is that the W1 and W2 bands mainly trace the continuum emission from evolved stars and the major part of baryons in a galaxy are trapped in those evolved stars (Jarrett et al., 2013). This makes W1 and W2 bands nearly ideal tracers of the galaxy stellar mass.

Secondly, we observe that the *WISE* W3 and W4 luminosity MCFs follow the SFR MCFs in general. The W3 band at 12 μm is sensitive to PAH (Jarrett et al., 2013) which are abundant in actively star forming regions of the galaxy (Sandstrom et al., 2010) and hence a direct estimate of the global SFR (Calzetti et al., 2007; Treyer et al., 2010). The W4 band (22 μm) measures the warm dust continuum which provides a reliable measure of star formation in the absence of active galactic nucleus (AGN) activity. The $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$ and $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$ are monochromatically derived from the W3 and W4 luminosities respectively (Cluver et al., 2014, 2017) and hence the W3 and W4 luminosity MCFs perfectly follow the corresponding SFR MCFs. However, the SFRs estimated from mid-IR luminosities represent only a part of the total IR SFR. What is lacking would be the largely obscured star formation in dense molecular cores which is best traced by the far-IR bands (Lacey et al., 2008; Jarrett et al., 2013). That is, mid-IR luminosities alone do not provide a complete picture of the star formation and hence proper care has to be taken while using W3 and W4 luminosities and their associated SFR estimates for clustering studies.

5.4.4 Environmental dependence of different estimates of stellar mass and SFR

In Sect. 5.3.4, we observe that rank-ordered stellar mass MCF shows the strongest amplitude compared to other properties, regardless of the method of estimation and selection. This is in agreement with the conclusions of Sureshkumar et al. (2021) in which we compared the stellar mass MCFs to $u, g, r, J,$ and K band luminosities and SFR MCFs and observed a stronger amplitude for the stellar mass MCF than others. In this work, we observe that in case of W1 selected galaxies, stellar mass is the property which better traces the galaxy clustering than luminosities and SFR. This is in agreement with our understandings from the hierarchical structure formation theory where the galaxy stellar mass is tightly connected to the halo properties (Moster et al., 2010; Wechsler and Tinker, 2018) and the halo properties are further correlated with the environment (Lemson and Kauffmann, 1999; Sheth and Tormen, 2004). So these two correlations, that is those between stellar mass and the halo properties, and between halo properties and the environment, prompt a tighter correlation between stellar mass and the environment.

When we compare the MCFs computed using stellar masses from different estimates, we observe that the MCFs with GAMA masses (Taylor et al., 2011), *WISE* masses (Cluver et al.,

2014), and ProSpect masses (Robotham et al., 2020) closely agree with each other. Only a weak disagreement is found in the lowest redshift sample \mathcal{P} in which the M_{WISE}^* MCFs exhibit a slightly lower amplitude (2.4σ on average from M_{GAMA}^*) in the scale $r_p > 0.1 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. The reason might be the scatter between GAMA and *WISE* stellar masses observed by Cluver et al. (2014) which causes the weak disagreement of M_{WISE}^* MCF in sample \mathcal{P} with other mass estimates. So we conclude that all the stellar mass estimates we used are equally good in tracing the galaxy clustering.

When it comes to the SFR, we observe that all corresponding MCFs (except that of *WISE* SFRs in the lowest redshift range) take values smaller than unity for separation scale in the range $0.05 < r_p < 60 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. This implies that SFR is anti-correlated with the galaxy local density and there is a small probability of finding pairs of actively star-forming galaxies in the dense regions of the LSS. This can be explained in the context of galaxy evolution. As galaxies evolve, they get their hot gas reservoir removed as a result of different galaxy processes such as ram-pressure stripping (Gunn and Gott, 1972), galaxy harassment (Moore et al., 1999), and tidal disruptions (Merritt, 1983). This results in a suppression of star formation activity in the dense environment (Gómez et al., 2003).

The anti-correlation between SFR and the environment can also be due to the AGN activity. It is known that massive galaxies tend to host an AGN (Wang and Kauffmann, 2008; Magliocchetti et al., 2020). Due to the stronger clustering tendency of massive galaxies, the denser regions of the LSS tend to have more AGN activity that expel gas from its host galaxy thereby terminating the star formation in the galaxy (Cheung et al., 2016; Argudo-Fernández et al., 2016).

However we observe an increase in the amplitude of SFR MCFs in the scales $r_p < 0.2 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. Enhancement of star formation on those scales are expected due to the tidal interactions (Kennicutt, 1998; Li et al., 2008; Wong et al., 2011). The rise in SFR MCF in scales $r_p < 0.2 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$ is most likely the evidence of small-scale galaxy interaction. Gunawardhana et al. (2018) also made a similar observation with SFR MCF in their stellar mass selected samples from the GAMA survey.

By comparing the MCFs measured using different estimates of SFR, we see that GAMA SFR and ProSpect SFR trace the environment in a similar way. The MCFs with *WISE* SFRs as marks, on the other hand show significantly different amplitudes than those with GAMA SFR, especially in the lowest redshift slice (see Fig. 5.6). However, as mentioned in Sect. 5.4.3, $\text{SFR}_{12\text{WISE}}$ and $\text{SFR}_{22\text{WISE}}$ have been measured using *WISE* W3 and W4 luminosities, respectively, and these mid-IR luminosities present only partial information about the total star formation (Jarrett et al., 2013). Additionally, the W4 band is not as sensitive as the other three bands in *WISE* (Jarrett et al., 2013). Hence, the disagreement shown between *WISE* SFRs and GAMA SFRs in the lowest redshift ranges is quite expected.

5.4.5 Selection effects on galaxy clustering

In Sect. 5.3.3, we observed that W1 selected galaxies show a slight increase in its correlation length than other bands. W2, W3, and W4 selected galaxies in our samples are basically subsets of W1 selected sample. For example, W4 selection chooses only those galaxies that have measurements of W4 luminosity. Same goes with W2 and W3 selection.

FIGURE 5.9: Dependence of 2pCF power-law parameters on the wavelength in which the sample is selected. The samples with same redshift range are color-coded as labelled.

The wavelength dependence of 2pCF parameters for different redshifts is shown in Fig. 5.9. The W1 and W2 bands preferably select the massive galaxies. When a selection in W4 (or W3) is made, we are possibly selecting the star forming galaxies that are known to exhibit a weaker clustering in the local Universe (Hartley et al., 2010). This could be the reason why there is a tendency for the correlation length to decrease when selection goes from W1 to W4.

However, this observation can also be due to the difference in sensitivities of *WISE* bands- W3 and W4 bands being less sensitive than W1 and W2. So, the selection effect that we observe in our samples could be a combined result of the dependence of clustering on the intrinsic *WISE* band luminosities and the sensitivity of the survey.

5.5 Summary and conclusions

In this paper, we explored the possibility of using *WISE* bands for tracing the environment in which galaxies live. We used a set of magnitude selected galaxy samples from the GAMA-*WISE* catalogue in the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$. Using MCF, we checked how the *WISE* bands trace the galaxy clustering. We compared how stellar masses and SFRs from three different estimates (GAMA, *WISE*, and ProSpect) trace the environment using MCFs. Additionally, using 2pCF we studied the luminosity dependence and redshift evolution of galaxy clustering.

The summary of our main results and conclusions of this work is as follows.

- We concluded that in terms of galaxy clustering studies, *K* band serves as a better proxy for stellar mass than W1 band. When it comes to SFR, we concluded that the W3 band is a better proxy than the *u* band and the W4 bands (Sect. 5.3.5).
- We observed a dependence of galaxy clustering on the W1 absolute magnitude in the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$. Galaxies brighter in the W1 band exhibit stronger clustering than their fainter counterparts. At the same time we did not observe a significant redshift evolution of galaxy clustering in this redshift range (Fig. 5.4).
- By comparing the amplitudes of rank-ordered MCFs, we concluded that in W1 magnitude selected samples, stellar mass is a stronger tracer of galaxy environment than luminosities and SFR (Fig. 5.6 and Fig. 5.7).
- We found that the W1 ($3.4 \mu\text{m}$) and W2 ($4.6 \mu\text{m}$) band luminosities can be the better choices among all the *WISE* bands after stellar mass for tracing the galaxy clustering.
- On the other hand, we found that W3 ($12 \mu\text{m}$) and W4 ($22 \mu\text{m}$) bands follow SFR in general.
- We observed a general agreement between different estimates of stellar mass in tracing the clustering, however we highlighted the necessity of caution while using different SFR estimates for tracing the clustering.
- We observed a weak dependence of clustering on the selection we apply on the sample (Fig. 5.5). The W4 selected galaxies exhibit a weaker clustering in the redshift range we considered.

All the research described in this chapter were done by me, and the resulting publication is submitted to *Astronomy&Astrophysics* (Sureshkumar et al., 2022).

Chapter 6

Influence of flux-limit on clustering measurements

*This chapter originally appeared as a part of ‘Galaxy and Mass Assembly (GAMA): Tracing galaxy environment using the marked correlation function’ by [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#); *Astronomy&Astrophysics*, 653, A35 ([arXiv:2102.04177](#)). All research work implemented in this chapter were done by me.*

6.1 Introduction

The galaxy surveys are usually flux-limited. That is, the survey can only observe objects above a particular apparent magnitude limit. Therefore, extra care has to be taken while working with stellar mass selected samples extracted from such surveys. They may tend to miss galaxies that are massive enough to pass the mass selection, but not luminous enough to reach the flux limit of the survey ([Meneux et al., 2008, 2009](#); [Zehavi et al., 2011](#); [Marulli et al., 2013](#)). This effect makes such samples incomplete and hence can influence the galaxy clustering measurements. In this chapter we try to understand how the flux limit of a survey affects the measured clustering and what steps are needed to account for resulting inaccuracies.

We compute the MCFs on stellar-mass-selected samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ using absolute magnitudes in the u, g, r, J , and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR (SFR per unit stellar mass) of galaxies as marks. We explore the effect of apparent flux limits on the correlation between small-scale clustering and galaxy properties. For this purpose, we impose various flux limits to the parent sample from the GAMA survey. Further we compare the MCFs using different marks to see how these functions are affected by the change in flux limit. We also compare the measurements in our GAMA sample with those from SDSS. We select samples from SDSS because it provides a larger number of galaxies to brighter flux limits than GAMA.

This chapter is structured as follows. In Sect. 6.2 we describe properties of the samples used in the study. Clustering measurements are presented and discussed in Sect. 6.3 and finally concluded in Sect. 6.5.

TABLE 6.1: Definitions of the galaxy samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, as used in this study. The columns represent the stellar mass cut, sample label, survey of origin, flux limit, and number of galaxies.

$\log \left(\frac{M_*}{M_\odot} \right)^{\min}$	Sample	Survey	r_{lim}	N_{gal}
10.4	$\mathcal{B}1$	GAMA	19.8	10706
	$\mathcal{B}2$	GAMA	17.8	5907
10.8	$\mathcal{C}1$	GAMA	19.8	3811
	$\mathcal{C}2$	GAMA	18.8	3752
	$\mathcal{C}3$	GAMA	17.8	3367
	$\mathcal{C}4$	SDSS	17.8	22772
	$\mathcal{C}5$	SDSS	16.8	11346

6.2 Data

6.2.1 Sample selection in GAMA

The samples used in this work covers a redshift range of $0.1 < z < 0.16$. First, we select two samples from the GAMA survey (see Sect. 2.1 for details). To investigate how the environmental dependence of the galaxy properties varies with different flux limits, we select two stellar-mass-selected samples in the same redshift range with a stellar mass cut of $\log(M_*/M_\odot)^{\min} = 10.4$ but different flux limits: Sample $\mathcal{B}1$ with $r < 19.8$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ with $r < 17.8$. The stellar mass and redshift distribution of these samples are shown in Fig. 6.1. The definition and properties of all the selected samples are given in Table 6.1 and Table 6.2 respectively. All the selected samples contain a sufficient number of galaxies for reliable clustering measurements.

For all the selected samples, random samples are selected from RANDOMSV02 DMU (Farrow et al., 2015) after applying corresponding r -band apparent magnitude cut and stellar mass cut as described in Sect. 4.2.1.

FIGURE 6.1: Redshift and stellar mass distribution of galaxies in stellar-mass-selected samples $\mathcal{B}1$ ($r < 19.8$; brown dots) and $\mathcal{B}2$ ($r < 17.8$; green circles). The top and right histograms show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

TABLE 6.2: Properties of the galaxy samples defined in Table 6.1. The columns represent the sample label, mean absolute magnitudes in the u , g , r , J , and K bands, mean stellar mass, and 16-, 50- (median), and 84-percentiles of SFR and sSFR of the corresponding sample. The uncertainty with each property mean represents its standard deviation within the sample.

Sample	$M_u^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	$M_g^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	$M_r^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	$M_J^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	$M_K^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	$\log \left(\frac{M_*}{M_\odot} \right)^{\text{mean} \pm 1\sigma}$	SFR ^(16%,50%,84%) ($M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$)	sSFR ^(16%,50%,84%) ($\times 10^{-12} \text{yr}^{-1}$)
B1	-19.46 ± 0.74	-20.88 ± 0.69	-21.59 ± 0.67	-22.57 ± 0.65	-22.63 ± 0.65	10.75 ± 0.27	(0.02, 0.26, 2.91)	(0.42, 5.35, 73.80)
B2	-19.84 ± 0.62	-21.25 ± 0.58	-21.95 ± 0.58	-22.91 ± 0.59	-22.96 ± 0.60	10.88 ± 0.28	(0.03, 0.43, 3.90)	(0.42, 5.72, 90.69)
C1	-20.00 ± 0.65	-21.49 ± 0.58	-22.24 ± 0.55	-23.24 ± 0.53	-23.30 ± 0.54	11.05 ± 0.22	(0.03, 0.19, 2.05)	(0.29, 2.19, 29.33)
C2	-19.98 ± 0.63	-21.47 ± 0.57	-22.23 ± 0.54	-23.23 ± 0.52	-23.29 ± 0.53	11.05 ± 0.21	(0.03, 0.19, 2.06)	(0.29, 2.14, 28.02)
C3	-20.02 ± 0.59	-21.52 ± 0.53	-22.27 ± 0.52	-23.26 ± 0.51	-23.32 ± 0.52	11.06 ± 0.21	(0.023, 0.20, 2.32)	(0.29, 2.10, 29.38)
C4	-19.73 ± 0.59	-21.53 ± 0.35	-22.29 ± 0.35	...	-23.33 ± 0.39	11.16 ± 0.23	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)
C5	-19.86 ± 0.52	-21.63 ± 0.35	-22.39 ± 0.38	...	-23.47 ± 0.39	11.19 ± 0.25	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)

6.2.2 Sample selection in SDSS

FIGURE 6.2: Redshift and stellar mass distribution of stellar-mass-selected samples mentioned in Table 6.1. The left panel represents the $\mathcal{C}1$ ($r < 19.8$; black dots), $\mathcal{C}2$ ($r < 18.8$; red circles), and $\mathcal{C}3$ ($r < 17.8$; green squares) galaxy samples from GAMA and the right panel shows the $\mathcal{C}4$ ($r < 17.8$; blue dots) and $\mathcal{C}5$ ($r < 16.8$; orange squares) galaxy samples from SDSS. The top and right histograms of both the panels show the distribution of redshift and stellar mass, respectively.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

Apart from the comparisons between $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$, we also compare the results with the SDSS LSS catalogue (see Sect. 6.2.2 for details) to understand better how brighter flux limits can affect our measurements. For better statistics, we fix the brightest magnitude limit in our work to be $r < 16.8$. For comparison between GAMA and SDSS, we define five stellar-mass-selected samples with the same stellar mass cut of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.8$, but different flux limits. This gives samples $\mathcal{C}1$, $\mathcal{C}2$, $\mathcal{C}3$ from our parent sample in GAMA with flux limits of $r < 19.8$, 18.8 , 17.8 , respectively. From SDSS, we have samples $\mathcal{C}4$, $\mathcal{C}5$ with flux limit of $r < 17.8$, 16.8 , respectively. More details of these samples are given in Table 6.1 and Table 6.2, respectively, and their mass distribution is shown in Fig. 6.2. The SFRs, sSFRs, and K -band absolute magnitudes of SDSS samples mentioned in Table 6.2 are derived from the same SED fits from which SDSS stellar masses are derived. The absolute magnitudes in the u , g , and r bands of SDSS samples are taken from the PHOTOZ table ([Beck et al., 2016](#)). The angular distribution of random galaxies for each SDSS sample are taken from the LSS random catalogue and the redshift is randomly assigned from a smoothed $N(z)$ distribution of the corresponding real galaxy sample.

6.3 Results with GAMA and SDSS

FIGURE 6.3: Rank-ordered projected MCFs $M_p(r_p)$ for samples $\mathcal{B}1$ (left) and $\mathcal{B}2$ (right) with different flux limits, as labelled. The different symbols represent different marks considered for the $M_p(r_p)$ measurement (as labelled) and the error bars are obtained by random scrambling of the marks.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

In this section, we present the measurements of 2pCFs and rank-ordered MCFs for various stellar-mass-selected samples described in Table 6.1 and Table . Each 2pCF is fitted with a power-law model and the MCFs are measured using eight different properties as marks: absolute magnitudes in $u, g, r, J,$ and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR. In all the samples, we could reliably measure the CFs in the range $0.1 < r_p < 10 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$. The errors in $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from 12 jackknife realisations and the errors in $M_p(r_p)$ are obtained by randomising the marks (100 times). The best-fitting power-law parameters for 2pCFs in all the samples are given in Table 6.3.

6.3.1 Dependence on flux limit

To study the impact of survey flux limit on the environmental dependence of galaxy properties, we select two distinct samples with the same stellar mass cut $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$, but different flux limits: sample $\mathcal{B}1$ with $r < 19.8$ and sample $\mathcal{B}2$ with $r < 17.8$ (see Table 6.1 for details). In Fig. 6.3, we show the measurements of MCFs for both of these galaxy samples. A direct comparison of results is shown in Fig. 6.4, where we present a 2pCFs (left panel) and the ratio

FIGURE 6.4: Projected 2PCFs $\omega_p(r_p)$ for samples $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ (filled markers; left panel) and the ratio $M_{\mathcal{B}2}/M_{\mathcal{B}1}$ between MCFs obtained for these two samples (unfilled markers; right panel). The different symbols in the right panel represent the ratio between different MCFs measured with corresponding galaxy property chosen as a mark. Small offsets along x-axis have been added for clarity. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively). In the right panel, the errors are calculated in quadrature.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

between the MCFs (right panel) measured for sample $\mathcal{B}2$ and sample $\mathcal{B}1$ using different galaxy properties as marks. The error bars in the right panel is obtained in quadrature¹.

For the same flux limit ($r < 19.8$), sample $\mathcal{B}1$ exhibits a larger correlation length than $\mathcal{A}1$ in Chapter. 4, although within 1σ (see Table 6.3). By definition, $\mathcal{A}1$ contains many more less massive galaxies than $\mathcal{B}1$. Our observation that $\mathcal{B}1$ shows slightly stronger clustering than $\mathcal{A}1$ therefore agrees with the common observation that more massive galaxies exhibit stronger clustering than less massive ones (e.g. [Skibba et al., 2015](#); [Durkalec et al., 2018](#)). We also observe in the left panel of Fig. 6.3 that the stellar mass and g, r, J , and K -band MCFs of $\mathcal{B}1$ sample exhibit lower amplitude than those in $\mathcal{A}1$, with g, r, J , and K -band MCFs falling below unity.

When it comes to sample $\mathcal{B}2$, most of the MCFs show a higher amplitude relative to $\mathcal{B}1$ (as shown in the Fig. 6.3). This can also be observed in the right panel of Fig. 6.4 in which the ratio of MCFs of $\mathcal{B}2$ to that of $\mathcal{B}1$ are above unity on most of the scales. This can be associated with the stellar mass incompleteness effect and Sect. 6.4 deals with a discussion on this effect. The stellar mass can still be used as a good indicator of galaxy environment; MCF, with the stellar mass used as mark, exhibits stronger deviation from unity than MCF with any of the luminosity

¹<http://phylabs1.physics.sunysb.edu/introlabs/ReferenceDocs/ErrorAnalysis.pdf>

FIGURE 6.5: Projected 2pCFs (filled markers; left panel) and stellar mass MCFs (unfilled markers; right panel) in GAMA and SDSS surveys. The different symbols represent the measurements in different samples as labelled. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method and those for $M_p(r_p)$ are obtained by random scrambling of the marks. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ , 2σ , and 3σ error contours (solid, dashed, and dotted, respectively). Small offsets along x-axis have been added for clarity.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2021\)](#)

marks.

However, the change in the flux limit does not affect our 2pCF measurements. The correlation lengths of samples $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ agree within 1σ . The best-fit power-law parameters for the sample $\mathcal{B}1$ take the values of $r_0 = 6.10 \pm 0.86 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ and $\gamma = 1.86 \pm 0.06$, whereas the same parameters for sample $\mathcal{B}2$ are $r_0 = 5.64 \pm 0.70 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ and $\gamma = 1.80 \pm 0.07$.

6.3.2 Comparison with the SDSS

To further check the effect of survey flux limit on clustering measurements, we extend our studies to even lower magnitude cuts. For that we use data from the SDSS survey. We select a total number of five samples: three from GAMA ($\mathcal{C}1, \mathcal{C}2, \mathcal{C}3$) and two from SDSS ($\mathcal{C}4, \mathcal{C}5$). Each of these samples have the same stellar mass cut ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.8$), but different flux limits. The details are given in Table 6.1. Figure 6.5 shows the results of 2pCF and MCF (with stellar mass used as mark) measurements for each of these samples. Additionally, the best-fit power-law parameters for each 2pCF are given in Table 6.3.

The correlation lengths obtained for the GAMA samples $\mathcal{C}1$, $\mathcal{C}2$, and $\mathcal{C}3$ are comparable within 1σ . In case of MCFs, the GAMA samples ($\mathcal{C}1$, $\mathcal{C}2$ and $\mathcal{C}3$) agree between each other

FIGURE 6.6: Dependence of 2pCF parameters on the apparent flux limit of the GAMA and SDSS surveys.

within the error bars. In general, we find an influence of flux limit on 2pCF parameters in SDSS: correlation length increases and the slope decreases as the flux limit increases (i.e. as the survey gets deeper). However, we do not observe such a dependence in the GAMA samples (Fig. 6.6). We connect this observation to the variation of number of galaxies differing in these samples in the Sect. 6.4.

However, the stellar mass MCFs of samples $\mathcal{C}3$ and $\mathcal{C}4$ (with the same flux limit and stellar mass limit) are noticeably different from each other on most of the scales although their correlations lengths agree with each other. We also observe significant differences between correlation lengths and MCFs of the SDSS samples $\mathcal{C}4$ and $\mathcal{C}5$.

6.4 Mass incompleteness effect of flux-limited galaxies

Samples $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ have the same stellar mass limit, but different flux limits in the r band. Namely, sample $\mathcal{B}1$ goes fainter with $r < 19.8$ and sample $\mathcal{B}2$ is brighter with $r < 17.8$ (see

TABLE 6.3: Best-fitting power-law parameters for all the galaxy samples used in this work.

$\log(M_*/M_\odot)^{\min}$	Sample	Flux limit	$r_0 (h^{-1}\text{Mpc})$	γ
10.4	$\mathcal{B}1$	$r < 19.8$	6.10 ± 0.86	1.86 ± 0.06
	$\mathcal{B}2$	$r < 17.8$	5.64 ± 0.70	1.80 ± 0.07
10.8	$\mathcal{C}1$	$r < 19.8$	6.54 ± 0.84	1.93 ± 0.10
	$\mathcal{C}2$	$r < 18.8$	6.56 ± 0.79	1.93 ± 0.10
	$\mathcal{C}3$	$r < 17.8$	6.59 ± 0.78	1.93 ± 0.11
	$\mathcal{C}4$	$r < 17.8$	7.37 ± 0.27	1.89 ± 0.03
	$\mathcal{C}5$	$r < 16.8$	6.93 ± 0.26	1.97 ± 0.04

Table 6.1 for details). As a result of the imposed flux limit, sample $\mathcal{B}2$ is partially incomplete and significantly less numerous than the complete sample $\mathcal{B}1$; sample $\mathcal{B}2$ lacks galaxies that have mass $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$ but are not luminous enough to cross the flux limit of $r < 17.8$ (Fig. 6.1).

From the measurements of 2pCFs in GAMA samples, we observe that the correlation length does not differ significantly between $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ (see left panel of Fig. 6.4). On the other hand, the MCFs are affected by the flux selection. In the right panel of Fig. 6.4, we show the ratio of MCFs between samples $\mathcal{B}2$ and $\mathcal{B}1$. It is to be noted that correlation studies based on the u -band luminosity are influenced at small scales by the imposed r -band flux thresholds. A difference between these two samples is visible in the u -band MCF on the smallest scale ($r_p \sim 0.1 h^{-1}\text{Mpc}$) in the right panel of Fig. 6.4, where a brighter sample shows a weaker MCF signal. This means that close pairs of galaxies that are similarly brighter in the u band drop out from the sample with the lower magnitude limit. The same behaviour is reflected in the SFR and sSFR MCFs. This is an important observation because the u -band luminosity is a very good tracer of star formation processes. So, even though samples $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ have the same stellar mass limit, clustering studies on a brighter flux-limited sample ($r < 17.8$) lose information about starburst galaxies. This effect has to be properly corrected for, for example by using methods discussed in Meneux et al. (2008, 2009).

As mentioned in Sect. 6.3.1, we observe a lowering of most of the MCF amplitudes while shifting from sample $\mathcal{A}1$ to $\mathcal{B}1$ (see Chapter 4). Interestingly, we also observe a rise in the amplitudes while shifting from $\mathcal{B}1$ to $\mathcal{B}2$, particularly at the larger scales. It is to be noted that, for the flux limit $r < 19.8$, sample $\mathcal{B}1$ is more stellar mass complete than $\mathcal{A}1$. Additionally, it is evident from the stellar mass histograms in Fig. 6.1 that sample $\mathcal{B}1$ is more stellar mass complete than $\mathcal{B}2$ for the same stellar mass limit $\log(M_*/M_\odot)^{\min} = 10.4$.

This suggests that the different behaviour of MCFs we observe in samples $\mathcal{A}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ is due to their stellar mass incompleteness, which in turn comes from the apparent flux limit of the

survey and the applied stellar mass limit.

We observe an enhancement in the MCFs of $\mathcal{B}2$ sample relative to $\mathcal{B}1$ at larger scales (Fig. 6.3 and right panel of Fig. 6.4). One possible reason could be the influence of the flux limit on the redshift distribution. In Fig. 6.1, it is clear that the $\mathcal{B}1$ sample is dominated by galaxies at the higher redshift. But the applied flux limit of $\mathcal{B}2$ reduces the number of galaxies at higher redshift by a factor of almost three. This effect could have been propagated to the MCFs causing them to deviate from unity at larger scale.

Mass incompleteness effects can also be observed in MCF measurements based on two differently flux-limited SDSS samples (see Fig. 6.5). The stellar mass MCF of the more incomplete sample $\mathcal{C}5$ shows a lower value than $\mathcal{C}4$ in most of the scales; the sample $\mathcal{C}5$ value varies from $\mathcal{C}4$ on average by $\Delta M_p(r_p) = 0.07 \pm 0.06$. These differences occur even though both samples have the same stellar mass limit.

We do not observe this mass incompleteness effect in GAMA samples, where amplitudes of MCFs do not change significantly with the apparent flux limit. However, although within error bars, the $\mathcal{C}3$ stellar mass MCF shows a consistently lower value than $\mathcal{C}1$ and $\mathcal{C}2$. This behaviour is similar to the $\mathcal{C}4$ and $\mathcal{C}5$ stellar mass MCFs. This can be associated with the variation in the number of galaxies that enter the flux-limited sample even with the same stellar mass limit. The SDSS sample with the brighter flux limit $r < 16.8$ ($\mathcal{C}5$) has 11426 fewer galaxies than that with the fainter limit $r < 17.8$ ($\mathcal{C}4$). At the same time, the differences between the number of galaxies in the GAMA samples ($\mathcal{C}1$, $\mathcal{C}2$, and $\mathcal{C}3$) are very small (see Table 6.1). Therefore the lack of flux limit dependence of CFs in the GAMA survey can be the result of little variation in the number of galaxies between the GAMA samples $\mathcal{C}1$, $\mathcal{C}2$, and $\mathcal{C}3$.

To study this effect further, we would have to understand the clustering properties of the galaxies missing in brighter flux-limited samples. Such studies were previously done by Meneux et al. (2008, 2009) and Marulli et al. (2013); however, these studies were only based on measurements of projected CFs. To understand detailed connections between these galaxies, we would like to measure the behaviour of different MCFs. As for now, the real data GAMA samples for this kind of studies would only consist of 300-400 galaxies (which are missing in the brighter samples). So this could only be done using catalogues built from simulations coupled with semi-analytical galaxy formation models.

6.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, we studied the dependence of 2pCFs and MCFs on the survey flux limit by comparing the measurements in two samples with different flux limits $r < 19.8$ and $r < 17.8$, but the same stellar mass limit $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$ (Sect. 6.3.1). We also did measurements in samples with GAMA galaxies that have mass $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.8$ and compared them with SDSS galaxies with the same stellar mass cut, but different flux limits (Sect. 6.3.2). In general,

we observed that the 2pCF and MCF measurements are significantly affected by the flux limit, whereas the 2pCFs remain unaffected (in the case of GAMA) or weakly affected (in the case of SDSS). From the comparative study of MCFs in different samples with the same mass selection but different apparent magnitude limits, we also observed that u band, SFR and sSFR MCFs are strongly affected at smaller scales. This impact is caused by the stellar mass incompleteness effect (Sect. 6.4). Therefore, we concluded that closer pairs of star-forming galaxies drop out of the sample when the survey becomes shallower in terms of the limiting apparent magnitude. I did all the works described in this chapter and the results were published in (Sureshkumar et al., 2021).

Chapter 7

Environmental dependence of galaxy properties in the LSST DESC CosmoDC2 catalogue

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we use 2pCF and MCF to test how well the state-of-the-art simulation catalogue CosmoDC2 (Korytov et al., 2019) reproduces the observed environmental correlations of galaxy properties. The cosmoDC2 catalogue was developed for the upcoming Vera C. Rubin observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST; Ivezić et al., 2019) as a starting point for the second data challenge carried out by the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC; LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration, 2012).

A general description of the catalogue is given in Sect. 2.3, whereas we describe the selected sample for this work in Sect. 7.2. Using the galaxies from the cosmoDC2 catalogue, we first test the stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering (Sect. 7.3). Then we compare clustering measurements in cosmoDC2 with that in the GAMA survey 7.4. Then in Sect. 7.4.3, we conduct a test to check if cosmoDC2 catalogue gets affected by the stellar-mass-incompleteness effect that we observed in GAMA (Fig. 6.4).

7.2 Sample selection

The catalogue is publicly available from the DESC data portal and can be accessed using the Python package `GCRCatalogs` (see Sect. 2.3 for details). We access the catalogue `COS-MODC2_v1.1.4_IMAGE` from which we extract the following quantities:

- Unique object identifier: `galaxy_id`
- Right Ascension: `ra`
- Declination: `dec`

- Redshift: `redshift`
- Apparent r -band magnitude: `mag_r_lsst`
- Absolute u -band magnitude: `Mag_true_u_lsst_z0`
- Absolute g -band magnitude: `Mag_true_g_lsst_z0`
- Absolute r -band magnitude: `Mag_true_r_lsst_z0`
- Stellar mass: `stellar_mass`

Then we apply a redshift filter of $0.1 < z < 0.16$ which gives 1677475 galaxies.

7.2.1 Random catalogue

Unlike GAMA and SDSS, the cosmoDC2 galaxy catalogue is not yet provided with a random catalogue. So we have to generate our own random catalogue for clustering measurements. The important requirement is that the random catalogue should cover the same sky area and match the overall redshift distribution of the real catalogue.

We use the python package HEALSPACE RANDOMS¹ to generate random galaxies in a circle around the centre of the cosmoDC2 sky region (RA=63.0, Dec=-35.0). The code is given below.

```

1 # GENERATING RANDOM RA AND DEC USING HEALSPARSE
2
3 import healparse
4
5 n_r = 20*n_d # 20 times the number of real galaxies
6
7 circ = healparse.Circle(ra=63.0, dec=-35.0, radius=17.0, value=1)
8 smap = circ.get_map(nside_coverage=2**5, nside_sparse=2**10, dtype=np.int16)
9
10 ra_rand, dec_rand = healparse.make_uniform_randoms_fast(smap, n_r)

```

Then we define a polygon using TOPCAT (Taylor, 2005) that exactly traces the sky region of cosmoDC2 (Fig. 2.3). The polygon is given by the (RA, Dec) coordinates [(47.84,-27.3), (50.63,-24.6), (52.01,-25.9), (53.42,-24.6), (54.78,-25.9), (56.24,-24.6), (57.65,-26.0), (59.07,-24.6), (60.47,-26.0), (61.88,-24.7), (63.37,-26.0), (64.68,-24.7), (66.11,-26.0), (67.49,-24.7), (68.93,-26.0), (70.28,-24.6), (71.72,-26.1), (73.16,-24.7), (74.44,-25.9), (73.16,-27.2), (75.97,-30.0), (74.51,-31.4), (75.88,-32.8), (74.53,-34.2), (75.88,-35.7), (74.47,-37.1), (75.88,-38.7), (74.53,-40.2), (75.88,-42.0), (74.47,-46.5), (71.98,-44.9), (71.39,-46.5), (68.95,-44.8), (68.27,-46.4), (65.94,-44.7), (65.13,-46.3), (62.97,-44.7), (62.10,-46.5), (59.99,-44.8), (58.96,-46.4),

¹<https://healparse.readthedocs.io/en/latest/randoms.html>

(57.00,-44.8), (55.89,-46.4), (53.86,-44.8), (52.84,-46.4), (50.94,-44.8), (49.65,-46.5), (48.13,-44.9), (49.32,-43.4), (47.93,-41.8), (49.24,-40.2), (47.89,-38.7), (49.30,-37.1), (47.95,-35.6), (49.30,-34.1), (47.95,-32.8), (49.37,-31.4), (47.93,-29.9), (49.37,-28.7), (47.82,-27.4)].

Then we use this polygon to filter the random galaxies so that we have a set of random galaxies with the same sky coverage of cosmoDC2.

The next important condition is the similar redshift distribution between the data and random sample. We model the $N(z)$ of cosmoDC2 galaxies in the redshift range $0 < z < 0.5$ using a simple Gaussian model using the `scipy.stats.norm.fit` as shown in Fig. 7.1. The model corresponds to $\mu = 0.236502$ and $\sigma = 0.095875$. This Gaussian model traces the $N(z)$, whereas smoothens the contribution from the cosmic structures. Then we randomly draw the required number of random galaxies in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ using `scipy.stats.norm.pdf`.

FIGURE 7.1: Redshift distribution of the cosmoDC2 galaxies. The red curve shows the gaussian model from which the random galaxies are drawn. The red vertical lines represent the redshift limits of the galaxies used in this work.

7.3 Stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering

In this section, we study the dependence of 2pCF on stellar mass in the cosmoDC2 galaxy catalogue. We select a set of stellar mass binned samples from the cosmoDC2 catalogue (with flux limit $r < 27.8$) as shown in Fig. 7.2. The number of galaxies in each such sample is given in Table 7.1.

TABLE 7.1: Stellar mass binned samples selected from the cosmoDC2 catalogue.

$\log(M_*/M_\odot)^{\text{range}}$	N_{gal}
7.5 - 8.0	101887
8.0 - 8.5	67300
8.5 - 9.0	41086
9.0 - 9.5	26629
9.5 - 10.0	21085
10.0 - 10.5	17168
10.5 - 11.0	10025
11.0 - 11.5	2402

We measure the projected 2pCF in each of these samples (Sect. 3.5). The uncertainties are obtained using jackknife method with 12 jackknife samples. Then we estimate the best-fitting power-law parameters as described in Sect. 3.7. The projected 2pCFs and the power-law parameters with the 1σ error contours are shown in Fig. 7.3.

In the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, we observe a stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering- massive galaxies are more strongly clustered than less massive ones. This dependence is clearly observed as an increase in the correlation length from less massive samples to more massive samples. This means that the cosmoDC2 mock catalogue successfully reproduces the stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering that is observed in real data (for e.g. Skibba et al., 2015; Farrow et al., 2015; Durkalec et al., 2018; Sureshkumar et al., 2021).

7.4 GAMA-cosmoDC2 comparison

In this section, we compare the 2pCFs and stellar mass MCFs between stellar-mass-selected samples of galaxies from the cosmoDC2 catalogue and the GAMA survey.

7.4.1 Mock GAMA sample from cosmoDC2

The flux limit of the cosmoDC2 is $r < 28$ and that of the GAMA is $r < 19.8$. As our intention in this section is to compare cosmoDC2 to GAMA, we try to create a cosmoDC2 sample that mocks the sample $\mathcal{A}1$ in Chapter 4. To recall, sample $\mathcal{A}1$ is a GAMA sample with redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, flux limit $r < 19.8$, and stellar mass limit $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$ and it contains 32401 galaxies (Table 4.1). To select a mock GAMA sample, we first select only galaxies with $r < 19.8$ from the cosmoDC2 catalogue.

The redshift-stellar mass distribution of the cosmoDC2 sample and GAMA sample with the same flux limit of $r < 19.8$ is shown in Fig. 7.4. However, we notice that the stellar masses vary

FIGURE 7.2: Stellar mass binned samples selected from the cosmoDC2 catalogue.

between both samples. The cosmoDC2 sample (yellow dots) becomes less complete than GAMA (green dots) at $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.3$ (marked by red horizontal line). Therefore, we increase the stellar mass limit and select galaxies with $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.6$ from both cosmoDC2 and GAMA. This gives 45351 cosmoDC2 galaxies and 27959 GAMA galaxies.

7.4.2 Correlation functions in cosmoDC2 and GAMA

In the two samples, we measure the 2pCF and MCF using luminosities in u , g , and r bands as well as stellar mass. We estimate the uncertainties in 2pCF using 12 jackknife samples and in MCF using random scrambling method. The result is shown in Fig. 7.5. The violet squares with dashed line corresponds to GAMA sample and the red circles with solid line corresponds to the cosmoDC2 sample in the left panel. In the right panel, all MCFs in cosmoDC2 sample carry markers with different shapes for different properties (as labelled) and those in GAMA sample are in the form of dashed lines with shaded region. In the inset of the left panel are the 1σ error contours associated with the corresponding power-law fit parameters. In the left panel of the figure, we find that the

FIGURE 7.3: *Left*: Projected 2pCFs in stellar-mass binned samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ of cosmoDC2 catalogue. *Right*: The corresponding best-fitting power-law parameters and 1σ error contours.

TABLE 7.2: Stellar mass selected samples from the cosmoDC2 catalogue and the GAMA survey.

Stellar mass limits	N_{gal}	
	cosmoDC2	GAMA
$\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.2$	22145	15005
$10.2 > \log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.6$	23206	12955

2pCF varies significantly between cosmoDC2 and GAMA with the correlation length r_0 having a greater value for the GAMA sample. However, no such disagreement is found for the slope γ .

Comparing the MCFs between GAMA and cosmoDC2 in the right panel of Fig. 7.5, we see a strong disagreement between the MCFs obtained using the same properties. However, the cosmoDC2 MCFs maintain the same hierarchy as observed in GAMA.

Now we are interested in verifying this effect if the samples are divided based on stellar mass. So we divide the cosmoDC2 and GAMA samples into two, limited by the stellar mass ranges $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.2$ and $10.2 > \log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.6$. This gives more massive and less massive samples from both cosmoDC2 and GAMA. Their number counts are given in Table 7.2.

In each of these samples, we remeasure the 2pCF and rank-ordered MCF with stellar mass as the mark. The results are shown in Fig. 7.6. The left panel shows the 2pCFs and the right panel shows the stellar mass MCFs. In each panel, the curves in green correspond to

FIGURE 7.4: Redshift-stellar mass distribution of stellar-mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 and GAMA with flux limit $r < 19.8$. The yellow dots represent the cosmoDC2 galaxies and green ones represent the GAMA galaxies. The boxes represent the redshift and stellar mass limits and the red horizontal line corresponds to $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.3$.

the massive sample ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.2$) and maroon correspond to the less massive sample ($10.2 > \log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.6$). The solid lines with markers correspond to the samples from GAMA and the dashed line with shaded regions correspond to those from the cosmoDC2. In the inset of the left panel are the 1σ error contours associated with the corresponding power-law fit parameters.

From the power-law parameters and the error contours in Fig. 7.6, we observe significant disagreement between GAMA and cosmoDC2 samples with the same stellar mass limit. In the right panel of Fig. 7.6, we see that the stellar mass MCFs of all the samples between GAMA and cosmoDC2 do not agree within the errorbar. This observation also holds for other properties, such as absolute magnitudes in u , g , and r bands as marks (see Fig. 7.8).

In Fig. 7.7, we show the dependence of the r_0 and γ parameters on the median stellar mass of the sample for both GAMA and cosmoDC2. It has results from all the samples we considered in this chapter till now. We see a continuous increase in the r_0 values for increasing stellar mass for both GAMA and cosmoDC2. However, clustering of galaxies in GAMA is systematically stronger

FIGURE 7.5: Projected 2pCFs (left panel) and rank-ordered MCFs (right panel) obtained in the stellar mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 and GAMA with the flux limit $r < 19.8$, redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$, and stellar mass range $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$.

than in cosmoDC2. But in the case of γ , we observe a less varying value till $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10$ and then a steady increase for both GAMA and cosmoDC2.

These disagreements of CFs between cosmoDC2 and GAMA imply a lack of consistency between these catalogues in tracing the environmental dependence of galaxy properties. That is, the cosmoDC2 catalogue does not reproduce the correlations between galaxy properties and their positions in the LSS up to the level of accuracy that we trace with 2pCF and MCF measurements.

7.4.3 Stellar mass incompleteness effect in the cosmoDC2 catalogue

In this section, we verify the stellar mass incompleteness effect in the cosmoDC2 catalogue by an extended investigation of the work done in Sect. 6.3.1. Similar as in that section, we select two different samples from the cosmoDC2 catalogue with the same stellar mass limit ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$), but different flux limits ($r < 19.8$ and $r < 17.8$). Both these samples have the same redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$. For comparison with GAMA, we use the same $\mathcal{B}1$ and $\mathcal{B}2$ samples from GAMA. The number of galaxies in each sample is given in Table 7.3.

In each of the four cosmoDC2 samples, we measure the 2pCF and MCFs with luminosities in u, g, r bands and stellar mass. Unlike Sect. 6.3.1, we do not consider J, K bands, SFR and sSFR simply due to their unavailability in the cosmoDC2 catalogue. The results are shown in Fig. 7.9. We have extended the scale of r_p in this analysis, i.e. the 2pCFs and MCFs are measured for $0.04 < r_p < 69.2 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$. In the left panel of Fig. 7.9, we show the 2pCFs and the associated

FIGURE 7.6: Projected 2pCFs (left panel) and rank-ordered stellar mass MCFs (right panel) obtained in the stellar mass selected samples from cosmoDC2 (dashed lines with shaded regions) and GAMA (solid line with markers) with the flux limit $r < 19.8$ and redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$.

TABLE 7.3: Stellar mass selected samples in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ with the same stellar mass limit ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.4$) but different flux limits from the cosmoDC2 catalogue and the GAMA survey.

Flux limit	N_{gal}	
	cosmoDC2	GAMA
$r < 19.8$	15557	10706
$r < 18.8$	9799	5907

power-law fit parameters with 1σ error contours in the inset. In the right panel, we show the ratio of MCFs obtained in $r < 17.8$ sample to that in $r < 19.8$ sample.

The correlation lengths, slopes and the σ differences of all the four samples are summarized in Table 7.4. We observe a strong disagreement between the power-law parameters of 2pCF in the cosmoDC2 samples with varying flux limits (dashed-shaded contours) with both r_0 and γ having $> 1\sigma$ difference. At the same time, this disagreement is not observed in GAMA (solid-unshaded contours) - their power-law parameters are within 1σ uncertainty. That means, the imposed flux limit is influencing the clustering results in the mock catalogue cosmoDC2, but not the observed data GAMA.

In the case of MCFs, we observe a deviation in the ratios from unity which implies that the MCFs in cosmoDC2 is also influenced by the flux limit similar to GAMA (Sect. 6.3.1). However,

FIGURE 7.7: Dependence of 2pCFs power-law fit parameters r_0 and γ on the median stellar mass of the stellar-mass-selected samples used in Sect. 7.3 and Sect. 7.4.2.

the surprising observation is that the deviation of ratios from unity shows the opposite behaviour in their scale dependence. That is, we observe that the ratios increase around $r_p = 1 h^{-1}$ Mpc for GAMA but decrease for cosmoDC2. This difference may be associated with the discrepancy that we observed between GAMA and cosmoDC2 in Sect. 7.4.2.

7.5 Conclusions

The main aim of this chapter was to verify how accurately the cosmoDC2 sky catalogue (Korytov et al., 2019) reproduces the observed environmental dependence of galaxy properties. First, we implemented a classic analysis to test whether the catalogue reproduces the well-known stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering. For that we selected eight stellar-mass-binned samples and measured 2pCF in each of them. The power-law parameters thus obtained in those samples clearly exhibit the stellar mass dependence of galaxy clustering - more massive galaxies tend to exhibit stronger clustering than less massive ones (Sect. 7.3).

FIGURE 7.8: Same comparison between GAMA and cosmoDC2 as in the right panel of Fig. 7.6. Here the marks are the absolute magnitudes in u , g , and r bands.

TABLE 7.4: Power-law parameters of the samples selected from GAMA and cosmoDC2 with different flux limits but same stellar mass limit.

Power-law parameter	GAMA			CosmoDC2		
	$r < 19.8$	$r < 17.8$	σ	$r < 19.8$	$r < 17.8$	σ
$r_0(h^{-1}\text{Mpc})$	6.62 ± 1.05	6.47 ± 1.02	0.1	5.30 ± 0.27	7.22 ± 0.77	2.4
γ	1.79 ± 0.09	1.76 ± 0.07	0.3	2.00 ± 0.04	1.53 ± 0.07	5.8

Then we measured 2pCFs and stellar mass MCF in three different stellar-mass-limited samples from GAMA and cosmoDC2 (Sect. 7.4.2). We compared the CFs between GAMA and cosmoDC2 samples with the same stellar mass limit. We observed disagreements between the 2pCFs and the MCFs between GAMA and cosmoDC2. With this observation, we concluded that the cosmoDC2 mock catalogue does not perfectly reproduce the environmental dependence of the galaxy properties.

We also extended the analysis in Sect. 6.3.1 to see the effect of stellar mass incompleteness effect in cosmoDC2 (Sect. 7.4.3). We observed that the cosmoDC2 samples show the effect of stellar mass incompleteness, but in the opposite way to the GAMA samples. We conclude that this can also be the effect of the disagreement between GAMA and cosmoDC2 in reproducing the environmental dependence of galaxy properties. This issue has to be investigated in detail by studying the models and various assumptions used in the creation of the cosmoDC2 catalogue (Korytov et al., 2019). However, that is beyond the scope of this thesis, and we plan to implement that study in the future using different mock catalogues, for example, the Buzzard catalogue (DeRose et al., 2019). A publication with the results of this chapter is in preparation.

FIGURE 7.9: *Left panel:* Projected 2PCFs for samples with $r < 17.8$ and $r < 19.8$ in GAMA (solid lines with markers) and cosmoDC2 (dashed lines with shaded region). *Right panel:* The ratio $M_{17.8}/M_{19.8}$ between MCFs obtained for these two samples. The different symbols in the right panel represent the ratio between different MCFs measured with corresponding galaxy property chosen as a mark. The error bars for $\omega_p(r_p)$ are obtained from jackknife resampling method. The inset in the left panel shows the power-law fit parameters (filled stars) and their 1σ error contours. In the right panel, the errors are calculated in quadrature.

Chapter 8

Summary and conclusions

In this thesis, I described the study on the environmental dependence of galaxy properties such as luminosities in optical to mid-IR bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR in various redshift ranges using a set of galaxy samples selected from the GAMA survey (Driver et al., 2009), SDSS (York et al., 2000), and cosmoDC2 mock catalogue (Korytov et al., 2019). The major aim of the thesis was to investigate how different galaxy properties are correlated with the environment in which the galaxies live, thereby finding a way to optimally describe the correlations of properties with the environment at different scales. We also studied the influence of the survey flux limit on the clustering measurements. The summary and main conclusions of this thesis are as follows.

The tools used to address these questions were the two-point correlation function (2pCF) and the marked correlation function (MCF). During the initial stage of this work, I developed a well-performing C code for computing 2pCF and MCF. The code uses OpenMP for parallel programming so that it computes the 2pCF for different jackknife regions in parallel and the MCF for different properties in parallel. I have also written a separate code for power-law modelling of 2pCF using the covariance matrix and generalised χ^2 -minimisation (see Chapter 3).

Using these codes, I first studied the environmental dependence of optical and near-IR luminosities, stellar mass, and SFR in the GAMA survey. We checked how these properties are correlated with the environment. We measured the 2pCF and MCFs in a stellar-mass-complete sample in the redshift range $0.1 < z < 0.16$ with a flux limit $r < 19.8$ and stellar mass cut $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.3$. The MCFs were measured using different properties such as luminosities in the u , g , r , J , and K bands, stellar mass, SFR, and sSFR as marks. We demonstrated how efficiently do MCFs trace the difference in environmental correlations of different galaxy properties. We found that, among all the properties used, stellar mass shows the strongest correlation and SFR shows the strongest anti-correlation with the environment. We also found that in these correlations, the K band ($2.2 \mu\text{m}$) follows the stellar mass and the u band ($0.3 \mu\text{m}$) follows the SFR although neither of them perfectly follows (see Chapter 4).

We extended the analysis to mid-infrared galaxy properties using the WISE counterparts of GAMA galaxies. We used a set of $3.4 \mu\text{m}$ -selected galaxy samples from the GAMA-WISE catalogue (Cluver et al., 2014) in the redshift range $0.07 \leq z < 0.43$. Using MCF, we studied how the WISE bands trace the environment. We showed that luminosities in the W1 band (3.4

μm) and W2 band ($4.6 \mu\text{m}$) trace the environment similarly, although not exactly the same as stellar mass. Similarly, we found that the W3 band ($12 \mu\text{m}$) and W4 band ($22 \mu\text{m}$) follow SFR in tracing the environment. We also compared how the stellar masses and SFRs estimated using three different methods (GAMA, *WISE*, and ProSpect) trace the environment, for which we found a general agreement between these estimates. Additionally, we studied the luminosity dependence and redshift evolution of galaxy clustering using 2pCF. We concluded that the galaxies brighter in the W1 band are more clustered. However, no significant redshift evolution of the galaxy clustering was observed within the range of redshift that we considered (see Chapter 5).

We also studied the impact of the survey flux limit on clustering measurements. For that we compared the 2pCF and MCF measurements in GAMA samples that have the same selection in redshift and stellar mass, but different selection in flux limit. We repeated these measurements in SDSS galaxy samples with similar selection. We demonstrated the significant impact of the survey flux limit on 2pCF and MCF measurements (see Chapter 6).

We explored the property-environment correlations in the cosmoDC2 catalogue and compared the measurements to those in GAMA. We demonstrated that the cosmoDC2 mock catalogue, developed using AlphaQ simulation and UNIVERSEMACHINE modelling approach, does not reproduce the environmental dependence of the galaxy properties observed in GAMA and SDSS.

Our measurements are the first of this kind with galaxies as faint as $r < 19.8$. Our results can be a useful reference for clustering studies with flux-limited surveys. In particular, the conclusions in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 together are very important, as they suggest being very careful when using redder bands of luminosity as proxy of stellar mass and bluer bands as proxy of SFR in the context of galaxy clustering. The conclusion in Chapter 6 puts forward a warning to be cautious about the possible incompleteness effects caused by the survey flux limit on samples selected based on a galaxy property, especially stellar mass. Some of the results mentioned in this thesis have been published and recognised by the scientific community (for e.g. Riggs et al., 2021; Massara et al., 2022).

I believe that this thesis works as a useful reference in future galaxy clustering studies, in particular the Chapter 3 for young scientists. I hope that the outcomes of this work bring new perspectives into galaxy studies and thereby contribute to our understanding of the formation and evolution of the large-scale structure of the Universe.

Appendix A

Equatorial coordinate system

The coordinate system used to specify the position of celestial objects like planets, stars, galaxies, satellites, etc. is called the celestial coordinate system. This section deals with the equatorial coordinate system that is always used in this thesis.

Coordinate systems are designed so that all celestial objects are projected on the surface of a huge sphere called *celestial sphere*, and the observer is considered to be at the centre of the sphere. The positional change of the observer is neglected since the radius of the celestial sphere is practically infinite. The *fundamental plane* passing through the centre of the celestial sphere divides it into two hemispheres. The poles are located at the $\pm 90^\circ$ from the plane.

FIGURE A.1: The celestial sphere.
Image credit: [Las Cumbres Observatory](#)

The extension of equatorial plane of the Earth marks a great circle on the celestial sphere known as *celestial equator*. Since the equatorial plane is independent of the Earth's rotation, the celestial equator can be used as the fundamental plane. The points at which the extension of Earth's rotational axis meets the celestial sphere are called the *celestial poles*. The apparent

annual path of the Sun on the celestial sphere is called *ecliptic*. The ecliptic intersects the celestial equator at two points named as *equinoxes*. The equinox through which sun moves from southern hemisphere to northern hemisphere is called *vernal equinox* and the equinox exactly opposite to vernal equinox is called *autumnal equinox* (See Fig. A.1).

One of the coordinates in the equatorial coordinate system is *declination* (*Dec*) δ which is the angular separation of the object from the celestial equator. It has values from -90° to $+90^\circ$. The second coordinate, *right ascension* (*RA*) α is defined as the angle of the object from the vernal equinox measured counterclockwise along the equator. The RA is often expressed in units of time in the range [0 h, 24 h) where 24 hour = 360 degrees.

FIGURE A.2: Equatorial coordinate system.
Image credit: [Las Cumbres Observatory](#)

The other commonly used coordinate systems in astronomy are the horizontal, ecliptic, galactic, and supergalactic coordinate systems. We refer the reader to Chapter 2 of [Karttunen et al. \(2007\)](#) for a detailed explanation of all the celestial coordinate systems.

Appendix B

Some basic equations

B.1 Calculation of separation between two galaxies

Let α be the Right Ascension (RA), δ be the Declination (Dec), and z be the redshift of a galaxy. To calculate the separation between two given galaxies with the coordinates $(\alpha_1, \delta_1, z_1)$ and $(\alpha_2, \delta_2, z_2)$, we first convert the coordinates to the Cartesian coordinate system (X, Y, Z) using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= \text{comov_dist}(z) \times \cos \delta \times \cos \alpha \\ Y &= \text{comov_dist}(z) \times \cos \delta \times \sin \alpha \\ Z &= \text{comov_dist}(z) \times \sin \delta \end{aligned} \tag{B.1}$$

where $\text{comov_dist}(z)$ is the line-of-sight comoving distance of the galaxy at its redshift z computed using the Eq. 15 of [Hogg \(1999\)](#).

Then the distance between the galaxies (r) is computed using the distance formula,

$$r = \sqrt{(X_1 - X_2)^2 + (Y_1 - Y_2)^2 + (Z_1 - Z_2)^2} \tag{B.2}$$

The angular separation (θ) between the galaxies is computed using the formula,

$$\theta = \arccos \left(\sin \delta_1 \times \sin \delta_2 + \cos \delta_1 \times \cos \delta_2 \times \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \right) \tag{B.3}$$

To compute the two-dimensional 2pCF, one needs to decompose the separation vector into components parallel and perpendicular to the line-of-sight.

B.2 Determination of the maximum distance scale for CF measurements

The maximum separation scale for which CF can be measured is determined by the sky coverage A (in deg^2) and the redshift range (z_{\min}, z_{\max}) of a sample of galaxies. The all-sky comoving volume $\text{comov_vol}(z)$ out to a given redshift z can be computed using the Eq. 29 of [Hogg](#)

(1999). As the total area of the sky is 41253 deg^2 , the comoving volume enclosed by the sky area A between the redshifts z_{\min} and z_{\max} is given by,

$$\Delta V = \frac{A}{41253} \times \left(\text{comov_vol}(z_{\max}) - \text{comov_vol}(z_{\min}) \right) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The the maximum separation scale that can be probed within this volume can be approximated to $(\Delta V)^{1/3}$.

Appendix C

Different estimators of 2pCF

The two-point correlation function $\xi(r)$ can be estimated in various ways from a given galaxy sample. As we explained in Sec. 3.4, $\xi(r)$ is computed by counting and averaging the number of galaxy pairs separated by r in the sample. If $DD(r)$ is number of galaxy-galaxy pairs separated by r in the real galaxy sample, $RR(r)$ is the number of pairs from the random sample, and $DR(r)$ is the number of cross pairs of galaxies between the real and random sample, then most widely used estimators are given by,

- [Davis and Peebles \(1983\)](#) estimator:

$$\xi_{\text{DP}}(r) = \frac{\langle DD(r) \rangle}{\langle RR(r) \rangle} - 1 \quad (\text{C.1})$$

- [Hamilton \(1993\)](#) estimator:

$$\xi_{\text{Ham}}(r) = \frac{\langle DD(r) \rangle \cdot \langle RR(r) \rangle}{\langle DR(r) \rangle^2} - 1 \quad (\text{C.2})$$

- [Landy and Szalay \(1993\)](#) estimator:

$$\xi_{\text{LS}}(r) = \frac{\langle DD(r) \rangle - 2\langle DR(r) \rangle + \langle RR(r) \rangle}{\langle RR(r) \rangle}, \quad (\text{C.3})$$

In Fig. C.1, we compare the 2pCF of sample \mathcal{O} estimated using the estimators mentioned above. We observe that the ξ_{LS} is less noisy than ξ_{DP} and ξ_{Ham} . It was also observed that the Landy-Szalay estimator works better than others as it reduces the edge effect caused by survey area, also known as cosmic bias ([Bernardeau et al., 2002](#)). For a detailed comparison of these estimators, we refer the reader to [Pons-Bordería et al. \(1999\)](#).

FIGURE C.1: Redshift space 2pCF of sample \mathcal{O} calculated using three estimators: ξ_{DP} (Davis and Peebles, 1983), ξ_{Ham} (Hamilton, 1993), and ξ_{LS} (Landy and Szalay, 1993).

Appendix D

Luminosity evolution of the W1 band

Galaxies evolve in their properties across the redshifts. The redshift range we cover in this work demands correction of galaxy luminosities to account for their redshift evolution. This makes it more convenient to compare the clustering behaviour of samples at different redshift ranges.

For the same purpose, we consider the evolution of the characteristic absolute magnitude in the W1 band (M_{W1}^*) as modelled in [Lake et al. \(2018\)](#). Using the datapoints taken from the dotted black curve of the Fig. 7(a) of [Lake et al. \(2018\)](#), we fit a second order polynomial function to $M_{W1(z)}^* - M_{W1(z=0)}^*$ given by,

$$M_{W1(z)}^* - M_{W1(z=0)}^* = 1.39z^2 - 2.08z \quad (\text{D.1})$$

The fit is shown in Fig. [D.1](#). Using the function given in Eq. [D.1](#), we correct the W1 absolute magnitudes of all the galaxies in our sample to $z = 0$. That means, for each galaxy we take $M_{W1} = M'_{W1} - (M_{W1(z)}^* - M_{W1(z=0)}^*)$ where M'_{W1} is the uncorrected W1 absolute magnitude.

FIGURE D.1: Green circles are the selected points extracted from the black dotted curve in Fig. 7(a) of [Lake et al. \(2018\)](#). The red curve is the polynomial fit given by Eq. D.1.

Image credit: [Sureshkumar et al. \(2022\)](#)

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